

Patterns in Splitted Selfie Fractions

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Abstract

*By selfie fractions, we understand that a fraction, where numerator and denominators are represented by same digits, with basic operation. For more details refer author's work [15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20]. Patterned selfie fractions are understand as selfie fractions extendable in symmetric way. There are two types of patterned selfie fractions. One is **multiplicative** type and another is **splitted** type. This paper brings **splitted selfie fraction patterns** where we use the repetition of digits.*

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1 Introduction

Kieth [2, 3] for the first gave an idea of **dottable fraction**. It is a proper fraction where multiplication signs can be inserted into numerator and denominator, and the resulting fraction is equal to the original. Keith's [2, 3] idea was only with multiplication. For the first time, we extended it to other operations also, such as, with **addition, multiplication, potentiation**, etc. separately or jointly. We can think all of them together also. See below some examples studied by author [5, 6, 7, 8, 9].

1.1 Selfie Fraction

• Addable Fractions

$$\frac{96}{352} = \frac{9+6}{3+52}, \quad \frac{182}{6734} = \frac{18+2}{6+734}, \text{ etc.} \quad (1)$$

• Subtractable Fractions

$$\frac{204}{357} = \frac{20-4}{35-7}, \quad \frac{726}{1089} = \frac{72-6}{108-9}, \text{ etc.} \quad (2)$$

• Dottable Fraction

$$\frac{13}{624} = \frac{1 \times 3}{6 \times 24}, \quad \frac{416}{728} = \frac{4 \times 16}{7 \times 2 \times 8}, \text{ etc.} \quad (3)$$

• Dottable with Potentiation Fractions

$$\frac{95}{342} = \frac{9 \times 5}{3^4 \times 2}, \quad \frac{728}{1456} = \frac{7^2 \times 8}{14 \times 56}, \text{ etc.} \quad (4)$$

• Mixed Fractions: All Operations

$$\frac{4980}{5312} = \frac{4-9+80}{5 \times (3+1)^2}, \quad \frac{3249}{5168} = \frac{(3+2^4) \times 9}{(5-1) \times 68}, \text{ etc.} \quad (5)$$

Observing the examples given in (1) - (5), the numerator and denominator follows the same order of digits in both sides of each fraction separated by operations. These type of fractions, we call **Selfie fractions**. There are two situations. One when all digits appearing in each fraction are distinct and second, when there are repetitions of digits. Initially, we shall work with distinct digits. Due to big number of fractions, the repetition of digits shall be dealt elsewhere. The idea of **equivalent e fractions** is explained below.

1.2 Equivalent Selfie Fractions

Above we have given *selfie fractions* with single value in each case. There are many fractions, that can be written in more than one way, for example,

- **Addable**

$$\frac{1453}{2906} := \frac{1 + 453}{2 + 906} = \frac{145 + 3}{290 + 6} = \frac{1 + 45 + 3}{2 + 90 + 6}.$$

- **Subtractable**

$$\frac{932}{1864} := \frac{9 - 32}{18 - 64} = \frac{93 - 2}{186 - 4}.$$

- **Dottable and Addable**

$$\frac{1680}{59472} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 80}{59 \times 4 \times 72} = \frac{1 + 6 + 8 + 0}{59 + 472}.$$

- **Dottable, Addable and Subtractable**

$$\frac{302}{8154} := \frac{30 \times 2}{81 \times 5 \times 4} = \frac{3 + 02}{81 + 54} = \frac{3 - 02}{81 - 54}.$$

- **Symmetric Addable and Subtractable**

$$\frac{645}{1290} := \frac{6 - 45}{12 - 90} = \frac{6 + 45}{12 + 90}.$$

- **Dottable and Addable together**

$$\frac{284}{639} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 4}{6 + 39} = \frac{28 + 4}{6 \times (3 + 9)}.$$

- **Mixed - All Operations**

$$\frac{73842}{90516} := \frac{7 - 3 \times (8 - 4^2)}{9 \times 05 - 1 - 6} = \frac{7 \times (3 + 8) + 4^2}{90 + (5 - 1) \times 6} = \frac{738 + 4 + 2}{905 + 1 + 6}.$$

Equivalent expression given in equation (8), let us classify it as *symmetric equivalent fraction*. In this case we just change plus with minus and vice-versa. There are many fractions *double symmetric equivalent fraction* too. In this paper, we shall work with *equivalent fractions* given in equations (6)-(10). Below are few examples of equivalent fractions with all operations:

$$\frac{15}{240} := \frac{1^5}{2^4 + 0} = \frac{1 \times 5}{2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{42}{1785} := \frac{4^2}{17 \times 8 \times 5} = \frac{4 - 2}{1^7 \times 85}$$

$$\frac{95}{3420} := \frac{9 - 5}{(3 \times 4)^{2+0}} = \frac{9 \times 5}{3^4 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{163}{7824} := \frac{1^{63}}{7 \times 8 - 2 \times 4} = \frac{16 - 3}{78 \times 2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{189}{4725} := \frac{1^{89}}{4 - 7 \times (2 - 5)} = \frac{1 - 8 + 9}{47 - 2 + 5} = \frac{18 - 9}{(47 - 2) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{206}{3914} := \frac{2 - 0 \times 6}{39 - 1^4} = \frac{2 + 06}{(39 - 1) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{384}{9216} := \frac{3 \times (8 - 4)}{9 \times 2 \times 16} = \frac{3 \times 8 - 4}{(9^2 - 1) \times 6} = \frac{3^{8-4}}{9 \times 216}$$

$$\frac{624}{1950} := \frac{(6 - 2) \times 4}{1^9 \times 50} = \frac{6 \times 24}{1 \times 9 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{142}{69580} := \frac{1^{42}}{6 \times 95 - 80} = \frac{1 \times 4 \times 2}{(6 \times 9 - 5) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{149}{36207} := \frac{1^{49}}{3^{6 \times 2} - 07} = \frac{1 - 4 + 9}{3^6 \times (2 + 0 \times 7)}$$

$$\frac{172}{63984} := \frac{1^7 \times 2}{6 \times (39 - 8) \times 4} = \frac{1 \times 7 - 2}{6^3 \times 9 - 84}$$

$$\frac{173}{29064} := \frac{1^{73}}{(-2 + 9) \times 06 \times 4} = \frac{1 \times 7 - 3}{2 \times (90 - 6) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{1975}{6320} := \frac{1^{97} \times 5}{6 \times 3 - 2 + 0} = \frac{(19 - 7) \times 5}{6 \times 32 + 0}$$

$$\frac{2457}{8190} := \frac{(2 - 4 + 5)^7}{81 \times 90} = \frac{2 \times 4 \times 57}{8 \times 190}$$

$$\frac{4256}{83790} := \frac{4 \times (2 \times 5 - 6)}{(8 - 3) \times 7 \times 9 + 0} = \frac{4 \times 2^5 \times 6}{8 \times 3 \times 7 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{5608}{79213} := \frac{(-5 + 6) \times 08}{7 \times 9 \times 2 - 13} = \frac{56 + 0 \times 8}{792 - 1^3}$$

$$\frac{7690}{13842} := \frac{7 - 6 + 9 + 0}{1 \times 3 \times (8 - 4 + 2)} = \frac{(7 - 6) \times 90}{(1 \times 3^{8-4} \times 2)}$$

$$\frac{9246}{37185} := \frac{92 - 46}{37 \times 1^8 \times 5} = \frac{9 \times 2 \times 46}{37 \times 18 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{21480}{73569} := \frac{(2 - 1 + 4) \times 8 + 0}{73 - 5 + 69} = \frac{2 - 1^4 \times 80}{7 - 3 + 5 \times 6 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{67284}{90513} := \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2 \times (8 - 4)}{90 \times 5 - 1 + 3} = \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2^{8-4}}{905 - 1^3}$$

Let's consider two selfie fractions of type $\frac{11}{1089} := \frac{1 \times 1}{10 + 89}$ and $\frac{11}{10989} := \frac{1 \times 1}{10 + 989}$. We observe that there is symmetric among these two selfie fraction. This symmetry allows us to extend the fraction for higher digits. This type of fractions, we call **patterned selfie fractions**. Below is a good list of **patterned selfie fractions** in two and three digits numerators, where in some cases there is a repetition of digits. For

study on selfie fractions with repeated and non repeated digits refer Taneja [16, 17, 18, 19].

There are two types of **selfie fraction patterns**. See the examples below:

1.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{12}{384} &:= \frac{1+2}{3 \times 8 \times 4} \\ \frac{12}{3840} &:= \frac{1+2}{3 \times 8 \times 40} \\ \frac{12}{38400} &:= \frac{1+2}{3 \times 8 \times 400} \\ \frac{12}{384000} &:= \frac{1+2}{3 \times 8 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

2.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{24}{264} &:= \frac{2+4}{2+64} \\ \frac{24}{2664} &:= \frac{2+4}{2+664} \\ \frac{24}{26664} &:= \frac{2+4}{2+6664} \\ \frac{24}{266664} &:= \frac{2+4}{2+66664} \end{aligned}$$

The first type we call as "**multiplicative selfie fraction patterns**". The second type we call as "**splitted selfie fraction patterns**". The previous work of author [19] is divided in two parts. One part is only on "**multiplicative selfie fraction patterns**". The second part is on "**splitted selfie fraction patterns**". In this work we shall work with second part. For first part refer Taneja [19].

2 Splitted Selfie Fraction Patterns

2.1 Two Digits Numerator

• Number 11

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{11}{1089} &:= \frac{1 \times 1}{10 + 89} & \frac{11}{121} &:= \frac{1 + 1}{1 + 21} & \frac{11}{242} &:= \frac{1 + 1}{2 + 42} \\ \frac{11}{10989} &:= \frac{1 \times 1}{10 + 989} & \frac{11}{1221} &:= \frac{1 + 1}{1 + 221} & \frac{11}{2442} &:= \frac{1 + 1}{2 + 442} \\ \frac{11}{109989} &:= \frac{1 \times 1}{10 + 9989} & \frac{11}{12221} &:= \frac{1 + 1}{1 + 2221} & \frac{11}{24442} &:= \frac{1 + 1}{2 + 4442} \\ \frac{11}{1099989} &:= \frac{1 \times 1}{10 + 99989} & \frac{11}{122221} &:= \frac{1 + 1}{1 + 22221} & \frac{11}{244442} &:= \frac{1 + 1}{2 + 44442} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{11}{33} &:= \frac{1+1}{3+3} \\ \frac{11}{363} &:= \frac{1+1}{3+63} \\ \frac{11}{3663} &:= \frac{1+1}{3+663} \\ \frac{11}{36663} &:= \frac{1+1}{3+6663} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{11}{44} &:= \frac{1+1}{4+4} \\ \frac{11}{484} &:= \frac{1+1}{4+84} \\ \frac{11}{4884} &:= \frac{1+1}{4+884} \\ \frac{11}{48884} &:= \frac{1+1}{4+8884} \end{aligned}$$

• Number 12

$$\frac{12}{10908} := \frac{1^2}{1 + 0908}$$

$$\frac{12}{1090908} := \frac{1^2}{1 + 090908}$$

$$\frac{12}{109090908} := \frac{1^2}{1 + 09090908}$$

$$\frac{12}{1188} := \frac{1^2}{11 + 88}$$

$$\frac{12}{11988} := \frac{1^2}{11 + 988}$$

$$\frac{12}{119988} := \frac{1^2}{11 + 9988}$$

$$\frac{12}{132} := \frac{1 + 2}{1 + 32}$$

$$\frac{12}{1332} := \frac{1 + 2}{1 + 332}$$

$$\frac{12}{13332} := \frac{1 + 2}{1 + 3332}$$

$$\frac{12}{133332} := \frac{1 + 2}{1 + 33332}$$

$$\frac{12}{24} := \frac{1 + 2}{2 + 4}$$

$$\frac{12}{264} := \frac{1 + 2}{2 + 64}$$

$$\frac{12}{2664} := \frac{1 + 2}{2 + 664}$$

$$\frac{12}{26664} := \frac{1 + 2}{2 + 6664}$$

$$\frac{12}{396} := \frac{1 + 2}{3 + 96}$$

$$\frac{12}{3996} := \frac{1 + 2}{3 + 996}$$

$$\frac{12}{39996} := \frac{1 + 2}{3 + 9996}$$

$$\frac{12}{594} := \frac{1 \times 2}{5 + 94}$$

$$\frac{12}{5994} := \frac{1 \times 2}{5 + 994}$$

$$\frac{12}{59994} := \frac{1 \times 2}{5 + 9994}$$

• **Number 13**

$$\frac{13}{1287} := \frac{1^3}{12 + 87}$$

$$\frac{13}{12987} := \frac{1^3}{12 + 987}$$

$$\frac{13}{129987} := \frac{1^3}{12 + 9987}$$

$$\frac{13}{1299987} := \frac{1^3}{12 + 99987}$$

$$\frac{13}{143} := \frac{1 + 3}{1 + 43}$$

$$\frac{13}{1443} := \frac{1 + 3}{1 + 443}$$

$$\frac{13}{14443} := \frac{1 + 3}{1 + 4443}$$

$$\frac{13}{144443} := \frac{1 + 3}{1 + 44443}$$

$$\frac{13}{286} := \frac{1 + 3}{2 + 86}$$

$$\frac{13}{2886} := \frac{1 + 3}{2 + 886}$$

$$\frac{13}{28886} := \frac{1 + 3}{2 + 8886}$$

$$\frac{13}{288886} := \frac{1 + 3}{2 + 88886}$$

$$\frac{13}{429} := \frac{1^3}{4 + 29}$$

$$\frac{13}{4329} := \frac{1^3}{4 + 329}$$

$$\frac{13}{43329} := \frac{1^3}{4 + 3329}$$

$$\frac{13}{433329} := \frac{1^3}{4 + 33329}$$

$$\frac{13}{858} := \frac{1^3}{8 + 58}$$

$$\frac{13}{8658} := \frac{1^3}{8 + 658}$$

$$\frac{13}{86658} := \frac{1^3}{8 + 6658}$$

$$\frac{13}{866658} := \frac{1^3}{8 + 66658}$$

• **Number 14**

$$\frac{14}{1386} := \frac{1^4}{13 + 86}$$

$$\frac{14}{13986} := \frac{1^4}{13 + 986}$$

$$\frac{14}{139986} := \frac{1^4}{13 + 9986}$$

$$\frac{14}{1399986} := \frac{1^4}{13 + 99986}$$

$$\frac{14}{154} := \frac{1 + 4}{1 + 54}$$

$$\frac{14}{1554} := \frac{1 + 4}{1 + 554}$$

$$\frac{14}{15554} := \frac{1 + 4}{1 + 5554}$$

$$\frac{14}{155554} := \frac{1 + 4}{1 + 55554}$$

● **Number 15**

$$\frac{15}{1485} := \frac{1^5}{14 + 85}$$

$$\frac{15}{14985} := \frac{1^5}{14 + 985}$$

$$\frac{15}{149985} := \frac{1^5}{14 + 9985}$$

$$\frac{15}{1499985} := \frac{1^5}{14 + 99985}$$

$$\frac{15}{165} := \frac{1 + 5}{1 + 65}$$

$$\frac{15}{1665} := \frac{1 + 5}{1 + 665}$$

$$\frac{15}{16665} := \frac{1 + 5}{1 + 6665}$$

$$\frac{15}{166665} := \frac{1 + 5}{1 + 66665}$$

$$\frac{15}{27} := \frac{1 \times 5}{2 + 7}$$

$$\frac{15}{297} := \frac{1 \times 5}{2 + 97}$$

$$\frac{15}{2997} := \frac{1 \times 5}{2 + 997}$$

$$\frac{15}{29997} := \frac{1 \times 5}{2 + 9997}$$

● **Number 16**

$$\frac{16}{1056} := \frac{1^6}{10 + 56}$$

$$\frac{16}{10656} := \frac{1^6}{10 + 656}$$

$$\frac{16}{106656} := \frac{1^6}{10 + 6656}$$

$$\frac{16}{1066656} := \frac{1^6}{10 + 66656}$$

$$\frac{16}{1584} := \frac{1^6}{15 + 84}$$

$$\frac{16}{15984} := \frac{1^6}{15 + 984}$$

$$\frac{16}{159984} := \frac{1^6}{15 + 9984}$$

$$\frac{16}{1599984} := \frac{1^6}{15 + 99984}$$

$$\frac{16}{176} := \frac{1 + 6}{1 + 76}$$

$$\frac{16}{1776} := \frac{1 + 6}{1 + 776}$$

$$\frac{16}{17776} := \frac{1 + 6}{1 + 7776}$$

$$\frac{16}{177776} := \frac{1 + 6}{1 + 77776}$$

$$\frac{16}{528} := \frac{1^6}{5 + 28}$$

$$\frac{16}{5328} := \frac{1^6}{5 + 328}$$

$$\frac{16}{53328} := \frac{1^6}{5 + 3328}$$

$$\frac{16}{533328} := \frac{1^6}{5 + 33328}$$

● **Number 17**

$$\frac{17}{1683} := \frac{1^7}{16 + 83}$$

$$\frac{17}{16983} := \frac{1^7}{16 + 983}$$

$$\frac{17}{169983} := \frac{1^7}{16 + 9983}$$

$$\frac{17}{1699983} := \frac{1^7}{16 + 99983}$$

$$\frac{17}{187} := \frac{1 + 7}{1 + 87}$$

$$\frac{17}{1887} := \frac{1 + 7}{1 + 887}$$

$$\frac{17}{18887} := \frac{1 + 7}{1 + 8887}$$

$$\frac{17}{188887} := \frac{1 + 7}{1 + 88887}$$

• **Number 18**

$$\frac{18}{1782} := \frac{1^8}{17 + 82}$$

$$\frac{18}{17982} := \frac{1^8}{17 + 982}$$

$$\frac{18}{179982} := \frac{1^8}{17 + 9982}$$

$$\frac{18}{1799982} := \frac{1^8}{17 + 99982}$$

$$\frac{18}{198} := \frac{1 + 8}{1 + 98}$$

$$\frac{18}{1998} := \frac{1 + 8}{1 + 998}$$

$$\frac{18}{19998} := \frac{1 + 8}{1 + 9998}$$

$$\frac{18}{199998} := \frac{1 + 8}{1 + 99998}$$

• **Number 19**

$$\frac{19}{1045} := \frac{1^9}{10 + 45}$$

$$\frac{19}{10545} := \frac{1^9}{10 + 545}$$

$$\frac{19}{105545} := \frac{1^9}{10 + 5545}$$

$$\frac{19}{1055545} := \frac{1^9}{10 + 55545}$$

$$\frac{19}{1254} := \frac{1^9}{12 + 54}$$

$$\frac{19}{12654} := \frac{1^9}{12 + 654}$$

$$\frac{19}{126654} := \frac{1^9}{12 + 6654}$$

$$\frac{19}{1266654} := \frac{1^9}{12 + 66654}$$

$$\frac{19}{1463} := \frac{1^9}{14 + 63}$$

$$\frac{19}{14763} := \frac{1^9}{14 + 763}$$

$$\frac{19}{147763} := \frac{1^9}{14 + 7763}$$

$$\frac{19}{1477763} := \frac{1^9}{14 + 77763}$$

$$\frac{19}{1672} := \frac{1^9}{16 + 72}$$

$$\frac{19}{16872} := \frac{1^9}{16 + 872}$$

$$\frac{19}{168872} := \frac{1^9}{16 + 8872}$$

$$\frac{19}{1688872} := \frac{1^9}{16 + 88872}$$

$$\frac{19}{1881} := \frac{1^9}{18 + 81}$$

$$\frac{19}{18981} := \frac{1^9}{18 + 981}$$

$$\frac{19}{189981} := \frac{1^9}{18 + 9981}$$

$$\frac{19}{1899981} := \frac{1^9}{18 + 99981}$$

$$\frac{19}{2109} := \frac{1^9}{2 + 109}$$

$$\frac{19}{21109} := \frac{1^9}{2 + 1109}$$

$$\frac{19}{211109} := \frac{1^9}{2 + 11109}$$

$$\frac{19}{2111109} := \frac{1^9}{2 + 111109}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{19}{627} := \frac{1^9}{6+27} \\ \frac{19}{6327} := \frac{1^9}{6+327} \\ \frac{19}{63327} := \frac{1^9}{6+3327} \\ \frac{19}{633327} := \frac{1^9}{6+33327} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \frac{19}{836} := \frac{1^9}{8+36} \\ \frac{19}{8436} := \frac{1^9}{8+436} \\ \frac{19}{84436} := \frac{1^9}{8+4436} \\ \frac{19}{844436} := \frac{1^9}{8+44436} \end{array}$$

• **Number 21**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{21}{231} := \frac{2+1}{2+31} \\ \frac{21}{2331} := \frac{2+1}{2+331} \\ \frac{21}{23331} := \frac{2+1}{2+3331} \\ \frac{21}{233331} := \frac{2+1}{2+33331} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \frac{21}{462} := \frac{2+1}{4+62} \\ \frac{21}{4662} := \frac{2+1}{4+662} \\ \frac{21}{46662} := \frac{2+1}{4+6662} \\ \frac{21}{466662} := \frac{2+1}{4+66662} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \frac{21}{63} := \frac{2+1}{6+3} \\ \frac{21}{693} := \frac{2+1}{6+93} \\ \frac{21}{6993} := \frac{2+1}{6+993} \\ \frac{21}{69993} := \frac{2+1}{6+9993} \end{array}$$

• **Number 22**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{22}{121} := \frac{2^2}{1+21} \\ \frac{22}{1221} := \frac{2^2}{1+221} \\ \frac{22}{12221} := \frac{2^2}{1+2221} \\ \frac{22}{122221} := \frac{2^2}{1+22221} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \frac{22}{242} := \frac{2^2}{2+42} \\ \frac{22}{2442} := \frac{2^2}{2+442} \\ \frac{22}{24442} := \frac{2^2}{2+4442} \\ \frac{22}{244442} := \frac{2^2}{2+44442} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \frac{22}{363} := \frac{2^2}{3+63} \\ \frac{22}{3663} := \frac{2^2}{3+663} \\ \frac{22}{36663} := \frac{2^2}{3+6663} \\ \frac{22}{366663} := \frac{2^2}{3+66663} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{22}{44} := \frac{2^2}{4+4} \\ \frac{22}{484} := \frac{2^2}{4+84} \\ \frac{22}{4884} := \frac{2^2}{4+884} \\ \frac{22}{48884} := \frac{2^2}{4+8884} \end{array}$$

• **Number 23**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{23}{253} &:= \frac{2+3}{2+53} \\ \frac{23}{2553} &:= \frac{2+3}{2+553} \\ \frac{23}{25553} &:= \frac{2+3}{2+5553} \\ \frac{23}{255553} &:= \frac{2+3}{2+55553} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 24**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{24}{132} &:= \frac{2+4}{1+32} \\ \frac{24}{1332} &:= \frac{2+4}{1+332} \\ \frac{24}{13332} &:= \frac{2+4}{1+3332} \\ \frac{24}{133332} &:= \frac{2+4}{1+33332} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{24}{264} &:= \frac{2+4}{2+64} \\ \frac{24}{2664} &:= \frac{2+4}{2+664} \\ \frac{24}{26664} &:= \frac{2+4}{2+6664} \\ \frac{24}{266664} &:= \frac{2+4}{2+66664} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{24}{27} &:= \frac{2 \times 4}{2+7} \\ \frac{24}{297} &:= \frac{2 \times 4}{2+97} \\ \frac{24}{2997} &:= \frac{2 \times 4}{2+997} \\ \frac{24}{29997} &:= \frac{2 \times 4}{2+9997} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{24}{36} &:= \frac{2+4}{3+6} \\ \frac{24}{396} &:= \frac{2+4}{3+96} \\ \frac{24}{3996} &:= \frac{2+4}{3+996} \\ \frac{24}{39996} &:= \frac{2+4}{3+9996} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 25**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{25}{165} &:= \frac{2 \times 5}{1+65} \\ \frac{25}{1665} &:= \frac{2 \times 5}{1+665} \\ \frac{25}{16665} &:= \frac{2 \times 5}{1+6665} \\ \frac{25}{166665} &:= \frac{2 \times 5}{1+66665} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{25}{275} &:= \frac{2+5}{2+75} \\ \frac{25}{2775} &:= \frac{2+5}{2+775} \\ \frac{25}{27775} &:= \frac{2+5}{2+7775} \\ \frac{25}{277775} &:= \frac{2+5}{2+77775} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 26**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{26}{143} := \frac{2+6}{1+43} \\ \frac{26}{1443} := \frac{2+6}{1+443} \\ \frac{26}{14443} := \frac{2+6}{1+4443} \\ \frac{26}{144443} := \frac{2+6}{1+44443} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{26}{286} := \frac{2+6}{2+86} \\ \frac{26}{2886} := \frac{2+6}{2+886} \\ \frac{26}{28886} := \frac{2+6}{2+8886} \\ \frac{26}{288886} := \frac{2+6}{2+88886} \end{array}$$

• **Number 27**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{27}{297} := \frac{2+7}{2+97} \\ \frac{27}{2997} := \frac{2+7}{2+997} \\ \frac{27}{29997} := \frac{2+7}{2+9997} \\ \frac{27}{299997} := \frac{2+7}{2+99997} \end{array}$$

• **Number 28**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{28}{154} := \frac{2+8}{1+54} \\ \frac{28}{1554} := \frac{2+8}{1+554} \\ \frac{28}{15554} := \frac{2+8}{1+5554} \\ \frac{28}{155554} := \frac{2+8}{1+55554} \end{array}$$

• **Number 31**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{31}{341} := \frac{3+1}{3+41} \\ \frac{31}{3441} := \frac{3+1}{3+441} \\ \frac{31}{34441} := \frac{3+1}{3+4441} \\ \frac{31}{344441} := \frac{3+1}{3+44441} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{31}{62} := \frac{3+1}{6+2} \\ \frac{31}{682} := \frac{3+1}{6+82} \\ \frac{31}{6882} := \frac{3+1}{6+882} \\ \frac{31}{68882} := \frac{3+1}{6+8882} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{32}{352} := \frac{3+2}{3+52} \\ \frac{32}{3552} := \frac{3+2}{3+552} \\ \frac{32}{35552} := \frac{3+2}{3+5552} \\ \frac{32}{355552} := \frac{3+2}{3+55552} \end{array}$$

• **Number 33**

$$\frac{33}{121} := \frac{3+3}{1+21}$$

$$\frac{33}{1221} := \frac{3+3}{1+221}$$

$$\frac{33}{12221} := \frac{3+3}{1+2221}$$

$$\frac{33}{242} := \frac{3+3}{2+42}$$

$$\frac{33}{2442} := \frac{3+3}{2+442}$$

$$\frac{33}{24442} := \frac{3+3}{2+4442}$$

$$\frac{33}{244442} := \frac{3+3}{2+44442}$$

$$\frac{33}{363} := \frac{3+3}{3+63}$$

$$\frac{33}{3663} := \frac{3+3}{3+663}$$

$$\frac{33}{36663} := \frac{3+3}{3+6663}$$

$$\frac{33}{366663} := \frac{3+3}{3+66663}$$

$$\frac{33}{44} := \frac{3+3}{4+4}$$

$$\frac{33}{484} := \frac{3+3}{4+84}$$

$$\frac{33}{4884} := \frac{3+3}{4+884}$$

$$\frac{33}{48884} := \frac{3+3}{4+8884}$$

● **Number 34**

$$\frac{34}{153} := \frac{3 \times 4}{1+53}$$

$$\frac{34}{15453} := \frac{3 \times 4}{1+5453}$$

$$\frac{34}{1545453} := \frac{3 \times 4}{1+545453}$$

$$\frac{34}{154545453} := \frac{3 \times 4}{1+54545453}$$

$$\frac{34}{374} := \frac{3+4}{3+74}$$

$$\frac{34}{3774} := \frac{3+4}{3+774}$$

$$\frac{34}{37774} := \frac{3+4}{3+7774}$$

$$\frac{34}{377774} := \frac{3+4}{3+77774}$$

● **Number 35**

$$\frac{35}{385} := \frac{3+5}{3+85}$$

$$\frac{35}{3885} := \frac{3+5}{3+885}$$

$$\frac{35}{38885} := \frac{3+5}{3+8885}$$

$$\frac{35}{388885} := \frac{3+5}{3+88885}$$

● **Number 36**

$$\frac{36}{132} := \frac{3+6}{1+32}$$

$$\frac{36}{1332} := \frac{3+6}{1+332}$$

$$\frac{36}{13332} := \frac{3+6}{1+3332}$$

$$\frac{36}{133332} := \frac{3+6}{1+33332}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{36}{264} := \frac{3+6}{2+64} \\ \frac{36}{2664} := \frac{3+6}{2+664} \\ \frac{36}{26664} := \frac{3+6}{2+6664} \\ \frac{36}{266664} := \frac{3+6}{2+66664} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{36}{396} := \frac{3+6}{3+96} \\ \frac{36}{3996} := \frac{3+6}{3+996} \\ \frac{36}{39996} := \frac{3+6}{3+9996} \\ \frac{36}{399996} := \frac{3+6}{3+99996} \end{array}$$

● **Number 39**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{39}{143} := \frac{3+9}{1+43} \\ \frac{39}{1443} := \frac{3+9}{1+443} \\ \frac{39}{14443} := \frac{3+9}{1+4443} \\ \frac{39}{144443} := \frac{3+9}{1+44443} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{39}{286} := \frac{3+9}{2+86} \\ \frac{39}{2886} := \frac{3+9}{2+886} \\ \frac{39}{28886} := \frac{3+9}{2+8886} \\ \frac{39}{288886} := \frac{3+9}{2+88886} \end{array}$$

● **Number 36**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{41}{451} := \frac{4+1}{4+51} \\ \frac{41}{4551} := \frac{4+1}{4+551} \\ \frac{41}{45551} := \frac{4+1}{4+5551} \\ \frac{41}{455551} := \frac{4+1}{4+55551} \end{array}$$

● **Number 42**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{42}{231} := \frac{4+2}{2+31} \\ \frac{42}{2331} := \frac{4+2}{2+331} \\ \frac{42}{23331} := \frac{4+2}{2+3331} \\ \frac{42}{233331} := \frac{4+2}{2+33331} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{42}{462} := \frac{4+2}{4+62} \\ \frac{42}{4662} := \frac{4+2}{4+662} \\ \frac{42}{46662} := \frac{4+2}{4+6662} \\ \frac{42}{466662} := \frac{4+2}{4+66662} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{42}{63} := \frac{4+2}{6+3} \\ \frac{42}{693} := \frac{4+2}{6+93} \\ \frac{42}{6993} := \frac{4+2}{6+993} \\ \frac{42}{69993} := \frac{4+2}{6+9993} \end{array}$$

● **Number 43**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{43}{473} &:= \frac{4+3}{4+73} \\ \frac{43}{4773} &:= \frac{4+3}{4+773} \\ \frac{43}{47773} &:= \frac{4+3}{4+7773} \\ \frac{43}{477773} &:= \frac{4+3}{4+77773}\end{aligned}$$

● **Number 44**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{44}{121} &:= \frac{4+4}{1+21} \\ \frac{44}{1221} &:= \frac{4+4}{1+221} \\ \frac{44}{12221} &:= \frac{4+4}{1+2221} \\ \frac{44}{122221} &:= \frac{4+4}{1+22221}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{44}{242} &:= \frac{4+4}{2+42} \\ \frac{44}{2442} &:= \frac{4+4}{2+442} \\ \frac{44}{24442} &:= \frac{4+4}{2+4442} \\ \frac{44}{244442} &:= \frac{4+4}{2+44442}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{44}{363} &:= \frac{4+4}{3+63} \\ \frac{44}{3663} &:= \frac{4+4}{3+663} \\ \frac{44}{36663} &:= \frac{4+4}{3+6663} \\ \frac{44}{366663} &:= \frac{4+4}{3+66663}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{44}{484} &:= \frac{4+4}{4+84} \\ \frac{44}{4884} &:= \frac{4+4}{4+884} \\ \frac{44}{48884} &:= \frac{4+4}{4+8884} \\ \frac{44}{488884} &:= \frac{4+4}{4+88884}\end{aligned}$$

● **Number 45**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{45}{495} &:= \frac{4+5}{4+95} \\ \frac{45}{4995} &:= \frac{4+5}{4+995} \\ \frac{45}{49995} &:= \frac{4+5}{4+9995} \\ \frac{45}{499995} &:= \frac{4+5}{4+99995}\end{aligned}$$

● **Number 46**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{46}{253} &:= \frac{4+6}{2+53} \\ \frac{46}{2553} &:= \frac{4+6}{2+553} \\ \frac{46}{25553} &:= \frac{4+6}{2+5553} \\ \frac{46}{255553} &:= \frac{4+6}{2+55553} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 48**

$\begin{aligned} \frac{48}{132} &:= \frac{4+8}{1+32} \\ \frac{48}{1332} &:= \frac{4+8}{1+332} \\ \frac{48}{13332} &:= \frac{4+8}{1+3332} \\ \frac{48}{133332} &:= \frac{4+8}{1+33332} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \frac{48}{264} &:= \frac{4+8}{2+64} \\ \frac{48}{2664} &:= \frac{4+8}{2+664} \\ \frac{48}{26664} &:= \frac{4+8}{2+6664} \\ \frac{48}{266664} &:= \frac{4+8}{2+66664} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \frac{48}{396} &:= \frac{4+8}{3+96} \\ \frac{48}{3996} &:= \frac{4+8}{3+996} \\ \frac{48}{39996} &:= \frac{4+8}{3+9996} \\ \frac{48}{399996} &:= \frac{4+8}{3+99996} \end{aligned}$
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● **Number 51**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{51}{561} &:= \frac{5+1}{5+61} \\ \frac{51}{5661} &:= \frac{5+1}{5+661} \\ \frac{51}{56661} &:= \frac{5+1}{5+6661} \\ \frac{51}{566661} &:= \frac{5+1}{5+66661} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 52**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{52}{572} &:= \frac{5+2}{5+72} \\ \frac{52}{5772} &:= \frac{5+2}{5+772} \\ \frac{52}{57772} &:= \frac{5+2}{5+7772} \\ \frac{52}{577772} &:= \frac{5+2}{5+77772} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 53**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{53}{583} &:= \frac{5+3}{5+83} \\ \frac{53}{5883} &:= \frac{5+3}{5+883} \\ \frac{53}{58883} &:= \frac{5+3}{5+8883} \\ \frac{53}{588883} &:= \frac{5+3}{5+88883} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 54**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{54}{594} &:= \frac{5+4}{5+94} \\ \frac{54}{5994} &:= \frac{5+4}{5+994} \\ \frac{54}{59994} &:= \frac{5+4}{5+9994} \\ \frac{54}{599994} &:= \frac{5+4}{5+99994} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 55**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{55}{121} &:= \frac{5+5}{1+21} \\ \frac{55}{1221} &:= \frac{5+5}{1+221} \\ \frac{55}{12221} &:= \frac{5+5}{1+2221} \\ \frac{55}{122221} &:= \frac{5+5}{1+22221} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{55}{242} &:= \frac{5+5}{2+42} \\ \frac{55}{2442} &:= \frac{5+5}{2+442} \\ \frac{55}{24442} &:= \frac{5+5}{2+4442} \\ \frac{55}{244442} &:= \frac{5+5}{2+44442} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{55}{363} &:= \frac{5+5}{3+63} \\ \frac{55}{3663} &:= \frac{5+5}{3+663} \\ \frac{55}{36663} &:= \frac{5+5}{3+6663} \\ \frac{55}{366663} &:= \frac{5+5}{3+66663} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{55}{484} &:= \frac{5+5}{4+84} \\ \frac{55}{4884} &:= \frac{5+5}{4+884} \\ \frac{55}{48884} &:= \frac{5+5}{4+8884} \\ \frac{55}{488884} &:= \frac{5+5}{4+88884} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 61**

$$\frac{61}{671} := \frac{6+1}{6+71}$$

$$\frac{61}{6771} := \frac{6+1}{6+771}$$

$$\frac{61}{67771} := \frac{6+1}{6+7771}$$

$$\frac{61}{677771} := \frac{6+1}{6+77771}$$

● **Number 62**

$$\frac{62}{341} := \frac{6+2}{3+41}$$

$$\frac{62}{3441} := \frac{6+2}{3+441}$$

$$\frac{62}{34441} := \frac{6+2}{3+4441}$$

$$\frac{62}{344441} := \frac{6+2}{3+44441}$$

$$\frac{62}{682} := \frac{6+2}{6+82}$$

$$\frac{62}{6882} := \frac{6+2}{6+882}$$

$$\frac{62}{68882} := \frac{6+2}{6+8882}$$

$$\frac{62}{688882} := \frac{6+2}{6+88882}$$

● **Number 63**

$$\frac{63}{231} := \frac{6+3}{2+31}$$

$$\frac{63}{2331} := \frac{6+3}{2+331}$$

$$\frac{63}{23331} := \frac{6+3}{2+3331}$$

$$\frac{63}{233331} := \frac{6+3}{2+33331}$$

$$\frac{63}{462} := \frac{6+3}{4+62}$$

$$\frac{63}{4662} := \frac{6+3}{4+662}$$

$$\frac{63}{46662} := \frac{6+3}{4+6662}$$

$$\frac{63}{466662} := \frac{6+3}{4+66662}$$

$$\frac{63}{693} := \frac{6+3}{6+93}$$

$$\frac{63}{6993} := \frac{6+3}{6+993}$$

$$\frac{63}{69993} := \frac{6+3}{6+9993}$$

$$\frac{63}{699993} := \frac{6+3}{6+99993}$$

● **Number 64**

$$\frac{64}{352} := \frac{6+4}{3+52}$$

$$\frac{64}{3552} := \frac{6+4}{3+552}$$

$$\frac{64}{35552} := \frac{6+4}{3+5552}$$

$$\frac{64}{355552} := \frac{6+4}{3+55552}$$

● **Number 66**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{66}{121} &:= \frac{6+6}{1+21} \\ \frac{66}{1221} &:= \frac{6+6}{1+221} \\ \frac{66}{12221} &:= \frac{6+6}{1+2221} \\ \frac{66}{122221} &:= \frac{6+6}{1+22221} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{66}{242} &:= \frac{6+6}{2+42} \\ \frac{66}{2442} &:= \frac{6+6}{2+442} \\ \frac{66}{24442} &:= \frac{6+6}{2+4442} \\ \frac{66}{244442} &:= \frac{6+6}{2+44442} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{66}{363} &:= \frac{6+6}{3+63} \\ \frac{66}{3663} &:= \frac{6+6}{3+663} \\ \frac{66}{36663} &:= \frac{6+6}{3+6663} \\ \frac{66}{366663} &:= \frac{6+6}{3+66663} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{66}{484} &:= \frac{6+6}{4+84} \\ \frac{66}{4884} &:= \frac{6+6}{4+884} \\ \frac{66}{48884} &:= \frac{6+6}{4+8884} \\ \frac{66}{488884} &:= \frac{6+6}{4+88884} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 68**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{68}{374} &:= \frac{6+8}{3+74} \\ \frac{68}{3774} &:= \frac{6+8}{3+774} \\ \frac{68}{37774} &:= \frac{6+8}{3+7774} \\ \frac{68}{377774} &:= \frac{6+8}{3+77774} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 69**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{69}{253} &:= \frac{6+9}{2+53} \\ \frac{69}{2553} &:= \frac{6+9}{2+553} \\ \frac{69}{25553} &:= \frac{6+9}{2+5553} \\ \frac{69}{255553} &:= \frac{6+9}{2+55553} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 71**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{71}{781} &:= \frac{7+1}{7+81} \\ \frac{71}{7881} &:= \frac{7+1}{7+881} \\ \frac{71}{78881} &:= \frac{7+1}{7+8881} \\ \frac{71}{788881} &:= \frac{7+1}{7+88881} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 72**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{72}{792} &:= \frac{7+2}{7+92} \\ \frac{72}{7992} &:= \frac{7+2}{7+992} \\ \frac{72}{79992} &:= \frac{7+2}{7+9992} \\ \frac{72}{799992} &:= \frac{7+2}{7+99992} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 77**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{77}{121} &:= \frac{7+7}{1+21} \\ \frac{77}{1221} &:= \frac{7+7}{1+221} \\ \frac{77}{12221} &:= \frac{7+7}{1+2221} \\ \frac{77}{122221} &:= \frac{7+7}{1+22221} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{77}{242} &:= \frac{7+7}{2+42} \\ \frac{77}{2442} &:= \frac{7+7}{2+442} \\ \frac{77}{24442} &:= \frac{7+7}{2+4442} \\ \frac{77}{244442} &:= \frac{7+7}{2+44442} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{77}{363} &:= \frac{7+7}{3+63} \\ \frac{77}{3663} &:= \frac{7+7}{3+663} \\ \frac{77}{36663} &:= \frac{7+7}{3+6663} \\ \frac{77}{366663} &:= \frac{7+7}{3+66663} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{77}{484} &:= \frac{7+7}{4+84} \\ \frac{77}{4884} &:= \frac{7+7}{4+884} \\ \frac{77}{48884} &:= \frac{7+7}{4+8884} \\ \frac{77}{488884} &:= \frac{7+7}{4+88884} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 81**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{81}{891} &:= \frac{8+1}{8+91} \\ \frac{81}{8991} &:= \frac{8+1}{8+991} \\ \frac{81}{89991} &:= \frac{8+1}{8+9991} \\ \frac{81}{899991} &:= \frac{8+1}{8+99991}\end{aligned}$$

● **Number 82**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{82}{451} &:= \frac{8+2}{4+51} \\ \frac{82}{4551} &:= \frac{8+2}{4+551} \\ \frac{82}{45551} &:= \frac{8+2}{4+5551} \\ \frac{82}{455551} &:= \frac{8+2}{4+55551}\end{aligned}$$

● **Number 84**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{84}{231} &:= \frac{8+4}{2+31} & \frac{84}{462} &:= \frac{8+4}{4+62} & \frac{84}{693} &:= \frac{8+4}{6+93} \\ \frac{84}{2331} &:= \frac{8+4}{2+331} & \frac{84}{4662} &:= \frac{8+4}{4+662} & \frac{84}{6993} &:= \frac{8+4}{6+993} \\ \frac{84}{23331} &:= \frac{8+4}{2+3331} & \frac{84}{46662} &:= \frac{8+4}{4+6662} & \frac{84}{69993} &:= \frac{8+4}{6+9993} \\ \frac{84}{233331} &:= \frac{8+4}{2+33331} & \frac{84}{466662} &:= \frac{8+4}{4+66662} & \frac{84}{699993} &:= \frac{8+4}{6+99993}\end{aligned}$$

● **Number 85**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{85}{187} &:= \frac{8 \times 5}{1+87} \\ \frac{85}{1887} &:= \frac{8 \times 5}{1+887} \\ \frac{85}{18887} &:= \frac{8 \times 5}{1+8887} \\ \frac{85}{188887} &:= \frac{8 \times 5}{1+88887}\end{aligned}$$

● **Number 36**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{86}{473} &:= \frac{8+6}{4+73} \\ \frac{86}{4773} &:= \frac{8+6}{4+773} \\ \frac{86}{47773} &:= \frac{8+6}{4+7773} \\ \frac{86}{477773} &:= \frac{8+6}{4+77773} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 88**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{88}{121} &:= \frac{8+8}{1+21} \\ \frac{88}{1221} &:= \frac{8+8}{1+221} \\ \frac{88}{12221} &:= \frac{8+8}{1+2221} \\ \frac{88}{122221} &:= \frac{8+8}{1+22221} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{88}{242} &:= \frac{8+8}{2+42} \\ \frac{88}{2442} &:= \frac{8+8}{2+442} \\ \frac{88}{24442} &:= \frac{8+8}{2+4442} \\ \frac{88}{244442} &:= \frac{8+8}{2+44442} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{88}{363} &:= \frac{8+8}{3+63} \\ \frac{88}{3663} &:= \frac{8+8}{3+663} \\ \frac{88}{36663} &:= \frac{8+8}{3+6663} \\ \frac{88}{366663} &:= \frac{8+8}{3+66663} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{88}{484} &:= \frac{8+8}{4+84} \\ \frac{88}{4884} &:= \frac{8+8}{4+884} \\ \frac{88}{48884} &:= \frac{8+8}{4+8884} \\ \frac{88}{488884} &:= \frac{8+8}{4+88884} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 93**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{93}{341} &:= \frac{9+3}{3+41} \\ \frac{93}{3441} &:= \frac{9+3}{3+441} \\ \frac{93}{34441} &:= \frac{9+3}{3+4441} \\ \frac{93}{344441} &:= \frac{9+3}{3+44441} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{93}{682} &:= \frac{9+3}{6+82} \\ \frac{93}{6882} &:= \frac{9+3}{6+882} \\ \frac{93}{68882} &:= \frac{9+3}{6+8882} \\ \frac{93}{688882} &:= \frac{9+3}{6+88882} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 96**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{96}{352} &:= \frac{9+6}{3+52} \\ \frac{96}{3552} &:= \frac{9+6}{3+552} \\ \frac{96}{35552} &:= \frac{9+6}{3+5552} \\ \frac{96}{355552} &:= \frac{9+6}{3+55552} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 99**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{99}{121} &:= \frac{9+9}{1+21} \\ \frac{99}{1221} &:= \frac{9+9}{1+221} \\ \frac{99}{12221} &:= \frac{9+9}{1+2221} \\ \frac{99}{122221} &:= \frac{9+9}{1+22221} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{99}{242} &:= \frac{9+9}{2+42} \\ \frac{99}{2442} &:= \frac{9+9}{2+442} \\ \frac{99}{24442} &:= \frac{9+9}{2+4442} \\ \frac{99}{244442} &:= \frac{9+9}{2+44442} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{99}{363} &:= \frac{9+9}{3+63} \\ \frac{99}{3663} &:= \frac{9+9}{3+663} \\ \frac{99}{36663} &:= \frac{9+9}{3+6663} \\ \frac{99}{366663} &:= \frac{9+9}{3+66663} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{99}{484} &:= \frac{9+9}{4+84} \\ \frac{99}{4884} &:= \frac{9+9}{4+884} \\ \frac{99}{48884} &:= \frac{9+9}{4+8884} \\ \frac{99}{488884} &:= \frac{9+9}{4+88884} \end{aligned}$$

2.2 Three Digits Numerator

● **Number 101**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{101}{1111} &:= \frac{1+01}{11+11} \\ \frac{101}{11211} &:= \frac{1+01}{11+211} \\ \frac{101}{112211} &:= \frac{1+01}{11+2211} \\ \frac{101}{1122211} &:= \frac{1+01}{11+22211} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{102}{1122} &:= \frac{1+02}{11+22} \\ \frac{102}{11322} &:= \frac{1+02}{11+322} \\ \frac{102}{113322} &:= \frac{1+02}{11+3322} \\ \frac{102}{1133322} &:= \frac{1+02}{11+33322} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 102**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{102}{561} &:= \frac{10+2}{5+61} \\ \frac{102}{5661} &:= \frac{10+2}{5+661} \\ \frac{102}{56661} &:= \frac{10+2}{5+6661} \\ \frac{102}{566661} &:= \frac{10+2}{5+66661} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 103**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{103}{1133} &:= \frac{1+03}{11+33} \\ \frac{103}{11433} &:= \frac{1+03}{11+433} \\ \frac{103}{114433} &:= \frac{1+03}{11+4433} \\ \frac{103}{1144433} &:= \frac{1+03}{11+44433} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 104**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{104}{1144} &:= \frac{1+04}{11+44} \\ \frac{104}{11544} &:= \frac{1+04}{11+544} \\ \frac{104}{115544} &:= \frac{1+04}{11+5544} \\ \frac{104}{1155544} &:= \frac{1+04}{11+55544} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{104}{572} &:= \frac{10+4}{5+72} \\ \frac{104}{5772} &:= \frac{10+4}{5+772} \\ \frac{104}{57772} &:= \frac{10+4}{5+7772} \\ \frac{104}{577772} &:= \frac{10+4}{5+77772} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 105**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{105}{231} &:= \frac{10+5}{2+31} \\ \frac{105}{2331} &:= \frac{10+5}{2+331} \\ \frac{105}{23331} &:= \frac{10+5}{2+3331} \\ \frac{105}{233331} &:= \frac{10+5}{2+33331} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{105}{462} &:= \frac{10+5}{4+62} \\ \frac{105}{4662} &:= \frac{10+5}{4+662} \\ \frac{105}{46662} &:= \frac{10+5}{4+6662} \\ \frac{105}{466662} &:= \frac{10+5}{4+66662} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{105}{693} &:= \frac{10+5}{6+93} \\ \frac{105}{6993} &:= \frac{10+5}{6+993} \\ \frac{105}{69993} &:= \frac{10+5}{6+9993} \\ \frac{105}{699993} &:= \frac{10+5}{6+99993} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 106**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{106}{583} &:= \frac{10+6}{5+83} \\ \frac{106}{5883} &:= \frac{10+6}{5+883} \\ \frac{106}{58883} &:= \frac{10+6}{5+8883} \\ \frac{106}{588883} &:= \frac{10+6}{5+88883} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 107**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{107}{1177} &:= \frac{1+07}{11+77} \\ \frac{107}{11877} &:= \frac{1+07}{11+877} \\ \frac{107}{118877} &:= \frac{1+07}{11+8877} \\ \frac{107}{1188877} &:= \frac{1+07}{11+88877} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 108**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{108}{1188} &:= \frac{1+08}{11+88} \\ \frac{108}{11988} &:= \frac{1+08}{11+988} \\ \frac{108}{119988} &:= \frac{1+08}{11+9988} \\ \frac{108}{1199988} &:= \frac{1+08}{11+99988} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{108}{594} &:= \frac{10+8}{5+94} \\ \frac{108}{5994} &:= \frac{10+8}{5+994} \\ \frac{108}{59994} &:= \frac{10+8}{5+9994} \\ \frac{108}{599994} &:= \frac{10+8}{5+99994} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 110**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{110}{1089} &:= \frac{1 \times 10}{10+89} \\ \frac{110}{10989} &:= \frac{1 \times 10}{10+989} \\ \frac{110}{109989} &:= \frac{1 \times 10}{10+9989} \\ \frac{110}{1099989} &:= \frac{1 \times 10}{10+99989} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{110}{1815} &:= \frac{1+1+0}{18+15} \\ \frac{110}{18315} &:= \frac{1+1+0}{18+315} \\ \frac{110}{183315} &:= \frac{1+1+0}{18+3315} \\ \frac{110}{1833315} &:= \frac{1+1+0}{18+33315} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{110}{605} &:= \frac{1+1+0}{6+05} \\ \frac{110}{6105} &:= \frac{1+1+0}{6+105} \\ \frac{110}{61105} &:= \frac{1+1+0}{6+1105} \\ \frac{110}{611105} &:= \frac{1+1+0}{6+11105} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 111**

$$\frac{111}{1221} := \frac{1+1+1}{12+21}$$

$$\frac{111}{12321} := \frac{1+1+1}{12+321}$$

$$\frac{111}{123321} := \frac{1+1+1}{12+3321}$$

$$\frac{111}{407} := \frac{1+1+1}{4+07}$$

$$\frac{111}{4107} := \frac{1+1+1}{4+107}$$

$$\frac{111}{41107} := \frac{1+1+1}{4+1107}$$

$$\frac{111}{814} := \frac{1+1+1}{8+14}$$

$$\frac{111}{8214} := \frac{1+1+1}{8+214}$$

$$\frac{111}{82214} := \frac{1+1+1}{8+2214}$$

• **Number 112**

$$\frac{112}{1232} := \frac{1+1+2}{12+32}$$

$$\frac{112}{12432} := \frac{1+1+2}{12+432}$$

$$\frac{112}{124432} := \frac{1+1+2}{12+4432}$$

$$\frac{112}{1244432} := \frac{1+1+2}{12+44432}$$

$$\frac{112}{308} := \frac{1+1+2}{3+08}$$

$$\frac{112}{3108} := \frac{1+1+2}{3+108}$$

$$\frac{112}{31108} := \frac{1+1+2}{3+1108}$$

$$\frac{112}{616} := \frac{1+1+2}{6+16}$$

$$\frac{112}{6216} := \frac{1+1+2}{6+216}$$

$$\frac{112}{62216} := \frac{1+1+2}{6+2216}$$

$$\frac{112}{924} := \frac{1+1+2}{9+24}$$

$$\frac{112}{9324} := \frac{1+1+2}{9+324}$$

$$\frac{112}{93324} := \frac{1+1+2}{9+3324}$$

$$\frac{112}{933324} := \frac{1+1+2}{9+33324}$$

• **Number 113**

$$\frac{113}{1243} := \frac{1+1+3}{12+43}$$

$$\frac{113}{12543} := \frac{1+1+3}{12+543}$$

$$\frac{113}{125543} := \frac{1+1+3}{12+5543}$$

$$\frac{113}{1255543} := \frac{1+1+3}{12+55543}$$

• **Number 114**

$$\frac{114}{1463} := \frac{1+1+4}{14+63}$$

$$\frac{114}{14763} := \frac{1+1+4}{14+763}$$

$$\frac{114}{147763} := \frac{1+1+4}{14+7763}$$

$$\frac{114}{1477763} := \frac{1+1+4}{14+77763}$$

$$\frac{114}{1672} := \frac{1+1+4}{16+72}$$

$$\frac{114}{16872} := \frac{1+1+4}{16+872}$$

$$\frac{114}{168872} := \frac{1+1+4}{16+8872}$$

$$\frac{114}{1688872} := \frac{1+1+4}{16+88872}$$

$$\frac{114}{209} := \frac{1+1+4}{2+09}$$

$$\frac{114}{2109} := \frac{1+1+4}{2+109}$$

$$\frac{114}{21109} := \frac{1+1+4}{2+1109}$$

$$\frac{114}{211109} := \frac{1+1+4}{2+11109}$$

$$\frac{114}{418} := \frac{1+1+4}{4+18}$$

$$\frac{114}{4218} := \frac{1+1+4}{4+218}$$

$$\frac{114}{42218} := \frac{1+1+4}{4+2218}$$

$$\frac{114}{422218} := \frac{1+1+4}{4+22218}$$

$$\frac{114}{627} := \frac{1+1+4}{6+27}$$

$$\frac{114}{6327} := \frac{1+1+4}{6+327}$$

$$\frac{114}{63327} := \frac{1+1+4}{6+3327}$$

$$\frac{114}{633327} := \frac{1+1+4}{6+33327}$$

$$\frac{114}{836} := \frac{1+1+4}{8+36}$$

$$\frac{114}{8436} := \frac{1+1+4}{8+436}$$

$$\frac{114}{84436} := \frac{1+1+4}{8+4436}$$

$$\frac{114}{844436} := \frac{1+1+4}{8+44436}$$

• **Number 115**

$$\frac{115}{1265} := \frac{1+1+5}{12+65}$$

$$\frac{115}{12765} := \frac{1+1+5}{12+765}$$

$$\frac{115}{127765} := \frac{1+1+5}{12+7765}$$

$$\frac{115}{1277765} := \frac{1+1+5}{12+77765}$$

$$\frac{115}{759} := \frac{(1+1) \times 5}{7+59}$$

$$\frac{115}{7659} := \frac{(1+1) \times 5}{7+659}$$

$$\frac{115}{76659} := \frac{(1+1) \times 5}{7+6659}$$

$$\frac{115}{766659} := \frac{(1+1) \times 5}{7+66659}$$

• **Number 116**

$$\frac{116}{319} := \frac{1+1+6}{3+19}$$

$$\frac{116}{3219} := \frac{1+1+6}{3+219}$$

$$\frac{116}{32219} := \frac{1+1+6}{3+2219}$$

$$\frac{116}{322219} := \frac{1+1+6}{3+22219}$$

$$\frac{116}{638} := \frac{1+1+6}{6+38}$$

$$\frac{116}{6438} := \frac{1+1+6}{6+438}$$

$$\frac{116}{64438} := \frac{1+1+6}{6+4438}$$

$$\frac{116}{644438} := \frac{1+1+6}{6+44438}$$

$$\frac{116}{957} := \frac{1+1+6}{9+57}$$

$$\frac{116}{9657} := \frac{1+1+6}{9+657}$$

$$\frac{116}{96657} := \frac{1+1+6}{9+6657}$$

$$\frac{116}{966657} := \frac{1+1+6}{9+66657}$$

● **Number 117**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{117}{1287} &:= \frac{1+1+7}{12+87} \\ \frac{117}{12987} &:= \frac{1+1+7}{12+987} \\ \frac{117}{129987} &:= \frac{1+1+7}{12+9987} \\ \frac{117}{1299987} &:= \frac{1+1+7}{12+99987}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{117}{429} &:= \frac{1+1+7}{4+29} \\ \frac{117}{4329} &:= \frac{1+1+7}{4+329} \\ \frac{117}{43329} &:= \frac{1+1+7}{4+3329} \\ \frac{117}{433329} &:= \frac{1+1+7}{4+33329}\end{aligned}$$

● **Number 118**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{118}{649} &:= \frac{1+1+8}{6+49} \\ \frac{118}{6549} &:= \frac{1+1+8}{6+549} \\ \frac{118}{65549} &:= \frac{1+1+8}{6+5549} \\ \frac{118}{655549} &:= \frac{1+1+8}{6+55549}\end{aligned}$$

● **Number 119**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{119}{1309} &:= \frac{1+1^9}{13+09} \\ \frac{119}{13209} &:= \frac{1+1^9}{13+209} \\ \frac{119}{132209} &:= \frac{1+1^9}{13+2209} \\ \frac{119}{1322209} &:= \frac{1+1^9}{13+22209}\end{aligned}$$

● **Number 120**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{120}{594} &:= \frac{1 \times 20}{5+94} \\ \frac{120}{5994} &:= \frac{1 \times 20}{5+994} \\ \frac{120}{59994} &:= \frac{1 \times 20}{5+9994} \\ \frac{120}{599994} &:= \frac{1 \times 20}{5+99994}\end{aligned}$$

● **Number 121**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{121}{1221} &:= \frac{1+21}{1+221} \\ \frac{121}{12221} &:= \frac{1+21}{1+2221} \\ \frac{121}{122221} &:= \frac{1+21}{1+22221} \\ \frac{121}{1222221} &:= \frac{1+21}{1+222221} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{121}{242} &:= \frac{1+21}{2+42} \\ \frac{121}{2442} &:= \frac{1+21}{2+442} \\ \frac{121}{24442} &:= \frac{1+21}{2+4442} \\ \frac{121}{244442} &:= \frac{1+21}{2+44442} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{121}{363} &:= \frac{1+21}{3+63} \\ \frac{121}{3663} &:= \frac{1+21}{3+663} \\ \frac{121}{36663} &:= \frac{1+21}{3+6663} \\ \frac{121}{366663} &:= \frac{1+21}{3+66663} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 122**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{122}{671} &:= \frac{12+2}{6+71} \\ \frac{122}{6771} &:= \frac{12+2}{6+771} \\ \frac{122}{67771} &:= \frac{12+2}{6+7771} \\ \frac{122}{677771} &:= \frac{12+2}{6+77771} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 123**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{123}{1353} &:= \frac{1+2+3}{13+53} \\ \frac{123}{13653} &:= \frac{1+2+3}{13+653} \\ \frac{123}{136653} &:= \frac{1+2+3}{13+6653} \\ \frac{123}{1366653} &:= \frac{1+2+3}{13+66653} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{123}{451} &:= \frac{12+3}{4+51} \\ \frac{123}{4551} &:= \frac{12+3}{4+551} \\ \frac{123}{45551} &:= \frac{12+3}{4+5551} \\ \frac{123}{455551} &:= \frac{12+3}{4+55551} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 124**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{124}{1023} &:= \frac{1^2 \times 4}{10+23} \\ \frac{124}{10323} &:= \frac{1^2 \times 4}{10+323} \\ \frac{124}{103323} &:= \frac{1^2 \times 4}{10+3323} \\ \frac{124}{1033323} &:= \frac{1^2 \times 4}{10+33323} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{124}{13764} &:= \frac{1+2+4}{13+764} \\ \frac{124}{137764} &:= \frac{1+2+4}{13+7764} \\ \frac{124}{1377764} &:= \frac{1+2+4}{13+77764} \\ \frac{124}{13777764} &:= \frac{1+2+4}{13+777764} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{124}{341} &:= \frac{1 \times 2^4}{3+41} \\ \frac{124}{3441} &:= \frac{1 \times 2^4}{3+441} \\ \frac{124}{34441} &:= \frac{1 \times 2^4}{3+4441} \\ \frac{124}{344441} &:= \frac{1 \times 2^4}{3+44441} \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{124}{682} := \frac{1 \times 2^4}{6 + 82}$$

$$\frac{124}{6882} := \frac{1 \times 2^4}{6 + 882}$$

$$\frac{124}{68882} := \frac{1 \times 2^4}{6 + 8882}$$

$$\frac{124}{688882} := \frac{1 \times 2^4}{6 + 88882}$$

• **Number 125**

$$\frac{125}{495} := \frac{1 \times 25}{4 + 95}$$

$$\frac{125}{4995} := \frac{1 \times 25}{4 + 995}$$

$$\frac{125}{49995} := \frac{1 \times 25}{4 + 9995}$$

$$\frac{125}{499995} := \frac{1 \times 25}{4 + 99995}$$

$$\frac{125}{825} := \frac{1^2 \times 5}{8 + 25}$$

$$\frac{125}{8325} := \frac{1^2 \times 5}{8 + 325}$$

$$\frac{125}{83325} := \frac{1^2 \times 5}{8 + 3325}$$

$$\frac{125}{833325} := \frac{1^2 \times 5}{8 + 33325}$$

• **Number 126**

$$\frac{126}{231} := \frac{12 + 6}{2 + 31}$$

$$\frac{126}{2331} := \frac{12 + 6}{2 + 331}$$

$$\frac{126}{23331} := \frac{12 + 6}{2 + 3331}$$

$$\frac{126}{233331} := \frac{12 + 6}{2 + 33331}$$

$$\frac{126}{462} := \frac{12 + 6}{4 + 62}$$

$$\frac{126}{4662} := \frac{12 + 6}{4 + 662}$$

$$\frac{126}{46662} := \frac{12 + 6}{4 + 6662}$$

$$\frac{126}{466662} := \frac{12 + 6}{4 + 66662}$$

$$\frac{126}{693} := \frac{12 + 6}{6 + 93}$$

$$\frac{126}{6993} := \frac{12 + 6}{6 + 993}$$

$$\frac{126}{69993} := \frac{12 + 6}{6 + 9993}$$

$$\frac{126}{699993} := \frac{12 + 6}{6 + 99993}$$

• **Number 128**

$$\frac{128}{1056} := \frac{1^2 \times 8}{10 + 56}$$

$$\frac{128}{10656} := \frac{1^2 \times 8}{10 + 656}$$

$$\frac{128}{106656} := \frac{1^2 \times 8}{10 + 6656}$$

$$\frac{128}{1066656} := \frac{1^2 \times 8}{10 + 66656}$$

$$\frac{128}{352} := \frac{12 + 8}{3 + 52}$$

$$\frac{128}{3552} := \frac{12 + 8}{3 + 552}$$

$$\frac{128}{35552} := \frac{12 + 8}{3 + 5552}$$

$$\frac{128}{355552} := \frac{12 + 8}{3 + 55552}$$

$$\frac{128}{784} := \frac{12 \times 8}{7 \times 84}$$

$$\frac{128}{7840} := \frac{12 \times 8}{7 \times 840}$$

$$\frac{128}{78400} := \frac{12 \times 8}{7 \times 8400}$$

$$\frac{128}{784000} := \frac{12 \times 8}{7 \times 84000}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{128}{792} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8}{7 + 92} \\ \frac{128}{7992} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8}{7 + 992} \\ \frac{128}{79992} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8}{7 + 9992} \\ \frac{128}{799992} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8}{7 + 99992} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 129**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{129}{473} &:= \frac{12 + 9}{4 + 73} \\ \frac{129}{4773} &:= \frac{12 + 9}{4 + 773} \\ \frac{129}{47773} &:= \frac{12 + 9}{4 + 7773} \\ \frac{129}{477773} &:= \frac{12 + 9}{4 + 77773} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 130**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{130}{1365} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 0}{1 + 36 + 5} \\ \frac{130}{14365} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 0}{1 + 436 + 5} \\ \frac{130}{144365} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 0}{1 + 4436 + 5} \\ \frac{130}{1444365} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 0}{1 + 44436 + 5} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 132**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{132}{1332} &:= \frac{1 + 32}{1 + 332} \\ \frac{132}{13332} &:= \frac{1 + 32}{1 + 3332} \\ \frac{132}{133332} &:= \frac{1 + 32}{1 + 33332} \\ \frac{132}{1333332} &:= \frac{1 + 32}{1 + 333332} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{132}{1452} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 2}{14 + 52} \\ \frac{132}{14652} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 2}{14 + 652} \\ \frac{132}{146652} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 2}{14 + 6652} \\ \frac{132}{1466652} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 2}{14 + 66652} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{132}{264} &:= \frac{1 + 32}{2 + 64} \\ \frac{132}{2664} &:= \frac{1 + 32}{2 + 664} \\ \frac{132}{26664} &:= \frac{1 + 32}{2 + 6664} \\ \frac{132}{266664} &:= \frac{1 + 32}{2 + 66664} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{132}{396} := \frac{1+32}{3+96} \\ \frac{132}{3996} := \frac{1+32}{3+996} \\ \frac{132}{39996} := \frac{1+32}{3+9996} \\ \frac{132}{399996} := \frac{1+32}{3+99996} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{132}{726} := \frac{1+3+2}{7+26} \\ \frac{132}{7326} := \frac{1+3+2}{7+326} \\ \frac{132}{73326} := \frac{1+3+2}{7+3326} \\ \frac{132}{733326} := \frac{1+3+2}{7+33326} \end{array}$$

● **Number 133**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{133}{1045} := \frac{1+3+3}{10+45} \\ \frac{133}{10545} := \frac{1+3+3}{10+545} \\ \frac{133}{105545} := \frac{1+3+3}{10+5545} \\ \frac{133}{1055545} := \frac{1+3+3}{10+55545} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{133}{1463} := \frac{1+3+3}{14+63} \\ \frac{133}{14763} := \frac{1+3+3}{14+763} \\ \frac{133}{147763} := \frac{1+3+3}{14+7763} \\ \frac{133}{1477763} := \frac{1+3+3}{14+77763} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{133}{209} := \frac{1+3+3}{2+09} \\ \frac{133}{2109} := \frac{1+3+3}{2+109} \\ \frac{133}{21109} := \frac{1+3+3}{2+1109} \\ \frac{133}{211109} := \frac{1+3+3}{2+11109} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{133}{418} := \frac{1+3+3}{4+18} \\ \frac{133}{4218} := \frac{1+3+3}{4+218} \\ \frac{133}{42218} := \frac{1+3+3}{4+2218} \\ \frac{133}{422218} := \frac{1+3+3}{4+22218} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{133}{627} := \frac{1+3+3}{6+27} \\ \frac{133}{6327} := \frac{1+3+3}{6+327} \\ \frac{133}{63327} := \frac{1+3+3}{6+3327} \\ \frac{133}{633327} := \frac{1+3+3}{6+33327} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{133}{836} := \frac{1+3+3}{8+36} \\ \frac{133}{8436} := \frac{1+3+3}{8+436} \\ \frac{133}{84436} := \frac{1+3+3}{8+4436} \\ \frac{133}{844436} := \frac{1+3+3}{8+44436} \end{array}$$

● **Number 134**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{134}{737} := \frac{1+3+4}{7+37} \\ \frac{134}{7437} := \frac{1+3+4}{7+437} \\ \frac{134}{74437} := \frac{1+3+4}{7+4437} \\ \frac{134}{744437} := \frac{1+3+4}{7+44437} \end{array}$$

● **Number 135**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{135}{1485} := \frac{1+3+5}{14+85} \\ \frac{135}{14985} := \frac{1+3+5}{14+985} \\ \frac{135}{149985} := \frac{1+3+5}{14+9985} \\ \frac{135}{1499985} := \frac{1+3+5}{14+99985} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{135}{891} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{8+91} \\ \frac{135}{8991} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{8+991} \\ \frac{135}{89991} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{8+9991} \\ \frac{135}{899991} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{8+99991} \end{array}$$

● **Number 136**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{136}{748} := \frac{1+3+6}{7+48} \\ \frac{136}{7548} := \frac{1+3+6}{7+548} \\ \frac{136}{75548} := \frac{1+3+6}{7+5548} \\ \frac{136}{755548} := \frac{1+3+6}{7+55548} \end{array}$$

● **Number 137**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{140}{1232} := \frac{1+4+0}{12+32} \\ \frac{140}{12432} := \frac{1+4+0}{12+432} \\ \frac{140}{124432} := \frac{1+4+0}{12+4432} \\ \frac{140}{1244432} := \frac{1+4+0}{12+44432} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{140}{308} := \frac{1+4+0}{3+08} \\ \frac{140}{3108} := \frac{1+4+0}{3+108} \\ \frac{140}{31108} := \frac{1+4+0}{3+1108} \\ \frac{140}{311108} := \frac{1+4+0}{3+11108} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{140}{616} := \frac{1+4+0}{6+16} \\ \frac{140}{6216} := \frac{1+4+0}{6+216} \\ \frac{140}{62216} := \frac{1+4+0}{6+2216} \\ \frac{140}{622216} := \frac{1+4+0}{6+22216} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{140}{924} := \frac{1+4+0}{9+24} \\ \frac{140}{9324} := \frac{1+4+0}{9+324} \\ \frac{140}{93324} := \frac{1+4+0}{9+3324} \\ \frac{140}{933324} := \frac{1+4+0}{9+33324} \end{array}$$

● **Number 141**

$$\frac{141}{1034} := \frac{1+4+1}{10+34}$$

$$\frac{141}{10434} := \frac{1+4+1}{10+434}$$

$$\frac{141}{104434} := \frac{1+4+1}{10+4434}$$

$$\frac{141}{1044434} := \frac{1+4+1}{10+44434}$$

$$\frac{141}{1551} := \frac{1+4+1}{15+51}$$

$$\frac{141}{15651} := \frac{1+4+1}{15+651}$$

$$\frac{141}{156651} := \frac{1+4+1}{15+6651}$$

$$\frac{141}{517} := \frac{1+4+1}{5+17}$$

$$\frac{141}{5217} := \frac{1+4+1}{5+217}$$

$$\frac{141}{52217} := \frac{1+4+1}{5+2217}$$

• **Number 142**

$$\frac{142}{1562} := \frac{1+4+2}{15+62}$$

$$\frac{142}{15762} := \frac{1+4+2}{15+762}$$

$$\frac{142}{157762} := \frac{1+4+2}{15+7762}$$

$$\frac{142}{1577762} := \frac{1+4+2}{15+77762}$$

$$\frac{142}{781} := \frac{1 \times 4^2}{7+81}$$

$$\frac{142}{7881} := \frac{1 \times 4^2}{7+881}$$

$$\frac{142}{78881} := \frac{1 \times 4^2}{7+8881}$$

• **Number 143**

$$\frac{143}{1089} := \frac{1+4 \times 3}{10+89}$$

$$\frac{143}{10989} := \frac{1+4 \times 3}{10+989}$$

$$\frac{143}{109989} := \frac{1+4 \times 3}{10+9989}$$

$$\frac{143}{1099989} := \frac{1+4 \times 3}{10+99989}$$

$$\frac{143}{1443} := \frac{1+43}{1+443}$$

$$\frac{143}{14443} := \frac{1+43}{1+4443}$$

$$\frac{143}{144443} := \frac{1+43}{1+44443}$$

$$\frac{143}{1444443} := \frac{1+43}{1+444443}$$

$$\frac{143}{1573} := \frac{1+4+3}{15+73}$$

$$\frac{143}{15873} := \frac{1+4+3}{15+873}$$

$$\frac{143}{158873} := \frac{1+4+3}{15+8873}$$

$$\frac{143}{1588873} := \frac{1+4+3}{15+88873}$$

$$\frac{143}{286} := \frac{1+43}{2+86}$$

$$\frac{143}{2886} := \frac{1+43}{2+886}$$

$$\frac{143}{28886} := \frac{1+43}{2+8886}$$

$$\frac{143}{288886} := \frac{1+43}{2+88886}$$

• **Number 144**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{144}{1056} := \frac{1+4+4}{10+56} \\ \frac{144}{10656} := \frac{1+4+4}{10+656} \\ \frac{144}{106656} := \frac{1+4+4}{10+6656} \\ \frac{144}{1066656} := \frac{1+4+4}{10+66656} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{144}{1782} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{17 + 82} \\ \frac{144}{17982} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{17 + 982} \\ \frac{144}{179982} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{17 + 9982} \\ \frac{144}{1799982} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{17 + 99982} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{144}{792} := \frac{14+4}{7+92} \\ \frac{144}{7992} := \frac{14+4}{7+992} \\ \frac{144}{79992} := \frac{14+4}{7+9992} \\ \frac{144}{799992} := \frac{14+4}{7+99992} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{144}{891} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{8 + 91} \\ \frac{144}{8991} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{8 + 991} \\ \frac{144}{89991} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{8 + 9991} \\ \frac{144}{899991} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{8 + 99991} \end{array}$$

• **Number 145**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{145}{319} := \frac{1+4+5}{3+19} \\ \frac{145}{3219} := \frac{1+4+5}{3+219} \\ \frac{145}{32219} := \frac{1+4+5}{3+2219} \\ \frac{145}{322219} := \frac{1+4+5}{3+22219} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{145}{638} := \frac{1+4+5}{6+38} \\ \frac{145}{6438} := \frac{1+4+5}{6+438} \\ \frac{145}{64438} := \frac{1+4+5}{6+4438} \\ \frac{145}{644438} := \frac{1+4+5}{6+44438} \end{array}$$

• **Number 147**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{147}{1078} := \frac{1+4+7}{10+78} \\ \frac{147}{10878} := \frac{1+4+7}{10+878} \\ \frac{147}{108878} := \frac{1+4+7}{10+8878} \\ \frac{147}{1088878} := \frac{1+4+7}{10+88878} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{147}{231} := \frac{14+7}{2+31} \\ \frac{147}{2331} := \frac{14+7}{2+331} \\ \frac{147}{23331} := \frac{14+7}{2+3331} \\ \frac{147}{233331} := \frac{14+7}{2+33331} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{147}{462} := \frac{14+7}{4+62} \\ \frac{147}{4662} := \frac{14+7}{4+662} \\ \frac{147}{46662} := \frac{14+7}{4+6662} \\ \frac{147}{466662} := \frac{14+7}{4+66662} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{147}{539} := \frac{1+4+7}{5+39} \\ \frac{147}{5439} := \frac{1+4+7}{5+439} \\ \frac{147}{54439} := \frac{1+4+7}{5+4439} \\ \frac{147}{544439} := \frac{1+4+7}{5+44439} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{147}{693} := \frac{14+7}{6+93} \\ \frac{147}{6993} := \frac{14+7}{6+993} \\ \frac{147}{69993} := \frac{14+7}{6+9993} \\ \frac{147}{699993} := \frac{14+7}{6+99993} \end{array}$$

• **Number 150**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{150}{297} := \frac{1 \times 50}{2+97} \\ \frac{150}{2997} := \frac{1 \times 50}{2+997} \\ \frac{150}{29997} := \frac{1 \times 50}{2+9997} \\ \frac{150}{299997} := \frac{1 \times 50}{2+99997} \end{array}$$

• **Number 151**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{151}{1661} := \frac{1+5+1}{16+61} \\ \frac{151}{16761} := \frac{1+5+1}{16+761} \\ \frac{151}{167761} := \frac{1+5+1}{16+7761} \\ \frac{151}{1677761} := \frac{1+5+1}{16+77761} \end{array}$$

• **Number 152**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{152}{1254} := \frac{1+5+2}{12+54} \\ \frac{152}{12654} := \frac{1+5+2}{12+654} \\ \frac{152}{126654} := \frac{1+5+2}{12+6654} \\ \frac{152}{1266654} := \frac{1+5+2}{12+66654} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{152}{1881} := \frac{1+5+2}{18+81} \\ \frac{152}{18981} := \frac{1+5+2}{18+981} \\ \frac{152}{189981} := \frac{1+5+2}{18+9981} \\ \frac{152}{1899981} := \frac{1+5+2}{18+99981} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{152}{209} := \frac{1+5+2}{2+09} \\ \frac{152}{2109} := \frac{1+5+2}{2+109} \\ \frac{152}{21109} := \frac{1+5+2}{2+1109} \\ \frac{152}{211109} := \frac{1+5+2}{2+11109} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{152}{418} := \frac{1+5+2}{4+18} \\ \frac{152}{4218} := \frac{1+5+2}{4+218} \\ \frac{152}{42218} := \frac{1+5+2}{4+2218} \\ \frac{152}{422218} := \frac{1+5+2}{4+22218} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{152}{627} := \frac{1+5+2}{6+27} \\ \frac{152}{6327} := \frac{1+5+2}{6+327} \\ \frac{152}{63327} := \frac{1+5+2}{6+3327} \\ \frac{152}{633327} := \frac{1+5+2}{6+33327} \end{array}$$

● **Number 153**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{153}{1683} := \frac{1+5+3}{16+83} \\ \frac{153}{16983} := \frac{1+5+3}{16+983} \\ \frac{153}{169983} := \frac{1+5+3}{16+9983} \\ \frac{153}{1699983} := \frac{1+5+3}{16+99983} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{153}{561} := \frac{15+3}{5+61} \\ \frac{153}{5661} := \frac{15+3}{5+661} \\ \frac{153}{56661} := \frac{15+3}{5+6661} \\ \frac{153}{566661} := \frac{15+3}{5+66661} \end{array}$$

● **Number 154**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{154}{1554} := \frac{1+54}{1+554} \\ \frac{154}{15554} := \frac{1+54}{1+5554} \\ \frac{154}{155554} := \frac{1+54}{1+55554} \\ \frac{154}{1555554} := \frac{1+54}{1+555554} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{154}{847} := \frac{1+5+4}{8+47} \\ \frac{154}{8547} := \frac{1+5+4}{8+547} \\ \frac{154}{85547} := \frac{1+5+4}{8+5547} \\ \frac{154}{855547} := \frac{1+5+4}{8+55547} \end{array}$$

● **Number 155**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{155}{341} := \frac{15+5}{3+41} \\ \frac{155}{3441} := \frac{15+5}{3+441} \\ \frac{155}{34441} := \frac{15+5}{3+4441} \\ \frac{155}{344441} := \frac{15+5}{3+44441} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{155}{682} := \frac{15+5}{6+82} \\ \frac{155}{6882} := \frac{15+5}{6+882} \\ \frac{155}{68882} := \frac{15+5}{6+8882} \\ \frac{155}{688882} := \frac{15+5}{6+88882} \end{array}$$

● **Number 156**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{156}{429} := \frac{1+5+6}{4+29} \\ \frac{156}{4329} := \frac{1+5+6}{4+329} \\ \frac{156}{43329} := \frac{1+5+6}{4+3329} \\ \frac{156}{433329} := \frac{1+5+6}{4+33329} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \frac{156}{572} := \frac{15+6}{5+72} \\ \frac{156}{5772} := \frac{15+6}{5+772} \\ \frac{156}{57772} := \frac{15+6}{5+7772} \\ \frac{156}{577772} := \frac{15+6}{5+77772} \end{array}$$

● **Number 158**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{158}{869} := \frac{1+5+8}{8+69} \\ \frac{158}{8769} := \frac{1+5+8}{8+769} \\ \frac{158}{87769} := \frac{1+5+8}{8+7769} \\ \frac{158}{877769} := \frac{1+5+8}{8+77769} \end{array}$$

● **Number 159**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{159}{583} := \frac{15+9}{5+83} \\ \frac{159}{5883} := \frac{15+9}{5+883} \\ \frac{159}{58883} := \frac{15+9}{5+8883} \\ \frac{159}{588883} := \frac{15+9}{5+88883} \end{array}$$

● **Number 162**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{162}{891} := \frac{16+2}{8+91} \\ \frac{162}{8991} := \frac{16+2}{8+991} \\ \frac{162}{89991} := \frac{16+2}{8+9991} \\ \frac{162}{899991} := \frac{16+2}{8+99991} \end{array}$$

● **Number 164**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{164}{451} &:= \frac{16+4}{4+51} \\ \frac{164}{4551} &:= \frac{16+4}{4+551} \\ \frac{164}{45551} &:= \frac{16+4}{4+5551} \\ \frac{164}{455551} &:= \frac{16+4}{4+55551} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 165**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{165}{1221} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{1+221} \\ \frac{165}{12221} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{1+2221} \\ \frac{165}{122221} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{1+22221} \\ \frac{165}{1222221} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{1+222221} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{165}{1485} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 5}{14+85} \\ \frac{165}{14985} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 5}{14+985} \\ \frac{165}{149985} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 5}{14+9985} \\ \frac{165}{1499985} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 5}{14+99985} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{165}{1665} &:= \frac{1+65}{1+665} \\ \frac{165}{16665} &:= \frac{1+65}{1+6665} \\ \frac{165}{166665} &:= \frac{1+65}{1+66665} \\ \frac{165}{1666665} &:= \frac{1+65}{1+666665} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{165}{242} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{2+42} \\ \frac{165}{2442} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{2+442} \\ \frac{165}{24442} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{2+4442} \\ \frac{165}{244442} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{2+44442} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{165}{363} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{3+63} \\ \frac{165}{3663} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{3+663} \\ \frac{165}{36663} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{3+6663} \\ \frac{165}{366663} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{3+66663} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{165}{484} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{4+84} \\ \frac{165}{4884} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{4+884} \\ \frac{165}{48884} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{4+8884} \\ \frac{165}{488884} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{4+88884} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 168**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{168}{1188} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 8}{11+88} \\ \frac{168}{11988} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 8}{11+988} \\ \frac{168}{119988} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 8}{11+9988} \\ \frac{168}{1199988} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 8}{11+99988} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{168}{231} &:= \frac{16+8}{2+31} \\ \frac{168}{2331} &:= \frac{16+8}{2+331} \\ \frac{168}{23331} &:= \frac{16+8}{2+3331} \\ \frac{168}{233331} &:= \frac{16+8}{2+33331} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{168}{297} &:= \frac{(1+6) \times 8}{2+97} \\ \frac{168}{2997} &:= \frac{(1+6) \times 8}{2+997} \\ \frac{168}{29997} &:= \frac{(1+6) \times 8}{2+9997} \\ \frac{168}{299997} &:= \frac{(1+6) \times 8}{2+99997} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{168}{462} := \frac{16+8}{4+62} \\ \frac{168}{4662} := \frac{16+8}{4+662} \\ \frac{168}{46662} := \frac{16+8}{4+6662} \\ \frac{168}{693} := \frac{16+8}{6+93} \\ \frac{168}{6993} := \frac{16+8}{6+993} \\ \frac{168}{69993} := \frac{16+8}{6+9993} \\ \frac{168}{699993} := \frac{16+8}{6+99993} \end{array}$$

● **Number 170**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{170}{1785} := \frac{1+7+0}{1+78+5} \\ \frac{170}{18785} := \frac{1+7+0}{1+878+5} \\ \frac{170}{188785} := \frac{1+7+0}{1+8878+5} \\ \frac{170}{1888785} := \frac{1+7+0}{1+88878+5} \\ \frac{170}{935} := \frac{1+7+0}{9+35} \\ \frac{170}{9435} := \frac{1+7+0}{9+435} \\ \frac{170}{94435} := \frac{1+7+0}{9+4435} \\ \frac{170}{944435} := \frac{1+7+0}{9+44435} \end{array}$$

● **Number 171**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{171}{1045} := \frac{1+7+1}{10+45} \\ \frac{171}{10545} := \frac{1+7+1}{10+545} \\ \frac{171}{105545} := \frac{1+7+1}{10+5545} \\ \frac{171}{1055545} := \frac{1+7+1}{10+55545} \\ \frac{171}{1254} := \frac{1+7+1}{12+54} \\ \frac{171}{12654} := \frac{1+7+1}{12+654} \\ \frac{171}{126654} := \frac{1+7+1}{12+6654} \\ \frac{171}{1266654} := \frac{1+7+1}{12+66654} \\ \frac{171}{1463} := \frac{1+7+1}{14+63} \\ \frac{171}{14763} := \frac{1+7+1}{14+763} \\ \frac{171}{147763} := \frac{1+7+1}{14+7763} \\ \frac{171}{1477763} := \frac{1+7+1}{14+77763} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{171}{1881} := \frac{1+7+1}{18+81} \\ \frac{171}{18981} := \frac{1+7+1}{18+981} \\ \frac{171}{189981} := \frac{1+7+1}{18+9981} \\ \frac{171}{1899981} := \frac{1+7+1}{18+99981} \\ \frac{171}{209} := \frac{1+7+1}{2+09} \\ \frac{171}{2109} := \frac{1+7+1}{2+109} \\ \frac{171}{21109} := \frac{1+7+1}{2+1109} \\ \frac{171}{211109} := \frac{1+7+1}{2+11109} \\ \frac{171}{418} := \frac{1+7+1}{4+18} \\ \frac{171}{4218} := \frac{1+7+1}{4+218} \\ \frac{171}{42218} := \frac{1+7+1}{4+2218} \\ \frac{171}{422218} := \frac{1+7+1}{4+22218} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{171}{494} := \frac{17+1}{(4+9) \times 4} \\ \frac{171}{4940} := \frac{17+1}{(4+9) \times 40} \\ \frac{171}{49400} := \frac{17+1}{(4+9) \times 400} \\ \frac{171}{494000} := \frac{17+1}{(4+9) \times 4000} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{171}{627} := \frac{1+7+1}{6+27} \\ \frac{171}{6327} := \frac{1+7+1}{6+327} \\ \frac{171}{63327} := \frac{1+7+1}{6+3327} \\ \frac{171}{633327} := \frac{1+7+1}{6+33327} \end{array}$$

• **Number 172**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{172}{946} := \frac{1+7+2}{9+46} \\ \frac{172}{9546} := \frac{1+7+2}{9+546} \\ \frac{172}{95546} := \frac{1+7+2}{9+5546} \\ \frac{172}{955546} := \frac{1+7+2}{9+55546} \end{array}$$

• **Number 174**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{174}{1276} := \frac{1+7+4}{12+76} \\ \frac{174}{12876} := \frac{1+7+4}{12+876} \\ \frac{174}{128876} := \frac{1+7+4}{12+8876} \\ \frac{174}{1288876} := \frac{1+7+4}{12+88876} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{174}{319} := \frac{1+7+4}{3+19} \\ \frac{174}{3219} := \frac{1+7+4}{3+219} \\ \frac{174}{32219} := \frac{1+7+4}{3+2219} \\ \frac{174}{322219} := \frac{1+7+4}{3+22219} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{174}{594} := \frac{1+7 \times 4}{5+94} \\ \frac{174}{5994} := \frac{1+7 \times 4}{5+994} \\ \frac{174}{59994} := \frac{1+7 \times 4}{5+9994} \\ \frac{174}{599994} := \frac{1+7 \times 4}{5+99994} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{174}{638} := \frac{1+7+4}{6+38} \\ \frac{174}{6438} := \frac{1+7+4}{6+438} \\ \frac{174}{64438} := \frac{1+7+4}{6+4438} \\ \frac{174}{644438} := \frac{1+7+4}{6+44438} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{174}{957} := \frac{1+7+4}{9+57} \\ \frac{174}{9657} := \frac{1+7+4}{9+657} \\ \frac{174}{96657} := \frac{1+7+4}{9+6657} \\ \frac{174}{966657} := \frac{1+7+4}{9+66657} \end{array}$$

• **Number 175**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{175}{385} &:= \frac{(1+7) \times 5}{3+85} & \frac{175}{495} &:= \frac{1 \times 7 \times 5}{4+95} \\ \frac{175}{3885} &:= \frac{(1+7) \times 5}{3+885} & \frac{175}{4995} &:= \frac{1 \times 7 \times 5}{4+995} \\ \frac{175}{38885} &:= \frac{(1+7) \times 5}{3+8885} & \frac{175}{49995} &:= \frac{1 \times 7 \times 5}{4+9995} \\ \frac{175}{388885} &:= \frac{(1+7) \times 5}{3+88885} & \frac{175}{499995} &:= \frac{1 \times 7 \times 5}{4+99995} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 176**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{176}{1776} &:= \frac{1+76}{1+776} & \frac{176}{968} &:= \frac{1+7+6}{9+68} \\ \frac{176}{17776} &:= \frac{1+76}{1+7776} & \frac{176}{9768} &:= \frac{1+7+6}{9+768} \\ \frac{176}{177776} &:= \frac{1+76}{1+77776} & \frac{176}{97768} &:= \frac{1+7+6}{9+7768} \\ \frac{176}{1777776} &:= \frac{1+76}{1+777776} & \frac{176}{977768} &:= \frac{1+7+6}{9+77768} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 177**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{177}{649} &:= \frac{1+7+7}{6+49} \\ \frac{177}{6549} &:= \frac{1+7+7}{6+549} \\ \frac{177}{65549} &:= \frac{1+7+7}{6+5549} \\ \frac{177}{655549} &:= \frac{1+7+7}{6+55549} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 178**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{178}{979} &:= \frac{1+7+8}{9+79} \\ \frac{178}{9879} &:= \frac{1+7+8}{9+879} \\ \frac{178}{98879} &:= \frac{1+7+8}{9+8879} \\ \frac{178}{988879} &:= \frac{1+7+8}{9+88879} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 182**

$$\frac{182}{1554} := \frac{1 + 8^2}{1 + 554}$$

$$\frac{182}{15554} := \frac{1 + 8^2}{1 + 5554}$$

$$\frac{182}{155554} := \frac{1 + 8^2}{1 + 55554}$$

$$\frac{182}{1555554} := \frac{1 + 8^2}{1 + 555554}$$

• **Number 183**

$$\frac{183}{671} := \frac{18 + 3}{6 + 71}$$

$$\frac{183}{6771} := \frac{18 + 3}{6 + 771}$$

$$\frac{183}{67771} := \frac{18 + 3}{6 + 7771}$$

$$\frac{183}{677771} := \frac{18 + 3}{6 + 77771}$$

• **Number 184**

$$\frac{184}{1012} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{10 + 12}$$

$$\frac{184}{10212} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{10 + 212}$$

$$\frac{184}{102212} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{10 + 2212}$$

$$\frac{184}{1022212} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{10 + 22212}$$

$$\frac{184}{1242} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{1 + 24 + 2}$$

$$\frac{184}{12742} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{1 + 274 + 2}$$

$$\frac{184}{127742} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{1 + 2774 + 2}$$

$$\frac{184}{1277742} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{1 + 27774 + 2}$$

$$\frac{184}{506} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{5 + 06}$$

$$\frac{184}{5106} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{5 + 106}$$

$$\frac{184}{51106} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{5 + 1106}$$

$$\frac{184}{511106} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{5 + 11106}$$

$$\frac{184}{506} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{5 + 06}$$

$$\frac{184}{5106} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{5 + 106}$$

$$\frac{184}{51106} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{5 + 1106}$$

$$\frac{184}{511106} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{5 + 11106}$$

• **Number 185**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{185}{1221} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{12 + 21} \\ \frac{185}{12321} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{12 + 321} \\ \frac{185}{123321} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{12 + 3321} \\ \frac{185}{1233321} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{12 + 33321} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{185}{407} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{4 + 07} \\ \frac{185}{4107} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{4 + 107} \\ \frac{185}{41107} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{4 + 1107} \\ \frac{185}{411107} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{4 + 11107} \end{array}$$

• **Number 186**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{186}{1023} := \frac{1^8 \times 6}{10 + 23} \\ \frac{186}{10323} := \frac{1^8 \times 6}{10 + 323} \\ \frac{186}{103323} := \frac{1^8 \times 6}{10 + 3323} \\ \frac{186}{1033323} := \frac{1^8 \times 6}{10 + 33323} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{186}{341} := \frac{18 + 6}{3 + 41} \\ \frac{186}{3441} := \frac{18 + 6}{3 + 441} \\ \frac{186}{34441} := \frac{18 + 6}{3 + 4441} \\ \frac{186}{344441} := \frac{18 + 6}{3 + 44441} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{186}{682} := \frac{18 + 6}{6 + 82} \\ \frac{186}{6882} := \frac{18 + 6}{6 + 882} \\ \frac{186}{68882} := \frac{18 + 6}{6 + 8882} \\ \frac{186}{688882} := \frac{18 + 6}{6 + 88882} \end{array}$$

• **Number 187**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{187}{1887} := \frac{1 + 87}{1 + 887} \\ \frac{187}{188887} := \frac{1 + 87}{1 + 88887} \\ \frac{187}{1888887} := \frac{1 + 87}{1 + 888887} \\ \frac{187}{18888887} := \frac{1 + 87}{1 + 8888887} \end{array}$$

• **Number 188**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{188}{1034} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{10 + 34} \\ \frac{188}{10434} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{10 + 434} \\ \frac{188}{104434} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{10 + 4434} \\ \frac{188}{1044434} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{10 + 44434} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{188}{1551} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{15 + 51} \\ \frac{188}{15651} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{15 + 651} \\ \frac{188}{156651} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{15 + 6651} \\ \frac{188}{1566651} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{15 + 66651} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{188}{517} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{5 + 17} \\ \frac{188}{5217} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{5 + 217} \\ \frac{188}{52217} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{5 + 2217} \\ \frac{188}{522217} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{5 + 22217} \end{array}$$

● **Number 189**

$\frac{189}{231} := \frac{18+9}{2+31}$	$\frac{189}{462} := \frac{18+9}{4+62}$	$\frac{189}{693} := \frac{18+9}{6+93}$
$\frac{189}{2331} := \frac{18+9}{2+331}$	$\frac{189}{4662} := \frac{18+9}{4+662}$	$\frac{189}{6993} := \frac{18+9}{6+993}$
$\frac{189}{23331} := \frac{18+9}{2+3331}$	$\frac{189}{46662} := \frac{18+9}{4+6662}$	$\frac{189}{69993} := \frac{18+9}{6+9993}$
$\frac{189}{233331} := \frac{18+9}{2+33331}$	$\frac{189}{466662} := \frac{18+9}{4+66662}$	$\frac{189}{699993} := \frac{18+9}{6+99993}$

● **Number 190**

$\frac{190}{1045} := \frac{1+9+0}{10+45}$	$\frac{190}{1254} := \frac{1+9+0}{12+54}$	$\frac{190}{1463} := \frac{1+9+0}{14+63}$
$\frac{190}{10545} := \frac{1+9+0}{10+545}$	$\frac{190}{12654} := \frac{1+9+0}{12+654}$	$\frac{190}{14763} := \frac{1+9+0}{14+763}$
$\frac{190}{105545} := \frac{1+9+0}{10+5545}$	$\frac{190}{126654} := \frac{1+9+0}{12+6654}$	$\frac{190}{147763} := \frac{1+9+0}{14+7763}$
$\frac{190}{1055545} := \frac{1+9+0}{10+55545}$	$\frac{190}{1266654} := \frac{1+9+0}{12+66654}$	$\frac{190}{1477763} := \frac{1+9+0}{14+77763}$

$\frac{190}{1881} := \frac{1+9+0}{18+81}$	$\frac{190}{209} := \frac{1+9+0}{2+09}$	$\frac{190}{418} := \frac{1+9+0}{4+18}$
$\frac{190}{18981} := \frac{1+9+0}{18+981}$	$\frac{190}{2109} := \frac{1+9+0}{2+109}$	$\frac{190}{4218} := \frac{1+9+0}{4+218}$
$\frac{190}{189981} := \frac{1+9+0}{18+9981}$	$\frac{190}{21109} := \frac{1+9+0}{2+1109}$	$\frac{190}{42218} := \frac{1+9+0}{4+2218}$
$\frac{190}{1899981} := \frac{1+9+0}{18+99981}$	$\frac{190}{211109} := \frac{1+9+0}{2+11109}$	$\frac{190}{422218} := \frac{1+9+0}{4+22218}$

$\frac{190}{627} := \frac{1+9+0}{6+27}$	$\frac{190}{836} := \frac{1+9+0}{8+36}$
$\frac{190}{6327} := \frac{1+9+0}{6+327}$	$\frac{190}{8436} := \frac{1+9+0}{8+436}$
$\frac{190}{63327} := \frac{1+9+0}{6+3327}$	$\frac{190}{84436} := \frac{1+9+0}{8+4436}$
$\frac{190}{633327} := \frac{1+9+0}{6+33327}$	$\frac{190}{844436} := \frac{1+9+0}{8+44436}$

● **Number 192**

$$\frac{192}{1056} := \frac{1+9+2}{10+56}$$

$$\frac{192}{10656} := \frac{1+9+2}{10+656}$$

$$\frac{192}{106656} := \frac{1+9+2}{10+6656}$$

$$\frac{192}{1066656} := \frac{1+9+2}{10+66656}$$

$$\frac{192}{528} := \frac{1+9+2}{5+28}$$

$$\frac{192}{5328} := \frac{1+9+2}{5+328}$$

$$\frac{192}{53328} := \frac{1+9+2}{5+3328}$$

$$\frac{192}{533328} := \frac{1+9+2}{5+33328}$$

$$\frac{192}{704} := \frac{1^9+2}{7+04}$$

$$\frac{192}{7104} := \frac{1^9+2}{7+104}$$

$$\frac{192}{71104} := \frac{1^9+2}{7+1104}$$

$$\frac{192}{711104} := \frac{1^9+2}{7+11104}$$

● **Number 194**

$$\frac{194}{1067} := \frac{1+9+4}{10+67}$$

$$\frac{194}{10767} := \frac{1+9+4}{10+767}$$

$$\frac{194}{107767} := \frac{1+9+4}{10+7767}$$

$$\frac{194}{1077767} := \frac{1+9+4}{10+77767}$$

● **Number 195**

$$\frac{195}{1287} := \frac{1+9+5}{12+87}$$

$$\frac{195}{12987} := \frac{1+9+5}{12+987}$$

$$\frac{195}{129987} := \frac{1+9+5}{12+9987}$$

$$\frac{195}{1299987} := \frac{1+9+5}{12+99987}$$

$$\frac{195}{429} := \frac{1+9+5}{4+29}$$

$$\frac{195}{4329} := \frac{1+9+5}{4+329}$$

$$\frac{195}{43329} := \frac{1+9+5}{4+3329}$$

$$\frac{195}{433329} := \frac{1+9+5}{4+33329}$$

$$\frac{195}{715} := \frac{1^9+5}{7+15}$$

$$\frac{195}{7215} := \frac{1^9+5}{7+215}$$

$$\frac{195}{72215} := \frac{1^9+5}{7+2215}$$

$$\frac{195}{722215} := \frac{1^9+5}{7+22215}$$

$$\frac{195}{858} := \frac{1+9+5}{8+58}$$

$$\frac{195}{8658} := \frac{1+9+5}{8+658}$$

$$\frac{195}{86658} := \frac{1+9+5}{8+6658}$$

$$\frac{195}{866658} := \frac{1+9+5}{8+66658}$$

● **Number 196**

$$\frac{196}{1078} := \frac{1+9+6}{10+78}$$

$$\frac{196}{10878} := \frac{1+9+6}{10+878}$$

$$\frac{196}{108878} := \frac{1+9+6}{10+8878}$$

$$\frac{196}{1088878} := \frac{1+9+6}{10+88878}$$

$$\frac{196}{1512} := \frac{1^9+6}{1+51+2}$$

$$\frac{196}{15512} := \frac{1^9+6}{1+551+2}$$

$$\frac{196}{155512} := \frac{1^9+6}{1+5551+2}$$

$$\frac{196}{1555512} := \frac{1^9+6}{1+55551+2}$$

$$\frac{196}{308} := \frac{1^9+6}{3+08}$$

$$\frac{196}{3108} := \frac{1^9+6}{3+108}$$

$$\frac{196}{31108} := \frac{1^9+6}{3+1108}$$

$$\frac{196}{311108} := \frac{1^9+6}{3+11108}$$

$$\frac{196}{539} := \frac{1+9+6}{5+39}$$

$$\frac{196}{5439} := \frac{1+9+6}{5+439}$$

$$\frac{196}{54439} := \frac{1+9+6}{5+4439}$$

$$\frac{196}{544439} := \frac{1+9+6}{5+44439}$$

$$\frac{196}{616} := \frac{1^9+6}{6+16}$$

$$\frac{196}{6216} := \frac{1^9+6}{6+216}$$

$$\frac{196}{62216} := \frac{1^9+6}{6+2216}$$

$$\frac{196}{622216} := \frac{1^9+6}{6+22216}$$

$$\frac{196}{924} := \frac{1^9+6}{9+24}$$

$$\frac{196}{9324} := \frac{1^9+6}{9+324}$$

$$\frac{196}{93324} := \frac{1^9+6}{9+3324}$$

$$\frac{196}{933324} := \frac{1^9+6}{9+33324}$$

• **Number 198**

$$\frac{198}{1089} := \frac{1+9+8}{10+89}$$

$$\frac{198}{10989} := \frac{1+9+8}{10+989}$$

$$\frac{198}{109989} := \frac{1+9+8}{10+9989}$$

$$\frac{198}{1099989} := \frac{1+9+8}{10+99989}$$

$$\frac{198}{1452} := \frac{1^9+8}{14+52}$$

$$\frac{198}{14652} := \frac{1^9+8}{14+652}$$

$$\frac{198}{146652} := \frac{1^9+8}{14+6652}$$

$$\frac{198}{1466652} := \frac{1^9+8}{14+66652}$$

$$\frac{198}{726} := \frac{1^9+8}{7+26}$$

$$\frac{198}{7326} := \frac{1^9+8}{7+326}$$

$$\frac{198}{73326} := \frac{1^9+8}{7+3326}$$

$$\frac{198}{733326} := \frac{1^9+8}{7+33326}$$

• **Number 202**

$$\frac{202}{1111} := \frac{2^{02}}{11+11}$$

$$\frac{202}{11211} := \frac{2^{02}}{11+211}$$

$$\frac{202}{112211} := \frac{2^{02}}{11+2211}$$

$$\frac{202}{1122211} := \frac{2^{02}}{11+22211}$$

• **Number 204**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{204}{1122} := \frac{2+04}{11+22} \\ \frac{204}{11322} := \frac{2+04}{11+322} \\ \frac{204}{113322} := \frac{2+04}{11+3322} \\ \frac{204}{1133322} := \frac{2+04}{11+33322} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \frac{204}{561} := \frac{20+4}{5+61} \\ \frac{204}{5661} := \frac{20+4}{5+661} \\ \frac{204}{56661} := \frac{20+4}{5+6661} \\ \frac{204}{566661} := \frac{20+4}{5+66661} \end{array}$$

● **Number 205**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{205}{1353} := \frac{2 \times 05}{13+53} \\ \frac{205}{13653} := \frac{2 \times 05}{13+653} \\ \frac{205}{136653} := \frac{2 \times 05}{13+6653} \\ \frac{205}{1366653} := \frac{2 \times 05}{13+66653} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \frac{205}{451} := \frac{20+5}{4+51} \\ \frac{205}{4551} := \frac{20+5}{4+551} \\ \frac{205}{45551} := \frac{20+5}{4+5551} \\ \frac{205}{455551} := \frac{20+5}{4+55551} \end{array}$$

● **Number 206**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{206}{1133} := \frac{2+06}{11+33} \\ \frac{206}{11433} := \frac{2+06}{11+433} \\ \frac{206}{114433} := \frac{2+06}{11+4433} \\ \frac{206}{1144433} := \frac{2+06}{11+44433} \end{array}$$

● **Number 208**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{208}{429} := \frac{2 \times 08}{4+29} \\ \frac{208}{4329} := \frac{2 \times 08}{4+329} \\ \frac{208}{43329} := \frac{2 \times 08}{4+3329} \\ \frac{208}{433329} := \frac{2 \times 08}{4+33329} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \frac{208}{572} := \frac{20+8}{5+72} \\ \frac{208}{5772} := \frac{20+8}{5+772} \\ \frac{208}{57772} := \frac{20+8}{5+7772} \\ \frac{208}{577772} := \frac{20+8}{5+77772} \end{array}$$

● **Number 209**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{209}{1045} &:= \frac{2+09}{10+45} \\ \frac{209}{10545} &:= \frac{2+09}{10+545} \\ \frac{209}{105545} &:= \frac{2+09}{10+5545} \\ \frac{209}{1055545} &:= \frac{2+09}{10+55545} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{209}{1254} &:= \frac{2+09}{12+54} \\ \frac{209}{12654} &:= \frac{2+09}{12+654} \\ \frac{209}{126654} &:= \frac{2+09}{12+6654} \\ \frac{209}{1266654} &:= \frac{2+09}{12+66654} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{209}{1463} &:= \frac{2+09}{14+63} \\ \frac{209}{14763} &:= \frac{2+09}{14+763} \\ \frac{209}{147763} &:= \frac{2+09}{14+7763} \\ \frac{209}{1477763} &:= \frac{2+09}{14+77763} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{209}{1672} &:= \frac{2+09}{16+72} \\ \frac{209}{16872} &:= \frac{2+09}{16+872} \\ \frac{209}{168872} &:= \frac{2+09}{16+8872} \\ \frac{209}{1688872} &:= \frac{2+09}{16+88872} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{209}{418} &:= \frac{2+09}{4+18} \\ \frac{209}{4218} &:= \frac{2+09}{4+218} \\ \frac{209}{42218} &:= \frac{2+09}{4+2218} \\ \frac{209}{422218} &:= \frac{2+09}{4+22218} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{209}{627} &:= \frac{2+09}{6+27} \\ \frac{209}{6327} &:= \frac{2+09}{6+327} \\ \frac{209}{63327} &:= \frac{2+09}{6+3327} \\ \frac{209}{633327} &:= \frac{2+09}{6+33327} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{209}{836} &:= \frac{2+09}{8+36} \\ \frac{209}{8436} &:= \frac{2+09}{8+436} \\ \frac{209}{84436} &:= \frac{2+09}{8+4436} \\ \frac{209}{844436} &:= \frac{2+09}{8+44436} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 210**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{210}{1155} &:= \frac{2+10}{11+55} \\ \frac{210}{11655} &:= \frac{2+10}{11+655} \\ \frac{210}{116655} &:= \frac{2+10}{11+6655} \\ \frac{210}{1166655} &:= \frac{2+10}{11+66655} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 212**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{212}{1749} &:= \frac{2^{1+2}}{17+49} \\ \frac{212}{17649} &:= \frac{2^{1+2}}{17+649} \\ \frac{212}{176649} &:= \frac{2^{1+2}}{17+6649} \\ \frac{212}{1766649} &:= \frac{2^{1+2}}{17+66649}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 213**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{213}{781} &:= \frac{21+3}{7+81} \\ \frac{213}{7881} &:= \frac{21+3}{7+881} \\ \frac{213}{78881} &:= \frac{21+3}{7+8881} \\ \frac{213}{788881} &:= \frac{21+3}{7+88881}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 214**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{214}{1177} &:= \frac{2+14}{11+77} \\ \frac{214}{11877} &:= \frac{2+14}{11+877} \\ \frac{214}{118877} &:= \frac{2+14}{11+8877} \\ \frac{214}{1188877} &:= \frac{2+14}{11+88877}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 216**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{216}{1188} &:= \frac{2+16}{11+88} \\ \frac{216}{11988} &:= \frac{2+16}{11+988} \\ \frac{216}{119988} &:= \frac{2+16}{11+9988} \\ \frac{216}{1199988} &:= \frac{2+16}{11+99988}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 217**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{217}{341} := \frac{21+7}{3+41} \\ \frac{217}{3441} := \frac{21+7}{3+441} \\ \frac{217}{34441} := \frac{21+7}{3+4441} \\ \frac{217}{344441} := \frac{21+7}{3+44441} \\ \frac{217}{682} := \frac{21+7}{6+82} \\ \frac{217}{6882} := \frac{21+7}{6+882} \\ \frac{217}{68882} := \frac{21+7}{6+8882} \\ \frac{217}{688882} := \frac{21+7}{6+88882} \end{array}$$

• **Number 219**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{219}{1606} := \frac{2+1^9}{16+06} \\ \frac{219}{16206} := \frac{2+1^9}{16+206} \\ \frac{219}{162206} := \frac{2+1^9}{16+2206} \\ \frac{219}{1622206} := \frac{2+1^9}{16+22206} \\ \frac{219}{803} := \frac{2+1^9}{8+03} \\ \frac{219}{8103} := \frac{2+1^9}{8+103} \\ \frac{219}{81103} := \frac{2+1^9}{8+1103} \\ \frac{219}{811103} := \frac{2+1^9}{8+11103} \end{array}$$

• **Number 220**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{220}{1221} := \frac{2 \times 20}{1+221} \\ \frac{220}{12221} := \frac{2 \times 20}{1+2221} \\ \frac{220}{122221} := \frac{2 \times 20}{1+22221} \\ \frac{220}{1222221} := \frac{2 \times 20}{1+222221} \\ \frac{220}{1155} := \frac{2^2+0}{1+15+5} \\ \frac{220}{12155} := \frac{2^2+0}{1+215+5} \\ \frac{220}{122155} := \frac{2^2+0}{1+2215+5} \\ \frac{220}{1222155} := \frac{2^2+0}{1+22215+5} \\ \frac{220}{1815} := \frac{2^{2+0}}{18+15} \\ \frac{220}{18315} := \frac{2^{2+0}}{18+315} \\ \frac{220}{183315} := \frac{2^{2+0}}{18+3315} \\ \frac{220}{1833315} := \frac{2^{2+0}}{18+33315} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{220}{242} := \frac{2 \times 20}{2+42} \\ \frac{220}{2442} := \frac{2 \times 20}{2+442} \\ \frac{220}{24442} := \frac{2 \times 20}{2+4442} \\ \frac{220}{244442} := \frac{2 \times 20}{2+44442} \\ \frac{220}{363} := \frac{2 \times 20}{3+63} \\ \frac{220}{3663} := \frac{2 \times 20}{3+663} \\ \frac{220}{36663} := \frac{2 \times 20}{3+6663} \\ \frac{220}{366663} := \frac{2 \times 20}{3+66663} \\ \frac{220}{484} := \frac{2 \times 20}{4+84} \\ \frac{220}{4884} := \frac{2 \times 20}{4+884} \\ \frac{220}{48884} := \frac{2 \times 20}{4+8884} \\ \frac{220}{488884} := \frac{2 \times 20}{4+88884} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{220}{48884} := \frac{2 \times 20}{4 + 8884} \\ \frac{220}{488884} := \frac{2 \times 20}{4 + 88884} \\ \frac{220}{4888884} := \frac{2 \times 20}{4 + 888884} \\ \frac{220}{605} := \frac{2^2 + 0}{6 + 05} \\ \frac{220}{6105} := \frac{2^2 + 0}{6 + 105} \\ \frac{220}{61105} := \frac{2^2 + 0}{6 + 1105} \\ \frac{220}{611105} := \frac{2^2 + 0}{6 + 11105} \end{array}$$

• **Number 222**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{222}{1221} := \frac{2 + 2^2}{12 + 21} \\ \frac{222}{12321} := \frac{2 + 2^2}{12 + 321} \\ \frac{222}{123321} := \frac{2 + 2^2}{12 + 3321} \\ \frac{222}{1233321} := \frac{2 + 2^2}{12 + 33321} \\ \frac{222}{407} := \frac{2 + 2^2}{4 + 07} \\ \frac{222}{4107} := \frac{2 + 2^2}{4 + 107} \\ \frac{222}{41107} := \frac{2 + 2^2}{4 + 1107} \\ \frac{222}{411107} := \frac{2 + 2^2}{4 + 11107} \\ \frac{222}{814} := \frac{2 + 2^2}{8 + 14} \\ \frac{222}{8214} := \frac{2 + 2^2}{8 + 214} \\ \frac{222}{82214} := \frac{2 + 2^2}{8 + 2214} \\ \frac{222}{822214} := \frac{2 + 2^2}{8 + 22214} \end{array}$$

• **Number 224**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{224}{1386} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 4}{13 + 86} \\ \frac{224}{13986} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 4}{13 + 986} \\ \frac{224}{139986} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 4}{13 + 9986} \\ \frac{224}{231} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{2 + 31} \\ \frac{224}{2331} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{2 + 331} \\ \frac{224}{23331} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{2 + 3331} \\ \frac{224}{233331} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{2 + 33331} \\ \frac{224}{308} := \frac{2 + 2 + 4}{3 + 08} \\ \frac{224}{3108} := \frac{2 + 2 + 4}{3 + 108} \\ \frac{224}{31108} := \frac{2 + 2 + 4}{3 + 1108} \\ \frac{224}{311108} := \frac{2 + 2 + 4}{3 + 11108} \\ \frac{224}{462} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{4 + 62} \\ \frac{224}{4662} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{4 + 662} \\ \frac{224}{46662} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{4 + 6662} \\ \frac{224}{616} := \frac{2 + 2 + 4}{6 + 16} \\ \frac{224}{6216} := \frac{2 + 2 + 4}{6 + 216} \\ \frac{224}{62216} := \frac{2 + 2 + 4}{6 + 2216} \\ \frac{224}{622216} := \frac{2 + 2 + 4}{6 + 22216} \\ \frac{224}{924} := \frac{2 + 2 + 4}{9 + 24} \\ \frac{224}{9324} := \frac{2 + 2 + 4}{9 + 324} \\ \frac{224}{93324} := \frac{2 + 2 + 4}{9 + 3324} \\ \frac{224}{933324} := \frac{2 + 2 + 4}{9 + 33324} \end{array}$$

• **Number 225**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{225}{825} &:= \frac{2+2+5}{8+25} \\ \frac{225}{8325} &:= \frac{2+2+5}{8+325} \\ \frac{225}{83325} &:= \frac{2+2+5}{8+3325} \\ \frac{225}{833325} &:= \frac{2+2+5}{8+33325} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 226**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{226}{1243} &:= \frac{2+2+6}{12+43} \\ \frac{226}{12543} &:= \frac{2+2+6}{12+543} \\ \frac{226}{125543} &:= \frac{2+2+6}{12+5543} \\ \frac{226}{1255543} &:= \frac{2+2+6}{12+55543} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 228**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{228}{1254} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{12+54} \\ \frac{228}{12654} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{12+654} \\ \frac{228}{126654} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{12+6654} \\ \frac{228}{1266654} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{12+66654} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{228}{1463} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{14+63} \\ \frac{228}{14763} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{14+763} \\ \frac{228}{147763} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{14+7763} \\ \frac{228}{1477763} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{14+77763} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{228}{1672} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{16+72} \\ \frac{228}{16872} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{16+872} \\ \frac{228}{168872} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{16+8872} \\ \frac{228}{1688872} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{16+88872} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{228}{418} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{4+18} \\ \frac{228}{4218} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{4+218} \\ \frac{228}{42218} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{4+2218} \\ \frac{228}{422218} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{4+22218} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{228}{627} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{6+27} \\ \frac{228}{6327} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{6+327} \\ \frac{228}{63327} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{6+3327} \\ \frac{228}{633327} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{6+33327} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{228}{836} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{8+36} \\ \frac{228}{8436} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{8+436} \\ \frac{228}{84436} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{8+4436} \\ \frac{228}{844436} &:= \frac{2+2+8}{8+44436} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 230**

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{230}{1012} := \frac{2+3+0}{10+12} \\
 \frac{230}{10212} := \frac{2+3+0}{10+212} \\
 \frac{230}{102212} := \frac{2+3+0}{10+2212} \\
 \frac{230}{1022212} := \frac{2+3+0}{10+22212} \\
 \frac{230}{17595} := \frac{2^3+0}{17+595} \\
 \frac{230}{175595} := \frac{2^3+0}{17+5595} \\
 \frac{230}{1755595} := \frac{2^3+0}{17+55595} \\
 \frac{230}{17555595} := \frac{2^3+0}{17+555595} \\
 \frac{230}{506} := \frac{2+3+0}{5+06} \\
 \frac{230}{5106} := \frac{2+3+0}{5+106} \\
 \frac{230}{51106} := \frac{2+3+0}{5+1106} \\
 \frac{230}{511106} := \frac{2+3+0}{5+11106}
 \end{array}$$

• **Number 231**

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{231}{462} := \frac{2+31}{4+62} \\
 \frac{231}{4662} := \frac{2+31}{4+662} \\
 \frac{231}{46662} := \frac{2+31}{4+6662} \\
 \frac{231}{466662} := \frac{2+31}{4+66662} \\
 \frac{231}{693} := \frac{2+31}{6+93} \\
 \frac{231}{6993} := \frac{2+31}{6+993} \\
 \frac{231}{69993} := \frac{2+31}{6+9993} \\
 \frac{231}{699993} := \frac{2+31}{6+99993}
 \end{array}$$

• **Number 232**

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{232}{319} := \frac{2^3 \times 2}{3+19} \\
 \frac{232}{3219} := \frac{2^3 \times 2}{3+219} \\
 \frac{232}{32219} := \frac{2^3 \times 2}{3+2219} \\
 \frac{232}{322219} := \frac{2^3 \times 2}{3+22219} \\
 \frac{232}{638} := \frac{2^3 \times 2}{6+38} \\
 \frac{232}{6438} := \frac{2^3 \times 2}{6+438} \\
 \frac{232}{64438} := \frac{2^3 \times 2}{6+4438} \\
 \frac{232}{644438} := \frac{2^3 \times 2}{6+44438}
 \end{array}$$

• **Number 235**

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{235}{1034} := \frac{2+3+5}{10+34} \\
 \frac{235}{10434} := \frac{2+3+5}{10+434} \\
 \frac{235}{104434} := \frac{2+3+5}{10+4434} \\
 \frac{235}{1044434} := \frac{2+3+5}{10+44434} \\
 \frac{235}{1551} := \frac{2+3+5}{15+51} \\
 \frac{235}{15651} := \frac{2+3+5}{15+651} \\
 \frac{235}{156651} := \frac{2+3+5}{15+6651} \\
 \frac{235}{1566651} := \frac{2+3+5}{15+66651} \\
 \frac{235}{517} := \frac{2+3+5}{5+17} \\
 \frac{235}{5217} := \frac{2+3+5}{5+217} \\
 \frac{235}{52217} := \frac{2+3+5}{5+2217} \\
 \frac{235}{522217} := \frac{2+3+5}{5+22217}
 \end{array}$$

● **Number 236**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{236}{649} &:= \frac{2+3 \times 6}{6+49} \\ \frac{236}{6549} &:= \frac{2+3 \times 6}{6+549} \\ \frac{236}{65549} &:= \frac{2+3 \times 6}{6+5549} \\ \frac{236}{655549} &:= \frac{2+3 \times 6}{6+55549} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 240**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{240}{1485} &:= \frac{2^4+0}{14+85} \\ \frac{240}{14985} &:= \frac{2^4+0}{14+985} \\ \frac{240}{149985} &:= \frac{2^4+0}{14+9985} \\ \frac{240}{1499985} &:= \frac{2^4+0}{14+99985} \\ \frac{240}{297} &:= \frac{2 \times 40}{2+97} \\ \frac{240}{2997} &:= \frac{2 \times 40}{2+997} \\ \frac{240}{29997} &:= \frac{2 \times 40}{2+9997} \\ \frac{240}{299997} &:= \frac{2 \times 40}{2+99997} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 242**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{242}{1221} &:= \frac{2+42}{1+221} \\ \frac{242}{12221} &:= \frac{2+42}{1+2221} \\ \frac{242}{122221} &:= \frac{2+42}{1+22221} \\ \frac{242}{1222221} &:= \frac{2+42}{1+222221} \\ \frac{242}{363} &:= \frac{2+42}{3+63} \\ \frac{242}{3663} &:= \frac{2+42}{3+663} \\ \frac{242}{36663} &:= \frac{2+42}{3+6663} \\ \frac{242}{366663} &:= \frac{2+42}{3+66663} \\ \frac{242}{1331} &:= \frac{2+4+2}{13+31} \\ \frac{242}{13431} &:= \frac{2+4+2}{13+431} \\ \frac{242}{134431} &:= \frac{2+4+2}{13+4431} \\ \frac{242}{1344431} &:= \frac{2+4+2}{13+44431} \\ \frac{242}{484} &:= \frac{2+42}{4+84} \\ \frac{242}{4884} &:= \frac{2+42}{4+884} \\ \frac{242}{48884} &:= \frac{2+42}{4+8884} \\ \frac{242}{488884} &:= \frac{2+42}{4+88884} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 243**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{243}{891} &:= \frac{24+3}{8+91} \\ \frac{243}{8991} &:= \frac{24+3}{8+991} \\ \frac{243}{89991} &:= \frac{24+3}{8+9991} \\ \frac{243}{899991} &:= \frac{24+3}{8+99991} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 244**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{244}{671} &:= \frac{24+4}{6+71} \\ \frac{244}{6771} &:= \frac{24+4}{6+771} \\ \frac{244}{67771} &:= \frac{24+4}{6+7771} \\ \frac{244}{677771} &:= \frac{24+4}{6+77771} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 246**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{246}{1353} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{13+53} \\ \frac{246}{13653} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{13+653} \\ \frac{246}{136653} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{13+6653} \\ \frac{246}{1366653} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{13+66653} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{246}{451} &:= \frac{24+6}{4+51} \\ \frac{246}{4551} &:= \frac{24+6}{4+551} \\ \frac{246}{45551} &:= \frac{24+6}{4+5551} \\ \frac{246}{455551} &:= \frac{24+6}{4+55551} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 247**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{247}{1045} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{10+45} \\ \frac{247}{10545} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{10+545} \\ \frac{247}{105545} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{10+5545} \\ \frac{247}{1055545} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{10+55545} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{247}{1254} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{12+54} \\ \frac{247}{12654} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{12+654} \\ \frac{247}{126654} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{12+6654} \\ \frac{247}{1266654} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{12+66654} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{247}{1463} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{14+63} \\ \frac{247}{14763} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{14+763} \\ \frac{247}{147763} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{14+7763} \\ \frac{247}{1477763} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{14+77763} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{247}{418} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{4+18} \\ \frac{247}{4218} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{4+218} \\ \frac{247}{42218} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{4+2218} \\ \frac{247}{422218} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{4+22218} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{247}{627} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{6+27} \\ \frac{247}{6327} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{6+327} \\ \frac{247}{63327} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{6+3327} \\ \frac{247}{633327} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{6+33327} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{247}{836} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{8+36} \\ \frac{247}{8436} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{8+436} \\ \frac{247}{84436} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{8+4436} \\ \frac{247}{844436} &:= \frac{2+4+7}{8+44436} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 248**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{248}{13764} &:= \frac{2+4+8}{13+764} \\ \frac{248}{137764} &:= \frac{2+4+8}{13+7764} \\ \frac{248}{1377764} &:= \frac{2+4+8}{13+77764} \\ \frac{248}{13777764} &:= \frac{2+4+8}{13+777764} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{248}{341} &:= \frac{24+8}{3+41} \\ \frac{248}{3441} &:= \frac{24+8}{3+441} \\ \frac{248}{34441} &:= \frac{24+8}{3+4441} \\ \frac{248}{344441} &:= \frac{24+8}{3+44441} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{248}{682} &:= \frac{24+8}{6+82} \\ \frac{248}{6882} &:= \frac{24+8}{6+882} \\ \frac{248}{68882} &:= \frac{24+8}{6+8882} \\ \frac{248}{688882} &:= \frac{24+8}{6+88882} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 250**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{250}{1575} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{1 + 57 + 5} \\ \frac{250}{16575} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{1 + 657 + 5} \\ \frac{250}{166575} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{1 + 6657 + 5} \\ \frac{250}{1666575} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{1 + 66657 + 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{250}{1665} &:= \frac{2 \times 50}{1 + 665} \\ \frac{250}{16665} &:= \frac{2 \times 50}{1 + 6665} \\ \frac{250}{166665} &:= \frac{2 \times 50}{1 + 66665} \\ \frac{250}{1666665} &:= \frac{2 \times 50}{1 + 666665} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{250}{825} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{8 + 25} \\ \frac{250}{8325} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{8 + 325} \\ \frac{250}{83325} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{8 + 3325} \\ \frac{250}{833325} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{8 + 33325} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 252**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{252}{616} &:= \frac{2+5+2}{6+16} \\ \frac{252}{6216} &:= \frac{2+5+2}{6+216} \\ \frac{252}{62216} &:= \frac{2+5+2}{6+2216} \\ \frac{252}{622216} &:= \frac{2+5+2}{6+22216} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{252}{924} &:= \frac{2+5+2}{9+24} \\ \frac{252}{9324} &:= \frac{2+5+2}{9+324} \\ \frac{252}{93324} &:= \frac{2+5+2}{9+3324} \\ \frac{252}{933324} &:= \frac{2+5+2}{9+33324} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 255**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{255}{1683} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{16 + 83} \\ \frac{255}{16983} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{16 + 983} \\ \frac{255}{169983} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{16 + 9983} \\ \frac{255}{1699983} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{16 + 99983} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{255}{561} &:= \frac{25 + 5}{5 + 61} \\ \frac{255}{5661} &:= \frac{25 + 5}{5 + 661} \\ \frac{255}{56661} &:= \frac{25 + 5}{5 + 6661} \\ \frac{255}{566661} &:= \frac{25 + 5}{5 + 66661} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{255}{935} &:= \frac{2 + 5 + 5}{9 + 35} \\ \frac{255}{9435} &:= \frac{2 + 5 + 5}{9 + 435} \\ \frac{255}{94435} &:= \frac{2 + 5 + 5}{9 + 4435} \\ \frac{255}{944435} &:= \frac{2 + 5 + 5}{9 + 44435} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 256**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{256}{1056} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 6}{10 + 56} \\ \frac{256}{10656} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 6}{10 + 656} \\ \frac{256}{106656} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 6}{10 + 6656} \\ \frac{256}{1066656} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 6}{10 + 66656} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{256}{1584} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 6}{15 + 84} \\ \frac{256}{15984} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 6}{15 + 984} \\ \frac{256}{159984} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 6}{15 + 9984} \\ \frac{256}{1599984} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 + 6}{15 + 99984} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{256}{1776} &:= \frac{2 \times 56}{1 + 776} \\ \frac{256}{17776} &:= \frac{2 \times 56}{1 + 7776} \\ \frac{256}{177776} &:= \frac{2 \times 56}{1 + 77776} \\ \frac{256}{1777776} &:= \frac{2 \times 56}{1 + 777776} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{256}{792} &:= \frac{2 + 5 \times 6}{7 + 92} \\ \frac{256}{7992} &:= \frac{2 + 5 \times 6}{7 + 992} \\ \frac{256}{79992} &:= \frac{2 + 5 \times 6}{7 + 9992} \\ \frac{256}{799992} &:= \frac{2 + 5 \times 6}{7 + 99992} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 258**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{258}{473} &:= \frac{2 + 5 \times 8}{4 + 73} \\ \frac{258}{4773} &:= \frac{2 + 5 \times 8}{4 + 773} \\ \frac{258}{47773} &:= \frac{2 + 5 \times 8}{4 + 7773} \\ \frac{258}{477773} &:= \frac{2 + 5 \times 8}{4 + 77773} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{258}{946} &:= \frac{2 + 5 + 8}{9 + 46} \\ \frac{258}{9546} &:= \frac{2 + 5 + 8}{9 + 546} \\ \frac{258}{95546} &:= \frac{2 + 5 + 8}{9 + 5546} \\ \frac{258}{955546} &:= \frac{2 + 5 + 8}{9 + 55546} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 260**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{260}{1365} := \frac{2+6+0}{1+36+5} \\ \frac{260}{14365} := \frac{2+6+0}{1+436+5} \\ \frac{260}{144365} := \frac{2+6+0}{1+4436+5} \\ \frac{260}{1444365} := \frac{2+6+0}{1+44436+5} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{260}{715} := \frac{2+6+0}{7+15} \\ \frac{260}{7215} := \frac{2+6+0}{7+215} \\ \frac{260}{72215} := \frac{2+6+0}{7+2215} \\ \frac{260}{722215} := \frac{2+6+0}{7+22215} \end{array}$$

● **Number 262**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{262}{1441} := \frac{2+6+2}{14+41} \\ \frac{262}{14541} := \frac{2+6+2}{14+541} \\ \frac{262}{145541} := \frac{2+6+2}{14+5541} \\ \frac{262}{1455541} := \frac{2+6+2}{14+55541} \end{array}$$

● **Number 264**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{264}{1221} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{1+221} \\ \frac{264}{12221} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{1+2221} \\ \frac{264}{122221} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{1+22221} \\ \frac{264}{1222221} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{1+222221} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{264}{1332} := \frac{2+64}{1+332} \\ \frac{264}{13332} := \frac{2+64}{1+3332} \\ \frac{264}{133332} := \frac{2+64}{1+33332} \\ \frac{264}{1333332} := \frac{2+64}{1+333332} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{264}{1452} := \frac{2+6+4}{14+52} \\ \frac{264}{14652} := \frac{2+6+4}{14+652} \\ \frac{264}{146652} := \frac{2+6+4}{14+6652} \\ \frac{264}{1466652} := \frac{2+6+4}{14+66652} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{264}{363} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{3+63} \\ \frac{264}{3663} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{3+663} \\ \frac{264}{36663} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{3+6663} \\ \frac{264}{366663} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{3+66663} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{264}{396} := \frac{2+64}{3+96} \\ \frac{264}{3996} := \frac{2+64}{3+996} \\ \frac{264}{39996} := \frac{2+64}{3+9996} \\ \frac{264}{399996} := \frac{2+64}{3+99996} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{264}{396} := \frac{2+64}{3+96} \\ \frac{264}{3996} := \frac{2+64}{3+996} \\ \frac{264}{39996} := \frac{2+64}{3+9996} \\ \frac{264}{726} := \frac{2+6+4}{7+26} \\ \frac{264}{7326} := \frac{2+6+4}{7+326} \\ \frac{264}{73326} := \frac{2+6+4}{7+3326} \\ \frac{264}{733326} := \frac{2+6+4}{7+33326} \end{array}$$

● **Number 265**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{265}{583} := \frac{(2+6) \times 5}{5+83} \\ \frac{265}{5883} := \frac{(2+6) \times 5}{5+883} \\ \frac{265}{58883} := \frac{(2+6) \times 5}{5+8883} \\ \frac{265}{588883} := \frac{(2+6) \times 5}{5+88883} \end{array}$$

● **Number 266**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{266}{1045} := \frac{2+6+6}{10+45} \\ \frac{266}{10545} := \frac{2+6+6}{10+545} \\ \frac{266}{105545} := \frac{2+6+6}{10+5545} \\ \frac{266}{1055545} := \frac{2+6+6}{10+55545} \\ \frac{266}{1463} := \frac{2+6+6}{14+63} \\ \frac{266}{14763} := \frac{2+6+6}{14+763} \\ \frac{266}{147763} := \frac{2+6+6}{14+7763} \\ \frac{266}{1477763} := \frac{2+6+6}{14+77763} \\ \frac{266}{1672} := \frac{2+6+6}{16+72} \\ \frac{266}{16872} := \frac{2+6+6}{16+872} \\ \frac{266}{168872} := \frac{2+6+6}{16+8872} \\ \frac{266}{1688872} := \frac{2+6+6}{16+88872} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{266}{418} := \frac{2+6+6}{4+18} \\ \frac{266}{4218} := \frac{2+6+6}{4+218} \\ \frac{266}{42218} := \frac{2+6+6}{4+2218} \\ \frac{266}{422218} := \frac{2+6+6}{4+22218} \\ \frac{266}{462} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{4+62} \\ \frac{266}{4662} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{4+662} \\ \frac{266}{46662} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{4+6662} \\ \frac{266}{466662} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{4+66662} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{266}{627} := \frac{2+6+6}{6+27} \\ \frac{266}{6327} := \frac{2+6+6}{6+327} \\ \frac{266}{63327} := \frac{2+6+6}{6+3327} \\ \frac{266}{633327} := \frac{2+6+6}{6+33327} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \frac{266}{693} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{6+93} \\ \frac{266}{6993} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{6+993} \\ \frac{266}{69993} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{6+9993} \\ \frac{266}{699993} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{6+99993} \end{array}$$

● **Number 268**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{268}{1474} := \frac{2+6+8}{14+74} \\ \frac{268}{14874} := \frac{2+6+8}{14+874} \\ \frac{268}{148874} := \frac{2+6+8}{14+8874} \\ \frac{268}{1488874} := \frac{2+6+8}{14+88874} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \frac{268}{737} := \frac{2+6+8}{7+37} \\ \frac{268}{7437} := \frac{2+6+8}{7+437} \\ \frac{268}{74437} := \frac{2+6+8}{7+4437} \\ \frac{268}{744437} := \frac{2+6+8}{7+44437} \end{array}$$

● **Number 272**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{272}{1683} := \frac{2+7 \times 2}{16+83} \\ \frac{272}{16983} := \frac{2+7 \times 2}{16+983} \\ \frac{272}{169983} := \frac{2+7 \times 2}{16+9983} \\ \frac{272}{1699983} := \frac{2+7 \times 2}{16+99983} \end{array}$$

● **Number 279**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{279}{341} := \frac{27+9}{3+41} \\ \frac{279}{3441} := \frac{27+9}{3+441} \\ \frac{279}{34441} := \frac{27+9}{3+4441} \\ \frac{279}{344441} := \frac{27+9}{3+44441} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \frac{279}{682} := \frac{27+9}{6+82} \\ \frac{279}{6882} := \frac{27+9}{6+882} \\ \frac{279}{68882} := \frac{27+9}{6+8882} \\ \frac{279}{688882} := \frac{27+9}{6+88882} \end{array}$$

● **Number 280**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{280}{1155} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 + 0}{11 + 55} \\ \frac{280}{11655} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 + 0}{11 + 655} \\ \frac{280}{116655} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 + 0}{11 + 6655} \\ \frac{280}{1166655} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 + 0}{11 + 66655} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{280}{1232} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{12 + 32} \\ \frac{280}{12432} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{12 + 432} \\ \frac{280}{124432} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{12 + 4432} \\ \frac{280}{1244432} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{12 + 44432} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{280}{1848} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{18 + 48} \\ \frac{280}{18648} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{18 + 648} \\ \frac{280}{186648} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{18 + 6648} \\ \frac{280}{1866648} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{18 + 66648} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{280}{308} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{3 + 08} \\ \frac{280}{3108} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{3 + 108} \\ \frac{280}{31108} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{3 + 1108} \\ \frac{280}{311108} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{3 + 11108} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{280}{616} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{6 + 16} \\ \frac{280}{6216} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{6 + 216} \\ \frac{280}{62216} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{6 + 2216} \\ \frac{280}{622216} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{6 + 22216} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{280}{924} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{9 + 24} \\ \frac{280}{9324} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{9 + 324} \\ \frac{280}{93324} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{9 + 3324} \\ \frac{280}{933324} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 0}{9 + 33324} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 282**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{282}{1034} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 2}{10 + 34} \\ \frac{282}{10434} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 2}{10 + 434} \\ \frac{282}{104434} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 2}{10 + 4434} \\ \frac{282}{1044434} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 2}{10 + 44434} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{282}{1551} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 2}{15 + 51} \\ \frac{282}{15651} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 2}{15 + 651} \\ \frac{282}{156651} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 2}{15 + 6651} \\ \frac{282}{1566651} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 2}{15 + 66651} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{282}{517} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 2}{5 + 17} \\ \frac{282}{5217} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 2}{5 + 217} \\ \frac{282}{52217} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 2}{5 + 2217} \\ \frac{282}{522217} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 2}{5 + 22217} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 284**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{284}{1562} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 4}{15 + 62} \\ \frac{284}{15762} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 4}{15 + 762} \\ \frac{284}{157762} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 4}{15 + 7762} \\ \frac{284}{1577762} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 4}{15 + 77762} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{284}{781} &:= \frac{28 + 4}{7 + 81} \\ \frac{284}{7881} &:= \frac{28 + 4}{7 + 881} \\ \frac{284}{78881} &:= \frac{28 + 4}{7 + 8881} \\ \frac{284}{788881} &:= \frac{28 + 4}{7 + 88881} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 285**

$$\frac{285}{1045} := \frac{2+8+5}{10+45}$$

$$\frac{285}{10545} := \frac{2+8+5}{10+545}$$

$$\frac{285}{105545} := \frac{2+8+5}{10+5545}$$

$$\frac{285}{1055545} := \frac{2+8+5}{10+55545}$$

$$\frac{285}{1254} := \frac{2+8+5}{12+54}$$

$$\frac{285}{12654} := \frac{2+8+5}{12+654}$$

$$\frac{285}{126654} := \frac{2+8+5}{12+6654}$$

$$\frac{285}{1266654} := \frac{2+8+5}{12+66654}$$

$$\frac{285}{1463} := \frac{2+8+5}{14+63}$$

$$\frac{285}{14763} := \frac{2+8+5}{14+763}$$

$$\frac{285}{147763} := \frac{2+8+5}{14+7763}$$

$$\frac{285}{1477763} := \frac{2+8+5}{14+77763}$$

$$\frac{285}{418} := \frac{2+8+5}{4+18}$$

$$\frac{285}{4218} := \frac{2+8+5}{4+218}$$

$$\frac{285}{42218} := \frac{2+8+5}{4+2218}$$

$$\frac{285}{422218} := \frac{2+8+5}{4+22218}$$

$$\frac{285}{627} := \frac{2+8+5}{6+27}$$

$$\frac{285}{6327} := \frac{2+8+5}{6+327}$$

$$\frac{285}{63327} := \frac{2+8+5}{6+3327}$$

$$\frac{285}{633327} := \frac{2+8+5}{6+33327}$$

$$\frac{285}{836} := \frac{2+8+5}{8+36}$$

$$\frac{285}{8436} := \frac{2+8+5}{8+436}$$

$$\frac{285}{84436} := \frac{2+8+5}{8+4436}$$

$$\frac{285}{844436} := \frac{2+8+5}{8+44436}$$

• **Number 286**

$$\frac{286}{1287} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{12 + 87}$$

$$\frac{286}{12987} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{12 + 987}$$

$$\frac{286}{129987} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{12 + 9987}$$

$$\frac{286}{1299987} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{12 + 99987}$$

$$\frac{286}{1443} := \frac{2+86}{1+443}$$

$$\frac{286}{14443} := \frac{2+86}{1+4443}$$

$$\frac{286}{144443} := \frac{2+86}{1+44443}$$

$$\frac{286}{1444443} := \frac{2+86}{1+444443}$$

$$\frac{286}{1573} := \frac{2+8+6}{15+73}$$

$$\frac{286}{15873} := \frac{2+8+6}{15+873}$$

$$\frac{286}{158873} := \frac{2+8+6}{15+8873}$$

$$\frac{286}{1588873} := \frac{2+8+6}{15+88873}$$

$$\frac{286}{429} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{4 + 29}$$

$$\frac{286}{4329} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{4 + 329}$$

$$\frac{286}{43329} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{4 + 3329}$$

$$\frac{286}{433329} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{4 + 33329}$$

$$\frac{286}{858} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{8 + 58}$$

$$\frac{286}{8658} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{8 + 658}$$

$$\frac{286}{86658} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{8 + 6658}$$

$$\frac{286}{866658} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{8 + 66658}$$

● **Number 287**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{287}{451} &:= \frac{28+7}{4+51} \\ \frac{287}{4551} &:= \frac{28+7}{4+551} \\ \frac{287}{45551} &:= \frac{28+7}{4+5551} \\ \frac{287}{455551} &:= \frac{28+7}{4+55551} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 288**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{288}{1056} &:= \frac{2+8+8}{10+56} \\ \frac{288}{10656} &:= \frac{2+8+8}{10+656} \\ \frac{288}{106656} &:= \frac{2+8+8}{10+6656} \\ \frac{288}{1066656} &:= \frac{2+8+8}{10+66656} \\ \frac{288}{528} &:= \frac{2+8+8}{5+28} \\ \frac{288}{5328} &:= \frac{2+8+8}{5+328} \\ \frac{288}{53328} &:= \frac{2+8+8}{5+3328} \\ \frac{288}{533328} &:= \frac{2+8+8}{5+33328} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 289**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{289}{561} &:= \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{5+61} \\ \frac{289}{5661} &:= \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{5+661} \\ \frac{289}{56661} &:= \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{5+6661} \\ \frac{289}{566661} &:= \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{5+66661} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 303**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{303}{1111} &:= \frac{3+03}{11+11} \\ \frac{303}{11211} &:= \frac{3+03}{11+211} \\ \frac{303}{112211} &:= \frac{3+03}{11+2211} \\ \frac{303}{1122211} &:= \frac{3+03}{11+22211} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 305**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{305}{671} &:= \frac{30+5}{6+71} \\ \frac{305}{6771} &:= \frac{30+5}{6+771} \\ \frac{305}{67771} &:= \frac{30+5}{6+7771} \\ \frac{305}{677771} &:= \frac{30+5}{6+77771} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 306**

$\begin{aligned} \frac{306}{1122} &:= \frac{3+06}{11+22} \\ \frac{306}{11322} &:= \frac{3+06}{11+322} \\ \frac{306}{113322} &:= \frac{3+06}{11+3322} \\ \frac{306}{1133322} &:= \frac{3+06}{11+33322} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \frac{306}{1683} &:= \frac{3 \times 06}{16+83} \\ \frac{306}{16983} &:= \frac{3 \times 06}{16+983} \\ \frac{306}{169983} &:= \frac{3 \times 06}{16+9983} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \frac{306}{561} &:= \frac{30+6}{5+61} \\ \frac{306}{5661} &:= \frac{30+6}{5+661} \\ \frac{306}{56661} &:= \frac{30+6}{5+6661} \end{aligned}$
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● **Number 308**

$\begin{aligned} \frac{308}{1232} &:= \frac{3+08}{12+32} \\ \frac{308}{12432} &:= \frac{3+08}{12+432} \\ \frac{308}{124432} &:= \frac{3+08}{12+4432} \\ \frac{308}{1244432} &:= \frac{3+08}{12+44432} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \frac{308}{616} &:= \frac{3+08}{6+16} \\ \frac{308}{6216} &:= \frac{3+08}{6+216} \\ \frac{308}{62216} &:= \frac{3+08}{6+2216} \\ \frac{308}{622216} &:= \frac{3+08}{6+22216} \end{aligned}$
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● **Number 309**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{309}{1133} &:= \frac{3+09}{11+33} \\ \frac{309}{11433} &:= \frac{3+09}{11+433} \\ \frac{309}{114433} &:= \frac{3+09}{11+4433} \\ \frac{309}{1144433} &:= \frac{3+09}{11+44433} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 310**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{310}{1705} &:= \frac{3+1+0}{17+05} \\ \frac{310}{17205} &:= \frac{3+1+0}{17+205} \\ \frac{310}{172205} &:= \frac{3+1+0}{17+2205} \\ \frac{310}{1722205} &:= \frac{3+1+0}{17+22205} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 312**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{312}{1144} &:= \frac{3+12}{11+44} \\ \frac{312}{11544} &:= \frac{3+12}{11+544} \\ \frac{312}{115544} &:= \frac{3+12}{11+5544} \\ \frac{312}{1155544} &:= \frac{3+12}{11+55544} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 312**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{314}{1727} &:= \frac{3+1+4}{17+27} \\ \frac{314}{17427} &:= \frac{3+1+4}{17+427} \\ \frac{314}{174427} &:= \frac{3+1+4}{17+4427} \\ \frac{314}{1744427} &:= \frac{3+1+4}{17+44427} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 315**

$\begin{aligned} \frac{315}{462} &:= \frac{3 \times 15}{4+62} \\ \frac{315}{4662} &:= \frac{3 \times 15}{4+662} \\ \frac{315}{46662} &:= \frac{3 \times 15}{4+6662} \\ \frac{315}{466662} &:= \frac{3 \times 15}{4+66662} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \frac{315}{693} &:= \frac{3 \times 15}{6+93} \\ \frac{315}{6993} &:= \frac{3 \times 15}{6+993} \\ \frac{315}{69993} &:= \frac{3 \times 15}{6+9993} \\ \frac{315}{699993} &:= \frac{3 \times 15}{6+99993} \end{aligned}$
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• **Number 316**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{316}{1738} &:= \frac{3+1+6}{17+38} \\ \frac{316}{17538} &:= \frac{3+1+6}{17+538} \\ \frac{316}{175538} &:= \frac{3+1+6}{17+5538} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 318**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{318}{1166} &:= \frac{3+18}{11+66} \\ \frac{318}{11766} &:= \frac{3+18}{11+766} \\ \frac{318}{117766} &:= \frac{3+18}{11+7766} \\ \frac{318}{1177766} &:= \frac{3+18}{11+77766} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{318}{1749} &:= \frac{3+1+8}{17+49} \\ \frac{318}{17649} &:= \frac{3+1+8}{17+649} \\ \frac{318}{176649} &:= \frac{3+1+8}{17+6649} \\ \frac{318}{1766649} &:= \frac{3+1+8}{17+66649} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 319**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{319}{1276} &:= \frac{3+19}{12+76} \\ \frac{319}{12876} &:= \frac{3+19}{12+876} \\ \frac{319}{128876} &:= \frac{3+19}{12+8876} \\ \frac{319}{1288876} &:= \frac{3+19}{12+88876} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{319}{638} &:= \frac{3+19}{6+38} \\ \frac{319}{6438} &:= \frac{3+19}{6+438} \\ \frac{319}{64438} &:= \frac{3+19}{6+4438} \\ \frac{319}{644438} &:= \frac{3+19}{6+44438} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{319}{957} &:= \frac{3+19}{9+57} \\ \frac{319}{9657} &:= \frac{3+19}{9+657} \\ \frac{319}{96657} &:= \frac{3+19}{9+6657} \\ \frac{319}{966657} &:= \frac{3+19}{9+66657} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 320**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{320}{704} &:= \frac{3+2+0}{7+04} \\ \frac{320}{7104} &:= \frac{3+2+0}{7+104} \\ \frac{320}{71104} &:= \frac{3+2+0}{7+1104} \\ \frac{320}{711104} &:= \frac{3+2+0}{7+11104} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 321**

$$\frac{321}{1177} := \frac{3 + 21}{11 + 77}$$

$$\frac{321}{11877} := \frac{3 + 21}{11 + 877}$$

$$\frac{321}{118877} := \frac{3 + 21}{11 + 8877}$$

$$\frac{321}{1188877} := \frac{3 + 21}{11 + 88877}$$

● **Number 322**

$$\frac{322}{1012} := \frac{3 + 2^2}{10 + 12}$$

$$\frac{322}{10212} := \frac{3 + 2^2}{10 + 212}$$

$$\frac{322}{102212} := \frac{3 + 2^2}{10 + 2212}$$

$$\frac{322}{1022212} := \frac{3 + 2^2}{10 + 22212}$$

$$\frac{322}{506} := \frac{3 + 2^2}{5 + 06}$$

$$\frac{322}{5106} := \frac{3 + 2^2}{5 + 106}$$

$$\frac{322}{51106} := \frac{3 + 2^2}{5 + 1106}$$

$$\frac{322}{511106} := \frac{3 + 2^2}{5 + 11106}$$

● **Number 324**

$$\frac{324}{1188} := \frac{3 + 24}{11 + 88}$$

$$\frac{324}{11988} := \frac{3 + 24}{11 + 988}$$

$$\frac{324}{119988} := \frac{3 + 24}{11 + 9988}$$

$$\frac{324}{1199988} := \frac{3 + 24}{11 + 99988}$$

$$\frac{324}{1782} := \frac{3 \times (2 + 4)}{17 + 82}$$

$$\frac{324}{17982} := \frac{3 \times (2 + 4)}{17 + 982}$$

$$\frac{324}{179982} := \frac{3 \times (2 + 4)}{17 + 9982}$$

$$\frac{324}{1799982} := \frac{3 \times (2 + 4)}{17 + 99982}$$

● **Number 325**

$$\frac{325}{1430} := \frac{3 + 2 + 5}{1 + 43 + 0}$$

$$\frac{325}{14430} := \frac{3 + 2 + 5}{1 + 443 + 0}$$

$$\frac{325}{144430} := \frac{3 + 2 + 5}{1 + 4443 + 0}$$

$$\frac{325}{1444430} := \frac{3 + 2 + 5}{1 + 44443 + 0}$$

$$\frac{325}{429} := \frac{(3 + 2) \times 5}{4 + 29}$$

$$\frac{325}{4329} := \frac{(3 + 2) \times 5}{4 + 329}$$

$$\frac{325}{43329} := \frac{(3 + 2) \times 5}{4 + 3329}$$

$$\frac{325}{433329} := \frac{(3 + 2) \times 5}{4 + 33329}$$

$$\frac{325}{715} := \frac{3 + 2 + 5}{7 + 15}$$

$$\frac{325}{7215} := \frac{3 + 2 + 5}{7 + 215}$$

$$\frac{325}{72215} := \frac{3 + 2 + 5}{7 + 2215}$$

$$\frac{325}{722215} := \frac{3 + 2 + 5}{7 + 22215}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{325}{825} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{8+25} \\ \frac{325}{8325} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{8+325} \\ \frac{325}{83325} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{8+3325} \\ \frac{325}{833325} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{8+33325} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{325}{858} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{8+58} \\ \frac{325}{8658} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{8+658} \\ \frac{325}{86658} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{8+6658} \\ \frac{325}{866658} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{8+66658} \end{array}$$

● **Number 328**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{328}{451} := \frac{32+8}{4+51} \\ \frac{328}{4551} := \frac{32+8}{4+551} \\ \frac{328}{45551} := \frac{32+8}{4+5551} \\ \frac{328}{455551} := \frac{32+8}{4+55551} \end{array}$$

● **Number 329**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{329}{1034} := \frac{3+2+9}{10+34} \\ \frac{329}{10434} := \frac{3+2+9}{10+434} \\ \frac{329}{104434} := \frac{3+2+9}{10+4434} \\ \frac{329}{1044434} := \frac{3+2+9}{10+44434} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{329}{1551} := \frac{3+2+9}{15+51} \\ \frac{329}{15651} := \frac{3+2+9}{15+651} \\ \frac{329}{156651} := \frac{3+2+9}{15+6651} \\ \frac{329}{1566651} := \frac{3+2+9}{15+66651} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{329}{517} := \frac{3+2+9}{5+17} \\ \frac{329}{5217} := \frac{3+2+9}{5+217} \\ \frac{329}{52217} := \frac{3+2+9}{5+2217} \\ \frac{329}{522217} := \frac{3+2+9}{5+22217} \end{array}$$

● **Number 330**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{330}{1155} := \frac{3+3+0}{1+15+5} \\ \frac{330}{12155} := \frac{3+3+0}{1+215+5} \\ \frac{330}{122155} := \frac{3+3+0}{1+2215+5} \\ \frac{330}{1222155} := \frac{3+3+0}{1+22215+5} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{330}{605} := \frac{3+3+0}{6+05} \\ \frac{330}{6105} := \frac{3+3+0}{6+105} \\ \frac{330}{61105} := \frac{3+3+0}{6+1105} \\ \frac{330}{611105} := \frac{3+3+0}{6+11105} \end{array}$$

● **Number 332**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{332}{1826} &:= \frac{3+3+2}{18+26} \\ \frac{332}{18426} &:= \frac{3+3+2}{18+426} \\ \frac{332}{184426} &:= \frac{3+3+2}{18+4426} \\ \frac{332}{1844426} &:= \frac{3+3+2}{18+44426} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{332}{913} &:= \frac{3+3+2}{9+13} \\ \frac{332}{9213} &:= \frac{3+3+2}{9+213} \\ \frac{332}{92213} &:= \frac{3+3+2}{9+2213} \\ \frac{332}{922213} &:= \frac{3+3+2}{9+22213} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 333**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{333}{1221} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{12+21} \\ \frac{333}{12321} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{12+321} \\ \frac{333}{123321} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{12+3321} \\ \frac{333}{1233321} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{12+33321} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{333}{407} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{4+07} \\ \frac{333}{4107} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{4+107} \\ \frac{333}{41107} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{4+1107} \\ \frac{333}{411107} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{4+11107} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{333}{814} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{8+14} \\ \frac{333}{8214} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{8+214} \\ \frac{333}{82214} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{8+2214} \\ \frac{333}{822214} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{8+22214} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 334**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{334}{1837} &:= \frac{3+3+4}{18+37} \\ \frac{334}{18537} &:= \frac{3+3+4}{18+537} \\ \frac{334}{185537} &:= \frac{3+3+4}{18+5537} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 336**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{336}{1056} &:= \frac{3+3 \times 6}{10+56} \\ \frac{336}{10656} &:= \frac{3+3 \times 6}{10+656} \\ \frac{336}{106656} &:= \frac{3+3 \times 6}{10+6656} \\ \frac{336}{1066656} &:= \frac{3+3 \times 6}{10+66656} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{336}{1232} &:= \frac{3+3+6}{12+32} \\ \frac{336}{12432} &:= \frac{3+3+6}{12+432} \\ \frac{336}{124432} &:= \frac{3+3+6}{12+4432} \\ \frac{336}{1244432} &:= \frac{3+3+6}{12+44432} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{336}{1584} &:= \frac{3+3 \times 6}{15+84} \\ \frac{336}{15984} &:= \frac{3+3 \times 6}{15+984} \\ \frac{336}{159984} &:= \frac{3+3 \times 6}{15+9984} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{336}{1848} &:= \frac{3+3+6}{18+48} \\ \frac{336}{18648} &:= \frac{3+3+6}{18+648} \\ \frac{336}{186648} &:= \frac{3+3+6}{18+6648} \\ \frac{336}{1866648} &:= \frac{3+3+6}{18+66648} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{336}{616} &:= \frac{3+3+6}{6+16} \\ \frac{336}{6216} &:= \frac{3+3+6}{6+216} \\ \frac{336}{62216} &:= \frac{3+3+6}{6+2216} \\ \frac{336}{622216} &:= \frac{3+3+6}{6+22216} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{336}{924} &:= \frac{3+3+6}{9+24} \\ \frac{336}{9324} &:= \frac{3+3+6}{9+324} \\ \frac{336}{93324} &:= \frac{3+3+6}{9+3324} \\ \frac{336}{933324} &:= \frac{3+3+6}{9+33324} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 339**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{339}{1243} &:= \frac{3+3+9}{12+43} \\ \frac{339}{12543} &:= \frac{3+3+9}{12+543} \\ \frac{339}{125543} &:= \frac{3+3+9}{12+5543} \\ \frac{339}{1255543} &:= \frac{3+3+9}{12+55543} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 341**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{341}{682} &:= \frac{3+41}{6+82} \\ \frac{341}{6882} &:= \frac{3+41}{6+882} \\ \frac{341}{68882} &:= \frac{3+41}{6+8882} \\ \frac{341}{688882} &:= \frac{3+41}{6+88882} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 342**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{342}{1045} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{10+45} \\ \frac{342}{10545} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{10+545} \\ \frac{342}{105545} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{10+5545} \\ \frac{342}{1055545} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{10+55545} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{342}{1254} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{12+54} \\ \frac{342}{12654} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{12+654} \\ \frac{342}{126654} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{12+6654} \\ \frac{342}{1266654} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{12+66654} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{342}{1463} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{14+63} \\ \frac{342}{14763} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{14+763} \\ \frac{342}{147763} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{14+7763} \\ \frac{342}{1477763} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{14+77763} \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{342}{1672} := \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{16 + 72}$$

$$\frac{342}{16872} := \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{16 + 872}$$

$$\frac{342}{168872} := \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{16 + 8872}$$

$$\frac{342}{1688872} := \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{16 + 88872}$$

$$\frac{342}{1881} := \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{18 + 81}$$

$$\frac{342}{18981} := \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{18 + 981}$$

$$\frac{342}{189981} := \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{18 + 9981}$$

$$\frac{342}{1899981} := \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{18 + 99981}$$

$$\frac{342}{418} := \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{4 + 18}$$

$$\frac{342}{4218} := \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{4 + 218}$$

$$\frac{342}{42218} := \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{4 + 2218}$$

$$\frac{342}{422218} := \frac{3 \times (4 + 2)}{4 + 22218}$$

• **Number 345**

$$\frac{345}{1485} := \frac{3 + 4 \times 5}{14 + 85}$$

$$\frac{345}{14985} := \frac{3 + 4 \times 5}{14 + 985}$$

$$\frac{345}{149985} := \frac{3 + 4 \times 5}{14 + 9985}$$

$$\frac{345}{1499985} := \frac{3 + 4 \times 5}{14 + 99985}$$

• **Number 352**

$$\frac{352}{1221} := \frac{(3 + 5)^2}{1 + 221}$$

$$\frac{352}{12221} := \frac{(3 + 5)^2}{1 + 2221}$$

$$\frac{352}{122221} := \frac{(3 + 5)^2}{1 + 22221}$$

$$\frac{352}{1222221} := \frac{(3 + 5)^2}{1 + 222221}$$

$$\frac{352}{363} := \frac{(3 + 5)^2}{3 + 63}$$

$$\frac{352}{3663} := \frac{(3 + 5)^2}{3 + 663}$$

$$\frac{352}{36663} := \frac{(3 + 5)^2}{3 + 6663}$$

$$\frac{352}{366663} := \frac{(3 + 5)^2}{3 + 66663}$$

$$\frac{352}{484} := \frac{(3 + 5)^2}{4 + 84}$$

$$\frac{352}{4884} := \frac{(3 + 5)^2}{4 + 884}$$

$$\frac{352}{48884} := \frac{(3 + 5)^2}{4 + 8884}$$

$$\frac{352}{488884} := \frac{(3 + 5)^2}{4 + 88884}$$

• **Number 355**

$$\frac{355}{781} := \frac{35 + 5}{7 + 81}$$

$$\frac{355}{7881} := \frac{35 + 5}{7 + 881}$$

$$\frac{355}{78881} := \frac{35 + 5}{7 + 8881}$$

$$\frac{355}{788881} := \frac{35 + 5}{7 + 88881}$$

● **Number 357**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{357}{561} &:= \frac{35+7}{5+61} \\ \frac{357}{5661} &:= \frac{35+7}{5+661} \\ \frac{357}{56661} &:= \frac{35+7}{5+6661} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 361**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{361}{1463} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{14 + 63} \\ \frac{361}{14763} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{14 + 763} \\ \frac{361}{147763} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{14 + 7763} \\ \frac{361}{1477763} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{14 + 77763} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{361}{1672} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{16 + 72} \\ \frac{361}{16872} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{16 + 872} \\ \frac{361}{168872} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{16 + 8872} \\ \frac{361}{1688872} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{16 + 88872} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{361}{627} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{6 + 27} \\ \frac{361}{6327} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{6 + 327} \\ \frac{361}{63327} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{6 + 3327} \\ \frac{361}{633327} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{6 + 33327} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{361}{836} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{8 + 36} \\ \frac{361}{8436} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{8 + 436} \\ \frac{361}{84436} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{8 + 4436} \\ \frac{361}{844436} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{8 + 44436} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{363}{1221} &:= \frac{3 + 63}{1 + 221} \\ \frac{363}{12221} &:= \frac{3 + 63}{1 + 2221} \\ \frac{363}{122221} &:= \frac{3 + 63}{1 + 22221} \\ \frac{363}{1222221} &:= \frac{3 + 63}{1 + 222221} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 363**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{363}{1331} &:= \frac{3 + 6 + 3}{13 + 31} \\ \frac{363}{13431} &:= \frac{3 + 6 + 3}{13 + 431} \\ \frac{363}{134431} &:= \frac{3 + 6 + 3}{13 + 4431} \\ \frac{363}{1344431} &:= \frac{3 + 6 + 3}{13 + 44431} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{363}{484} &:= \frac{3 + 63}{4 + 84} \\ \frac{363}{4884} &:= \frac{3 + 63}{4 + 884} \\ \frac{363}{48884} &:= \frac{3 + 63}{4 + 8884} \\ \frac{363}{488884} &:= \frac{3 + 63}{4 + 88884} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 364**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{364}{1232} &:= \frac{3+6+4}{12+32} \\ \frac{364}{12432} &:= \frac{3+6+4}{12+432} \\ \frac{364}{124432} &:= \frac{3+6+4}{12+4432} \\ \frac{364}{1244432} &:= \frac{3+6+4}{12+44432} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{364}{616} &:= \frac{3+6+4}{6+16} \\ \frac{364}{6216} &:= \frac{3+6+4}{6+216} \\ \frac{364}{62216} &:= \frac{3+6+4}{6+2216} \\ \frac{364}{622216} &:= \frac{3+6+4}{6+22216} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{364}{924} &:= \frac{3+6+4}{9+24} \\ \frac{364}{9324} &:= \frac{3+6+4}{9+324} \\ \frac{364}{93324} &:= \frac{3+6+4}{9+3324} \\ \frac{364}{933324} &:= \frac{3+6+4}{9+33324} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 366**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{366}{1342} &:= \frac{3+6+6}{13+42} \\ \frac{366}{13542} &:= \frac{3+6+6}{13+542} \\ \frac{366}{135542} &:= \frac{3+6+6}{13+5542} \\ \frac{366}{1355542} &:= \frac{3+6+6}{13+55542} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{366}{671} &:= \frac{36+6}{6+71} \\ \frac{366}{6771} &:= \frac{36+6}{6+771} \\ \frac{366}{67771} &:= \frac{36+6}{6+7771} \\ \frac{366}{677771} &:= \frac{36+6}{6+77771} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 369**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{369}{1353} &:= \frac{3+6+9}{13+53} \\ \frac{369}{13653} &:= \frac{3+6+9}{13+653} \\ \frac{369}{136653} &:= \frac{3+6+9}{13+6653} \\ \frac{369}{1366653} &:= \frac{3+6+9}{13+66653} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{369}{451} &:= \frac{3 \times (6+9)}{4+51} \\ \frac{369}{4551} &:= \frac{3 \times (6+9)}{4+551} \\ \frac{369}{45551} &:= \frac{3 \times (6+9)}{4+5551} \\ \frac{369}{455551} &:= \frac{3 \times (6+9)}{4+55551} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 370**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{370}{407} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{4+07} \\ \frac{370}{4107} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{4+107} \\ \frac{370}{41107} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{4+1107} \\ \frac{370}{411107} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{4+11107} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{370}{814} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{8+14} \\ \frac{370}{8214} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{8+214} \\ \frac{370}{82214} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{8+2214} \\ \frac{370}{822214} &:= \frac{3+7+0}{8+22214} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 372**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{372}{1023} &:= \frac{3+7+2}{10+23} \\ \frac{372}{10323} &:= \frac{3+7+2}{10+323} \\ \frac{372}{103323} &:= \frac{3+7+2}{10+3323} \\ \frac{372}{1033323} &:= \frac{3+7+2}{10+33323} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 375**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{375}{825} &:= \frac{3+7+5}{8+25} \\ \frac{375}{8325} &:= \frac{3+7+5}{8+325} \\ \frac{375}{83325} &:= \frac{3+7+5}{8+3325} \\ \frac{375}{833325} &:= \frac{3+7+5}{8+33325} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 376**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{376}{1034} &:= \frac{3+7+6}{10+34} & \frac{376}{1551} &:= \frac{3+7+6}{15+51} & \frac{376}{517} &:= \frac{3+7+6}{5+17} \\ \frac{376}{10434} &:= \frac{3+7+6}{10+434} & \frac{376}{15651} &:= \frac{3+7+6}{15+651} & \frac{376}{5217} &:= \frac{3+7+6}{5+217} \\ \frac{376}{104434} &:= \frac{3+7+6}{10+4434} & \frac{376}{156651} &:= \frac{3+7+6}{15+6651} & \frac{376}{52217} &:= \frac{3+7+6}{5+2217} \\ \frac{376}{1044434} &:= \frac{3+7+6}{10+44434} & \frac{376}{1566651} &:= \frac{3+7+6}{15+66651} & \frac{376}{522217} &:= \frac{3+7+6}{5+22217} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 384**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{384}{1332} &:= \frac{3 \times 8 \times 4}{1+332} & \frac{384}{396} &:= \frac{3 \times 8 \times 4}{3+96} \\ \frac{384}{13332} &:= \frac{3 \times 8 \times 4}{1+3332} & \frac{384}{3996} &:= \frac{3 \times 8 \times 4}{3+996} \\ \frac{384}{133332} &:= \frac{3 \times 8 \times 4}{1+33332} & \frac{384}{39996} &:= \frac{3 \times 8 \times 4}{3+9996} \\ \frac{384}{1333332} &:= \frac{3 \times 8 \times 4}{1+333332} & \frac{384}{399996} &:= \frac{3 \times 8 \times 4}{3+99996} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 385**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{385}{462} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{4+62} \\ \frac{385}{4662} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{4+662} \\ \frac{385}{46662} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{4+6662} \\ \frac{385}{466662} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{4+66662} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{385}{693} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{6+93} \\ \frac{385}{6993} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{6+993} \\ \frac{385}{69993} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{6+9993} \\ \frac{385}{699993} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{6+99993} \end{array}$$

● **Number 390**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{390}{1365} := \frac{3+9+0}{1+36+5} \\ \frac{390}{14365} := \frac{3+9+0}{1+436+5} \\ \frac{390}{144365} := \frac{3+9+0}{1+4436+5} \\ \frac{390}{1444365} := \frac{3+9+0}{1+44436+5} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{390}{715} := \frac{3+9+0}{7+15} \\ \frac{390}{7215} := \frac{3+9+0}{7+215} \\ \frac{390}{72215} := \frac{3+9+0}{7+2215} \\ \frac{390}{722215} := \frac{3+9+0}{7+22215} \end{array}$$

● **Number 392**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{392}{1232} := \frac{3+9+2}{12+32} \\ \frac{392}{12432} := \frac{3+9+2}{12+432} \\ \frac{392}{124432} := \frac{3+9+2}{12+4432} \\ \frac{392}{1244432} := \frac{3+9+2}{12+44432} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{392}{1512} := \frac{3+9+2}{1+51+2} \\ \frac{392}{15512} := \frac{3+9+2}{1+551+2} \\ \frac{392}{155512} := \frac{3+9+2}{1+5551+2} \\ \frac{392}{1555512} := \frac{3+9+2}{1+55551+2} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{392}{616} := \frac{3+9+2}{6+16} \\ \frac{392}{6216} := \frac{3+9+2}{6+216} \\ \frac{392}{62216} := \frac{3+9+2}{6+2216} \\ \frac{392}{622216} := \frac{3+9+2}{6+22216} \end{array}$$

● **Number 393**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{393}{1441} := \frac{3+9+3}{14+41} \\ \frac{393}{14541} := \frac{3+9+3}{14+541} \\ \frac{393}{145541} := \frac{3+9+3}{14+5541} \\ \frac{393}{1455541} := \frac{3+9+3}{14+55541} \end{array}$$

● **Number 396**

$$\frac{396}{1221} := \frac{(3+9) \times 6}{1+221}$$

$$\frac{396}{12221} := \frac{(3+9) \times 6}{1+2221}$$

$$\frac{396}{122221} := \frac{(3+9) \times 6}{1+22221}$$

$$\frac{396}{1222221} := \frac{(3+9) \times 6}{1+222221}$$

$$\frac{396}{1332} := \frac{3+96}{1+332}$$

$$\frac{396}{13332} := \frac{3+96}{1+3332}$$

$$\frac{396}{133332} := \frac{3+96}{1+33332}$$

$$\frac{396}{1333332} := \frac{3+96}{1+333332}$$

$$\frac{396}{1452} := \frac{3+9+6}{14+52}$$

$$\frac{396}{14652} := \frac{3+9+6}{14+652}$$

$$\frac{396}{146652} := \frac{3+9+6}{14+6652}$$

$$\frac{396}{1466652} := \frac{3+9+6}{14+66652}$$

$$\frac{396}{484} := \frac{(3+9) \times 6}{4+84}$$

$$\frac{396}{4884} := \frac{(3+9) \times 6}{4+884}$$

$$\frac{396}{48884} := \frac{(3+9) \times 6}{4+8884}$$

$$\frac{396}{488884} := \frac{(3+9) \times 6}{4+88884}$$

$$\frac{396}{726} := \frac{3+9+6}{7+26}$$

$$\frac{396}{7326} := \frac{3+9+6}{7+326}$$

$$\frac{396}{73326} := \frac{3+9+6}{7+3326}$$

$$\frac{396}{733326} := \frac{3+9+6}{7+33326}$$

● **Number 399**

$$\frac{399}{1045} := \frac{3+9+9}{10+45}$$

$$\frac{399}{10545} := \frac{3+9+9}{10+545}$$

$$\frac{399}{105545} := \frac{3+9+9}{10+5545}$$

$$\frac{399}{1055545} := \frac{3+9+9}{10+55545}$$

$$\frac{399}{1463} := \frac{3+9+9}{14+63}$$

$$\frac{399}{14763} := \frac{3+9+9}{14+763}$$

$$\frac{399}{147763} := \frac{3+9+9}{14+7763}$$

$$\frac{399}{1477763} := \frac{3+9+9}{14+77763}$$

$$\frac{399}{418} := \frac{3+9+9}{4+18}$$

$$\frac{399}{4218} := \frac{3+9+9}{4+218}$$

$$\frac{399}{42218} := \frac{3+9+9}{4+2218}$$

$$\frac{399}{422218} := \frac{3+9+9}{4+22218}$$

$$\frac{399}{627} := \frac{3+9+9}{6+27}$$

$$\frac{399}{6327} := \frac{3+9+9}{6+327}$$

$$\frac{399}{63327} := \frac{3+9+9}{6+3327}$$

$$\frac{399}{633327} := \frac{3+9+9}{6+33327}$$

$$\frac{399}{836} := \frac{3+9+9}{8+36}$$

$$\frac{399}{8436} := \frac{3+9+9}{8+436}$$

$$\frac{399}{84436} := \frac{3+9+9}{8+4436}$$

$$\frac{399}{844436} := \frac{3+9+9}{8+44436}$$

● **Number 404**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{404}{1111} &:= \frac{4 + 04}{11 + 11} \\ \frac{404}{11211} &:= \frac{4 + 04}{11 + 211} \\ \frac{404}{112211} &:= \frac{4 + 04}{11 + 2211} \\ \frac{404}{1122211} &:= \frac{4 + 04}{11 + 22211} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 405**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{405}{891} &:= \frac{40 + 5}{8 + 91} \\ \frac{405}{8991} &:= \frac{40 + 5}{8 + 991} \\ \frac{405}{89991} &:= \frac{40 + 5}{8 + 9991} \\ \frac{405}{899991} &:= \frac{40 + 5}{8 + 99991} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 407**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{407}{1221} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{12 + 21} \\ \frac{407}{12321} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{12 + 321} \\ \frac{407}{123321} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{12 + 3321} \\ \frac{407}{1233321} &:= \frac{4 + 07}{12 + 33321} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 408**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{408}{1122} &:= \frac{4 + 08}{11 + 22} \\ \frac{408}{11322} &:= \frac{4 + 08}{11 + 322} \\ \frac{408}{113322} &:= \frac{4 + 08}{11 + 3322} \\ \frac{408}{1133322} &:= \frac{4 + 08}{11 + 33322} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{408}{561} &:= \frac{40 + 8}{5 + 61} \\ \frac{408}{5661} &:= \frac{40 + 8}{5 + 661} \\ \frac{408}{56661} &:= \frac{40 + 8}{5 + 6661} \\ \frac{408}{566661} &:= \frac{40 + 8}{5 + 66661} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 410**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{410}{1804} := \frac{4+1+0}{18+04} \\ \frac{410}{18204} := \frac{4+1+0}{18+204} \\ \frac{410}{182204} := \frac{4+1+0}{18+2204} \\ \frac{410}{1822204} := \frac{4+1+0}{18+22204} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{410}{902} := \frac{4+1+0}{9+02} \\ \frac{410}{9102} := \frac{4+1+0}{9+102} \\ \frac{410}{91102} := \frac{4+1+0}{9+1102} \\ \frac{410}{911102} := \frac{4+1+0}{9+11102} \end{array}$$

• **Number 411**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{411}{1507} := \frac{4+1+1}{15+07} \\ \frac{411}{15207} := \frac{4+1+1}{15+207} \\ \frac{411}{152207} := \frac{4+1+1}{15+2207} \\ \frac{411}{1522207} := \frac{4+1+1}{15+22207} \end{array}$$

• **Number 412**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{412}{1133} := \frac{4+12}{11+33} \\ \frac{412}{11433} := \frac{4+12}{11+433} \\ \frac{412}{114433} := \frac{4+12}{11+4433} \\ \frac{412}{1144433} := \frac{4+12}{11+44433} \end{array}$$

• **Number 414**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{414}{506} := \frac{4+1+4}{5+06} \\ \frac{414}{5106} := \frac{4+1+4}{5+106} \\ \frac{414}{51106} := \frac{4+1+4}{5+1106} \\ \frac{414}{511106} := \frac{4+1+4}{5+11106} \end{array}$$

• **Number 415**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{415}{1826} := \frac{4+1+5}{18+26} \\ \frac{415}{18426} := \frac{4+1+5}{18+426} \\ \frac{415}{184426} := \frac{4+1+5}{18+4426} \\ \frac{415}{1844426} := \frac{4+1+5}{18+44426} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{415}{913} := \frac{4+1+5}{9+13} \\ \frac{415}{9213} := \frac{4+1+5}{9+213} \\ \frac{415}{92213} := \frac{4+1+5}{9+2213} \\ \frac{415}{922213} := \frac{4+1+5}{9+22213} \end{array}$$

● **Number 416**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{416}{1144} := \frac{4+16}{11+44} \\ \frac{416}{11544} := \frac{4+16}{11+544} \\ \frac{416}{115544} := \frac{4+16}{11+5544} \\ \frac{416}{1155544} := \frac{4+16}{11+55544} \end{array}$$

● **Number 417**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{417}{1529} := \frac{4+1+7}{15+29} \\ \frac{417}{15429} := \frac{4+1+7}{15+429} \\ \frac{417}{154429} := \frac{4+1+7}{15+4429} \\ \frac{417}{1544429} := \frac{4+1+7}{15+44429} \end{array}$$

● **Number 418**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{418}{1045} := \frac{4+18}{10+45} \\ \frac{418}{10545} := \frac{4+18}{10+545} \\ \frac{418}{105545} := \frac{4+18}{10+5545} \\ \frac{418}{1055545} := \frac{4+18}{10+55545} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{418}{1254} := \frac{4+18}{12+54} \\ \frac{418}{12654} := \frac{4+18}{12+654} \\ \frac{418}{126654} := \frac{4+18}{12+6654} \\ \frac{418}{1266654} := \frac{4+18}{12+66654} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{418}{1463} := \frac{4+18}{14+63} \\ \frac{418}{14763} := \frac{4+18}{14+763} \\ \frac{418}{147763} := \frac{4+18}{14+7763} \\ \frac{418}{1477763} := \frac{4+18}{14+77763} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{418}{1672} := \frac{4+18}{16+72} \\ \frac{418}{16872} := \frac{4+18}{16+872} \\ \frac{418}{168872} := \frac{4+18}{16+8872} \\ \frac{418}{1688872} := \frac{4+18}{16+88872} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{418}{1881} := \frac{4+18}{18+81} \\ \frac{418}{18981} := \frac{4+18}{18+981} \\ \frac{418}{189981} := \frac{4+18}{18+9981} \\ \frac{418}{1899981} := \frac{4+18}{18+99981} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{418}{627} := \frac{4+18}{6+27} \\ \frac{418}{6327} := \frac{4+18}{6+327} \\ \frac{418}{63327} := \frac{4+18}{6+3327} \\ \frac{418}{633327} := \frac{4+18}{6+33327} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{418}{836} := \frac{4+18}{8+36} \\ \frac{418}{8436} := \frac{4+18}{8+436} \\ \frac{418}{84436} := \frac{4+18}{8+4436} \\ \frac{418}{844436} := \frac{4+18}{8+44436} \end{array}$$

● **Number 420**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{420}{1155} := \frac{4+20}{11+55} \\ \frac{420}{11655} := \frac{4+20}{11+655} \\ \frac{420}{116655} := \frac{4+20}{11+6655} \\ \frac{420}{1166655} := \frac{4+20}{11+66655} \end{array}$$

● **Number 423**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{423}{1034} := \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{10+34} \\ \frac{423}{10434} := \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{10+434} \\ \frac{423}{104434} := \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{10+4434} \\ \frac{423}{1044434} := \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{10+44434} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{423}{1551} := \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{15+51} \\ \frac{423}{15651} := \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{15+651} \\ \frac{423}{156651} := \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{15+6651} \\ \frac{423}{1566651} := \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{15+66651} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{423}{517} := \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{5+17} \\ \frac{423}{5217} := \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{5+217} \\ \frac{423}{52217} := \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{5+2217} \\ \frac{423}{522217} := \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{5+22217} \end{array}$$

● **Number 424**

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{424}{1166} := \frac{4 + 24}{11 + 66} \\
 \frac{424}{11766} := \frac{4 + 24}{11 + 766} \\
 \frac{424}{117766} := \frac{4 + 24}{11 + 7766} \\
 \frac{424}{1177766} := \frac{4 + 24}{11 + 77766} \\
 \frac{424}{583} := \frac{4 \times 2^4}{5 + 83} \\
 \frac{424}{5883} := \frac{4 \times 2^4}{5 + 883} \\
 \frac{424}{58883} := \frac{4 \times 2^4}{5 + 8883} \\
 \frac{424}{588883} := \frac{4 \times 2^4}{5 + 88883}
 \end{array}$$

● **Number 427**

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{427}{671} := \frac{42 + 7}{6 + 71} \\
 \frac{427}{6771} := \frac{42 + 7}{6 + 771} \\
 \frac{427}{67771} := \frac{42 + 7}{6 + 7771} \\
 \frac{427}{677771} := \frac{42 + 7}{6 + 77771}
 \end{array}$$

● **Number 428**

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{428}{1177} := \frac{4 + 28}{11 + 77} \\
 \frac{428}{11877} := \frac{4 + 28}{11 + 877} \\
 \frac{428}{118877} := \frac{4 + 28}{11 + 8877} \\
 \frac{428}{1188877} := \frac{4 + 28}{11 + 88877}
 \end{array}$$

● **Number 429**

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{429}{1287} := \frac{4 + 29}{12 + 87} \\
 \frac{429}{12987} := \frac{4 + 29}{12 + 987} \\
 \frac{429}{129987} := \frac{4 + 29}{12 + 9987} \\
 \frac{429}{1299987} := \frac{4 + 29}{12 + 99987} \\
 \frac{429}{858} := \frac{4 + 29}{8 + 58} \\
 \frac{429}{8658} := \frac{4 + 29}{8 + 658} \\
 \frac{429}{86658} := \frac{4 + 29}{8 + 6658} \\
 \frac{429}{866658} := \frac{4 + 29}{8 + 66658}
 \end{array}$$

● **Number 432**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{432}{1188} &:= \frac{4 + 32}{11 + 88} \\ \frac{432}{11988} &:= \frac{4 + 32}{11 + 988} \\ \frac{432}{119988} &:= \frac{4 + 32}{11 + 9988} \\ \frac{432}{1199988} &:= \frac{4 + 32}{11 + 99988} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 440**

$\frac{440}{1155} := \frac{4 + 4 + 0}{1 + 15 + 5}$	$\frac{440}{1815} := \frac{4 + 4 + 0}{18 + 15}$	$\frac{440}{605} := \frac{4 + 4 + 0}{6 + 05}$
$\frac{440}{12155} := \frac{4 + 4 + 0}{1 + 215 + 5}$	$\frac{440}{18315} := \frac{4 + 4 + 0}{18 + 315}$	$\frac{440}{6105} := \frac{4 + 4 + 0}{6 + 105}$
$\frac{440}{122155} := \frac{4 + 4 + 0}{1 + 2215 + 5}$	$\frac{440}{183315} := \frac{4 + 4 + 0}{18 + 3315}$	$\frac{440}{61105} := \frac{4 + 4 + 0}{6 + 1105}$
$\frac{440}{1222155} := \frac{4 + 4 + 0}{1 + 22215 + 5}$	$\frac{440}{1833315} := \frac{4 + 4 + 0}{18 + 33315}$	$\frac{440}{611105} := \frac{4 + 4 + 0}{6 + 11105}$

● **Number 441**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{441}{1617} &:= \frac{4 + 4 + 1}{16 + 17} \\ \frac{441}{16317} &:= \frac{4 + 4 + 1}{16 + 317} \\ \frac{441}{163317} &:= \frac{4 + 4 + 1}{16 + 3317} \\ \frac{441}{1633317} &:= \frac{4 + 4 + 1}{16 + 33317} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 444**

$\frac{444}{1221} := \frac{4 + 4 + 4}{12 + 21}$	$\frac{444}{814} := \frac{4 + 4 + 4}{8 + 14}$
$\frac{444}{12321} := \frac{4 + 4 + 4}{12 + 321}$	$\frac{444}{8214} := \frac{4 + 4 + 4}{8 + 214}$
$\frac{444}{123321} := \frac{4 + 4 + 4}{12 + 3321}$	$\frac{444}{82214} := \frac{4 + 4 + 4}{8 + 2214}$
$\frac{444}{1233321} := \frac{4 + 4 + 4}{12 + 33321}$	$\frac{444}{822214} := \frac{4 + 4 + 4}{8 + 22214}$

● **Number 445**

$$\frac{445}{979} := \frac{(4+4) \times 5}{9+79}$$

$$\frac{445}{9879} := \frac{(4+4) \times 5}{9+879}$$

$$\frac{445}{98879} := \frac{(4+4) \times 5}{9+8879}$$

$$\frac{445}{988879} := \frac{(4+4) \times 5}{9+88879}$$

• **Number 447**

$$\frac{447}{1639} := \frac{4+4+7}{16+39}$$

$$\frac{447}{16539} := \frac{4+4+7}{16+539}$$

$$\frac{447}{165539} := \frac{4+4+7}{16+5539}$$

• **Number 448**

$$\frac{448}{1848} := \frac{4+4+8}{18+48}$$

$$\frac{448}{18648} := \frac{4+4+8}{18+648}$$

$$\frac{448}{186648} := \frac{4+4+8}{18+6648}$$

$$\frac{448}{462} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{4+62}$$

$$\frac{448}{4662} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{4+662}$$

$$\frac{448}{46662} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{4+6662}$$

$$\frac{448}{616} := \frac{4+4+8}{6+16}$$

$$\frac{448}{6216} := \frac{4+4+8}{6+216}$$

$$\frac{448}{62216} := \frac{4+4+8}{6+2216}$$

$$\frac{448}{622216} := \frac{4+4+8}{6+22216}$$

$$\frac{448}{693} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{6+93}$$

$$\frac{448}{6993} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{6+993}$$

$$\frac{448}{69993} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{6+9993}$$

• **Number 459**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{459}{561} &:= \frac{45+9}{5+61} \\ \frac{459}{5661} &:= \frac{45+9}{5+661} \\ \frac{459}{56661} &:= \frac{45+9}{5+6661} \\ \frac{459}{566661} &:= \frac{45+9}{5+66661} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 460**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{460}{1012} &:= \frac{4+6+0}{10+12} \\ \frac{460}{10212} &:= \frac{4+6+0}{10+212} \\ \frac{460}{102212} &:= \frac{4+6+0}{10+2212} \\ \frac{460}{1022212} &:= \frac{4+6+0}{10+22212} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{460}{506} &:= \frac{4+6+0}{5+06} \\ \frac{460}{5106} &:= \frac{4+6+0}{5+106} \\ \frac{460}{51106} &:= \frac{4+6+0}{5+1106} \\ \frac{460}{511106} &:= \frac{4+6+0}{5+11106} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 462**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{462}{693} &:= \frac{4+62}{6+93} \\ \frac{462}{6993} &:= \frac{4+62}{6+993} \\ \frac{462}{69993} &:= \frac{4+62}{6+9993} \\ \frac{462}{699993} &:= \frac{4+62}{6+99993} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 465**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{465}{1023} &:= \frac{4+6+5}{10+23} \\ \frac{465}{10323} &:= \frac{4+6+5}{10+323} \\ \frac{465}{103323} &:= \frac{4+6+5}{10+3323} \\ \frac{465}{1033323} &:= \frac{4+6+5}{10+33323} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 468**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{468}{891} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{8 + 91} \\ \frac{468}{8991} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{8 + 991} \\ \frac{468}{89991} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{8 + 9991} \\ \frac{468}{899991} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{8 + 99991} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 471**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{471}{1727} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 1}{17 + 27} \\ \frac{471}{17427} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 1}{17 + 427} \\ \frac{471}{174427} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 1}{17 + 4427} \\ \frac{471}{1744427} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 1}{17 + 44427} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 474**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{474}{1738} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 4}{17 + 38} \\ \frac{474}{17538} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 4}{17 + 538} \\ \frac{474}{175538} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 4}{17 + 5538} \\ \frac{474}{1755538} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 4}{17 + 55538} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 476**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{476}{1848} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{18 + 48} \\ \frac{476}{18648} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{18 + 648} \\ \frac{476}{186648} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{18 + 6648} \\ \frac{476}{1866648} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{18 + 66648} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{476}{616} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{6 + 16} \\ \frac{476}{6216} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{6 + 216} \\ \frac{476}{62216} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{6 + 2216} \\ \frac{476}{622216} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{6 + 22216} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{476}{924} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{9 + 24} \\ \frac{476}{9324} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{9 + 324} \\ \frac{476}{93324} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{9 + 3324} \\ \frac{476}{933324} &:= \frac{4 + 7 + 6}{9 + 33324} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 477**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{477}{1749} &:= \frac{4+7+7}{17+49} \\ \frac{477}{17649} &:= \frac{4+7+7}{17+649} \\ \frac{477}{176649} &:= \frac{4+7+7}{17+6649} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 481**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{481}{1221} &:= \frac{4+8+1}{12+21} \\ \frac{481}{12321} &:= \frac{4+8+1}{12+321} \\ \frac{481}{123321} &:= \frac{4+8+1}{12+3321} \\ \frac{481}{1233321} &:= \frac{4+8+1}{12+33321} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{481}{814} &:= \frac{4+8+1}{8+14} \\ \frac{481}{8214} &:= \frac{4+8+1}{8+214} \\ \frac{481}{82214} &:= \frac{4+8+1}{8+2214} \\ \frac{481}{822214} &:= \frac{4+8+1}{8+22214} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 484**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{484}{1221} &:= \frac{4+84}{1+221} \\ \frac{484}{12221} &:= \frac{4+84}{1+2221} \\ \frac{484}{122221} &:= \frac{4+84}{1+22221} \\ \frac{484}{1222221} &:= \frac{4+84}{1+222221} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{484}{1331} &:= \frac{4+8+4}{13+31} \\ \frac{484}{13431} &:= \frac{4+8+4}{13+431} \\ \frac{484}{134431} &:= \frac{4+8+4}{13+4431} \\ \frac{484}{1344431} &:= \frac{4+8+4}{13+44431} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 486**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{486}{891} &:= \frac{48+6}{8+91} \\ \frac{486}{8991} &:= \frac{48+6}{8+991} \\ \frac{486}{89991} &:= \frac{48+6}{8+9991} \\ \frac{486}{899991} &:= \frac{48+6}{8+99991} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 488**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{488}{671} &:= \frac{48+8}{6+71} \\ \frac{488}{6771} &:= \frac{48+8}{6+771} \\ \frac{488}{67771} &:= \frac{48+8}{6+7771} \\ \frac{488}{677771} &:= \frac{48+8}{6+77771}\end{aligned}$$

● **Number 497**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{497}{781} &:= \frac{49+7}{7+81} \\ \frac{497}{7881} &:= \frac{49+7}{7+881} \\ \frac{497}{78881} &:= \frac{49+7}{7+8881} \\ \frac{497}{788881} &:= \frac{49+7}{7+88881}\end{aligned}$$

● **Number 505**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{505}{1111} &:= \frac{5+05}{11+11} \\ \frac{505}{11211} &:= \frac{5+05}{11+211} \\ \frac{505}{112211} &:= \frac{5+05}{11+2211} \\ \frac{505}{1122211} &:= \frac{5+05}{11+22211}\end{aligned}$$

● **Number 506**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{506}{1012} &:= \frac{5+06}{10+12} \\ \frac{506}{10212} &:= \frac{5+06}{10+212} \\ \frac{506}{102212} &:= \frac{5+06}{10+2212} \\ \frac{506}{1022212} &:= \frac{5+06}{10+22212}\end{aligned}$$

● **Number 510**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{510}{1122} &:= \frac{5+10}{11+22} \\ \frac{510}{11322} &:= \frac{5+10}{11+322} \\ \frac{510}{113322} &:= \frac{5+10}{11+3322} \\ \frac{510}{1133322} &:= \frac{5+10}{11+33322}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 511**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{511}{1606} &:= \frac{5+1+1}{16+06} \\ \frac{511}{16206} &:= \frac{5+1+1}{16+206} \\ \frac{511}{162206} &:= \frac{5+1+1}{16+2206} \\ \frac{511}{1622206} &:= \frac{5+1+1}{16+22206}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 512**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{512}{704} &:= \frac{5+1+2}{7+04} \\ \frac{512}{7104} &:= \frac{5+1+2}{7+104} \\ \frac{512}{71104} &:= \frac{5+1+2}{7+1104} \\ \frac{512}{711104} &:= \frac{5+1+2}{7+11104}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 515**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{515}{1133} &:= \frac{5+15}{11+33} \\ \frac{515}{11433} &:= \frac{5+15}{11+433} \\ \frac{515}{114433} &:= \frac{5+15}{11+4433} \\ \frac{515}{1144433} &:= \frac{5+15}{11+44433}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 516**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{516}{946} &:= \frac{5 \times 1 \times 6}{9 + 46} \\ \frac{516}{9546} &:= \frac{5 \times 1 \times 6}{9 + 546} \\ \frac{516}{95546} &:= \frac{5 \times 1 \times 6}{9 + 5546} \\ \frac{516}{955546} &:= \frac{5 \times 1 \times 6}{9 + 55546} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 517**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{517}{1034} &:= \frac{5 + 17}{10 + 34} \\ \frac{517}{10434} &:= \frac{5 + 17}{10 + 434} \\ \frac{517}{104434} &:= \frac{5 + 17}{10 + 4434} \\ \frac{517}{1044434} &:= \frac{5 + 17}{10 + 44434} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{517}{1551} &:= \frac{5 + 17}{15 + 51} \\ \frac{517}{15651} &:= \frac{5 + 17}{15 + 651} \\ \frac{517}{156651} &:= \frac{5 + 17}{15 + 6651} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 518**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{518}{1221} &:= \frac{5 + 1 + 8}{12 + 21} \\ \frac{518}{12321} &:= \frac{5 + 1 + 8}{12 + 321} \\ \frac{518}{123321} &:= \frac{5 + 1 + 8}{12 + 3321} \\ \frac{518}{1233321} &:= \frac{5 + 1 + 8}{12 + 33321} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{518}{814} &:= \frac{5 + 1 + 8}{8 + 14} \\ \frac{518}{8214} &:= \frac{5 + 1 + 8}{8 + 214} \\ \frac{518}{82214} &:= \frac{5 + 1 + 8}{8 + 2214} \\ \frac{518}{822214} &:= \frac{5 + 1 + 8}{8 + 22214} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 519**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{519}{1903} &:= \frac{5 + 1^9}{19 + 03} \\ \frac{519}{19203} &:= \frac{5 + 1^9}{19 + 203} \\ \frac{519}{192203} &:= \frac{5 + 1^9}{19 + 2203} \\ \frac{519}{1922203} &:= \frac{5 + 1^9}{19 + 22203} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 520**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{520}{1144} &:= \frac{5 + 20}{11 + 44} \\ \frac{520}{11544} &:= \frac{5 + 20}{11 + 544} \\ \frac{520}{115544} &:= \frac{5 + 20}{11 + 544} \\ \frac{520}{1155544} &:= \frac{5 + 20}{11 + 544} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 525**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{525}{1155} &:= \frac{5 + 25}{11 + 55} \\ \frac{525}{11655} &:= \frac{5 + 25}{11 + 655} \\ \frac{525}{116655} &:= \frac{5 + 25}{11 + 6655} \\ \frac{525}{1166655} &:= \frac{5 + 25}{11 + 66655} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 527**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{527}{1023} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{10 + 23} \\ \frac{527}{10323} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{10 + 323} \\ \frac{527}{103323} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{10 + 3323} \\ \frac{527}{1033323} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{10 + 33323} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 528**

$\begin{aligned} \frac{528}{1056} &:= \frac{5 + 28}{10 + 56} \\ \frac{528}{10656} &:= \frac{5 + 28}{10 + 656} \\ \frac{528}{106656} &:= \frac{5 + 28}{10 + 6656} \\ \frac{528}{1066656} &:= \frac{5 + 28}{10 + 66656} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \frac{528}{1584} &:= \frac{5 + 28}{15 + 84} \\ \frac{528}{15984} &:= \frac{5 + 28}{15 + 984} \\ \frac{528}{159984} &:= \frac{5 + 28}{15 + 9984} \end{aligned}$
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• **Number 530**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{530}{1166} &:= \frac{5+30}{11+66} \\ \frac{530}{11766} &:= \frac{5+30}{11+766} \\ \frac{530}{117766} &:= \frac{5+30}{11+7766} \\ \frac{530}{1177766} &:= \frac{5+30}{11+77766}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 535**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{535}{1177} &:= \frac{5+35}{11+77} \\ \frac{535}{11877} &:= \frac{5+35}{11+877} \\ \frac{535}{118877} &:= \frac{5+35}{11+8877} \\ \frac{535}{1188877} &:= \frac{5+35}{11+88877}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 539**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{539}{1078} &:= \frac{5+39}{10+78} \\ \frac{539}{10878} &:= \frac{5+39}{10+878} \\ \frac{539}{108878} &:= \frac{5+39}{10+8878} \\ \frac{539}{1088878} &:= \frac{5+39}{10+88878}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 540**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{540}{1188} &:= \frac{5+40}{11+88} \\ \frac{540}{11988} &:= \frac{5+40}{11+988} \\ \frac{540}{119988} &:= \frac{5+40}{11+9988} \\ \frac{540}{1199988} &:= \frac{5+40}{11+99988}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 544**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{544}{748} &:= \frac{5 \times (4 + 4)}{7 + 48} \\ \frac{544}{7548} &:= \frac{5 \times (4 + 4)}{7 + 548} \\ \frac{544}{75548} &:= \frac{5 \times (4 + 4)}{7 + 5548} \\ \frac{544}{755548} &:= \frac{5 \times (4 + 4)}{7 + 55548} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 549**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{549}{671} &:= \frac{54 + 9}{6 + 71} \\ \frac{549}{6771} &:= \frac{54 + 9}{6 + 771} \\ \frac{549}{67771} &:= \frac{54 + 9}{6 + 7771} \\ \frac{549}{677771} &:= \frac{54 + 9}{6 + 77771} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 550**

$\frac{550}{1155} := \frac{5 + 5 + 0}{1 + 15 + 5}$	$\frac{550}{605} := \frac{5 + 5 + 0}{6 + 05}$	$\frac{550}{726} := \frac{5 \times 5 + 0}{7 + 26}$
$\frac{550}{12155} := \frac{5 + 5 + 0}{1 + 215 + 5}$	$\frac{550}{6105} := \frac{5 + 5 + 0}{6 + 105}$	$\frac{550}{7326} := \frac{5 \times 5 + 0}{7 + 326}$
$\frac{550}{122155} := \frac{5 + 5 + 0}{1 + 2215 + 5}$	$\frac{550}{61105} := \frac{5 + 5 + 0}{6 + 1105}$	$\frac{550}{73326} := \frac{5 \times 5 + 0}{7 + 3326}$
$\frac{550}{1222155} := \frac{5 + 5 + 0}{1 + 22215 + 5}$	$\frac{550}{611105} := \frac{5 + 5 + 0}{6 + 11105}$	$\frac{550}{733326} := \frac{5 \times 5 + 0}{7 + 33326}$

• **Number 552**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{552}{1012} &:= \frac{5 + 5 + 2}{10 + 12} \\ \frac{552}{10212} &:= \frac{5 + 5 + 2}{10 + 212} \\ \frac{552}{102212} &:= \frac{5 + 5 + 2}{10 + 2212} \\ \frac{552}{1022212} &:= \frac{5 + 5 + 2}{10 + 22212} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 555**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{555}{1221} := \frac{5+5+5}{12+21} \\ \frac{555}{12321} := \frac{5+5+5}{12+321} \\ \frac{555}{123321} := \frac{5+5+5}{12+3321} \\ \frac{555}{1233321} := \frac{5+5+5}{12+33321} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \frac{555}{814} := \frac{5+5+5}{8+14} \\ \frac{555}{8214} := \frac{5+5+5}{8+214} \\ \frac{555}{82214} := \frac{5+5+5}{8+2214} \\ \frac{555}{822214} := \frac{5+5+5}{8+22214} \end{array}$$

● **Number 556**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{556}{1529} := \frac{5+5+6}{15+29} \\ \frac{556}{15429} := \frac{5+5+6}{15+429} \\ \frac{556}{154429} := \frac{5+5+6}{15+4429} \\ \frac{556}{1544429} := \frac{5+5+6}{15+44429} \end{array}$$

● **Number 567**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{567}{891} := \frac{56+7}{8+91} \\ \frac{567}{8991} := \frac{56+7}{8+991} \\ \frac{567}{89991} := \frac{56+7}{8+9991} \\ \frac{567}{899991} := \frac{56+7}{8+99991} \end{array}$$

● **Number 568**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{568}{781} := \frac{56+8}{7+81} \\ \frac{568}{7881} := \frac{56+8}{7+881} \\ \frac{568}{78881} := \frac{56+8}{7+8881} \\ \frac{568}{788881} := \frac{56+8}{7+88881} \end{array}$$

● **Number 576**

$$\frac{576}{792} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{7+92}$$

$$\frac{576}{7992} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{7+992}$$

$$\frac{576}{79992} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{7+9992}$$

$$\frac{576}{799992} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{7+99992}$$

● **Number 580**

$$\frac{580}{1276} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{12 + 76}$$

$$\frac{580}{12876} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{12 + 876}$$

$$\frac{580}{128876} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{12 + 8876}$$

$$\frac{580}{1288876} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{12 + 88876}$$

$$\frac{580}{638} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{6 + 38}$$

$$\frac{580}{6438} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{6 + 438}$$

$$\frac{580}{64438} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{6 + 4438}$$

$$\frac{580}{644438} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{6 + 44438}$$

$$\frac{580}{957} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{9 + 57}$$

$$\frac{580}{9657} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{9 + 657}$$

$$\frac{580}{96657} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{9 + 6657}$$

$$\frac{580}{966657} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{9 + 66657}$$

● **Number 581**

$$\frac{581}{1826} := \frac{5 + 8 + 1}{18 + 26}$$

$$\frac{581}{18426} := \frac{5 + 8 + 1}{18 + 426}$$

$$\frac{581}{184426} := \frac{5 + 8 + 1}{18 + 4426}$$

$$\frac{581}{1844426} := \frac{5 + 8 + 1}{18 + 44426}$$

$$\frac{581}{913} := \frac{5 + 8 + 1}{9 + 13}$$

$$\frac{581}{9213} := \frac{5 + 8 + 1}{9 + 213}$$

$$\frac{581}{92213} := \frac{5 + 8 + 1}{9 + 2213}$$

$$\frac{581}{922213} := \frac{5 + 8 + 1}{9 + 22213}$$

● **Number 585**

$$\frac{585}{1287} := \frac{5 + 8 \times 5}{12 + 87}$$

$$\frac{585}{12987} := \frac{5 + 8 \times 5}{12 + 987}$$

$$\frac{585}{129987} := \frac{5 + 8 \times 5}{12 + 9987}$$

$$\frac{585}{1299987} := \frac{5 + 8 \times 5}{12 + 99987}$$

$$\frac{585}{715} := \frac{5 + 8 + 5}{7 + 15}$$

$$\frac{585}{7215} := \frac{5 + 8 + 5}{7 + 215}$$

$$\frac{585}{72215} := \frac{5 + 8 + 5}{7 + 2215}$$

$$\frac{585}{722215} := \frac{5 + 8 + 5}{7 + 22215}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{585}{858} := \frac{5+8 \times 5}{8+58} \\ \frac{585}{8658} := \frac{5+8 \times 5}{8+658} \\ \frac{585}{86658} := \frac{5+8 \times 5}{8+6658} \\ \frac{585}{866658} := \frac{5+8 \times 5}{8+66658} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{585}{891} := \frac{5 \times (8+5)}{8+91} \\ \frac{585}{8991} := \frac{5 \times (8+5)}{8+991} \\ \frac{585}{89991} := \frac{5 \times (8+5)}{8+9991} \\ \frac{585}{899991} := \frac{5 \times (8+5)}{8+99991} \end{array}$$

● **Number 588**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{588}{1232} := \frac{5+8+8}{12+32} \\ \frac{588}{12432} := \frac{5+8+8}{12+432} \\ \frac{588}{124432} := \frac{5+8+8}{12+4432} \\ \frac{588}{1244432} := \frac{5+8+8}{12+44432} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{588}{1848} := \frac{5+8+8}{18+48} \\ \frac{588}{18648} := \frac{5+8+8}{18+648} \\ \frac{588}{186648} := \frac{5+8+8}{18+6648} \\ \frac{588}{1866648} := \frac{5+8+8}{18+66648} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{588}{616} := \frac{5+8+8}{6+16} \\ \frac{588}{6216} := \frac{5+8+8}{6+216} \\ \frac{588}{62216} := \frac{5+(8+8)}{6+2216} \\ \frac{588}{622216} := \frac{5+(8+8)}{6+22216} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{588}{924} := \frac{5+8+8}{9+24} \\ \frac{588}{9324} := \frac{5+8+8}{9+324} \\ \frac{588}{93324} := \frac{5+8+8}{9+3324} \\ \frac{588}{933324} := \frac{5+8+8}{9+33324} \end{array}$$

● **Number 592**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{592}{1221} := \frac{5+9+2}{12+21} \\ \frac{592}{12321} := \frac{5+9+2}{12+321} \\ \frac{592}{123321} := \frac{5+9+2}{12+3321} \\ \frac{592}{1233321} := \frac{5+9+2}{12+33321} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{592}{814} := \frac{5+9+2}{8+14} \\ \frac{592}{8214} := \frac{5+9+2}{8+214} \\ \frac{592}{82214} := \frac{5+9+2}{8+2214} \\ \frac{592}{822214} := \frac{5+9+2}{8+22214} \end{array}$$

● **Number 596**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{596}{1639} &:= \frac{5+9+6}{16+39} \\ \frac{596}{16539} &:= \frac{5+9+6}{16+539} \\ \frac{596}{165539} &:= \frac{5+9+6}{16+5539}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 605**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{605}{1815} &:= \frac{6+05}{18+15} \\ \frac{605}{18315} &:= \frac{6+05}{18+315} \\ \frac{605}{183315} &:= \frac{6+05}{18+3315}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 606**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{606}{1111} &:= \frac{6+06}{11+11} \\ \frac{606}{11211} &:= \frac{6+06}{11+211} \\ \frac{606}{112211} &:= \frac{6+06}{11+2211} \\ \frac{606}{1122211} &:= \frac{6+06}{11+22211}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 612**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{612}{1122} &:= \frac{6+12}{11+22} \\ \frac{612}{11322} &:= \frac{6+12}{11+322} \\ \frac{612}{113322} &:= \frac{6+12}{11+3322}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 615**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{615}{1353} &:= \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{13 + 53} \\ \frac{615}{13653} &:= \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{13 + 653} \\ \frac{615}{136653} &:= \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{13 + 6653} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 616**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{616}{1232} &:= \frac{6 + 16}{12 + 32} \\ \frac{616}{12432} &:= \frac{6 + 16}{12 + 432} \\ \frac{616}{124432} &:= \frac{6 + 16}{12 + 4432} \\ \frac{616}{1244432} &:= \frac{6 + 16}{12 + 44432} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{616}{924} &:= \frac{6 + 16}{9 + 24} \\ \frac{616}{9324} &:= \frac{6 + 16}{9 + 324} \\ \frac{616}{93324} &:= \frac{6 + 16}{9 + 3324} \\ \frac{616}{933324} &:= \frac{6 + 16}{9 + 33324} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 618**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{618}{1133} &:= \frac{6 + 18}{11 + 33} \\ \frac{618}{11433} &:= \frac{6 + 18}{11 + 433} \\ \frac{618}{114433} &:= \frac{6 + 18}{11 + 4433} \\ \frac{618}{1144433} &:= \frac{6 + 18}{11 + 44433} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 620**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{620}{1705} &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 0}{17 + 05} \\ \frac{620}{17205} &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 0}{17 + 205} \\ \frac{620}{172205} &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 0}{17 + 2205} \\ \frac{620}{1722205} &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 0}{17 + 22205} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 624**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{624}{1287} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{12 + 87} \\ \frac{624}{12987} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{12 + 987} \\ \frac{624}{129987} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{12 + 9987} \\ \frac{624}{1299987} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{12 + 99987} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{624}{858} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{8 + 58} \\ \frac{624}{8658} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{8 + 658} \\ \frac{624}{86658} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{8 + 6658} \\ \frac{624}{866658} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{8 + 66658} \end{array}$$

• **Number 625**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{625}{1375} := \frac{(6 + 2) \times 5}{13 + 75} \\ \frac{625}{13875} := \frac{(6 + 2) \times 5}{13 + 875} \\ \frac{625}{138875} := \frac{(6 + 2) \times 5}{13 + 8875} \\ \frac{625}{1388875} := \frac{(6 + 2) \times 5}{13 + 88875} \end{array}$$

• **Number 627**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{627}{1045} := \frac{6 + 27}{10 + 45} \\ \frac{627}{10545} := \frac{6 + 27}{10 + 545} \\ \frac{627}{105545} := \frac{6 + 27}{10 + 5545} \\ \frac{627}{1055545} := \frac{6 + 27}{10 + 55545} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{627}{1254} := \frac{6 + 27}{12 + 54} \\ \frac{627}{12654} := \frac{6 + 27}{12 + 654} \\ \frac{627}{126654} := \frac{6 + 27}{12 + 6654} \\ \frac{627}{1266654} := \frac{6 + 27}{12 + 66654} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{627}{1463} := \frac{6 + 27}{14 + 63} \\ \frac{627}{14763} := \frac{6 + 27}{14 + 763} \\ \frac{627}{147763} := \frac{6 + 27}{14 + 7763} \\ \frac{627}{1477763} := \frac{6 + 27}{14 + 77763} \end{array}$$

• **Number 628**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{628}{1727} := \frac{6 + 2 + 8}{17 + 27} \\ \frac{628}{17427} := \frac{6 + 2 + 8}{17 + 427} \\ \frac{628}{174427} := \frac{6 + 2 + 8}{17 + 4427} \\ \frac{628}{1744427} := \frac{6 + 2 + 8}{17 + 44427} \end{array}$$

• **Number 629**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{629}{1221} &:= \frac{6+2+9}{12+21} \\ \frac{629}{12321} &:= \frac{6+2+9}{12+321} \\ \frac{629}{123321} &:= \frac{6+2+9}{12+3321} \\ \frac{629}{1233321} &:= \frac{6+2+9}{12+33321}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 630**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{630}{1155} &:= \frac{6+30}{11+55} \\ \frac{630}{11655} &:= \frac{6+30}{11+655} \\ \frac{630}{116655} &:= \frac{6+30}{11+6655} \\ \frac{630}{1166655} &:= \frac{6+30}{11+66655}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 632**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{632}{1738} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 + 2}{17+38} \\ \frac{632}{17538} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 + 2}{17+538} \\ \frac{632}{175538} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 + 2}{17+5538} \\ \frac{632}{1755538} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 + 2}{17+55538}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 636**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{636}{1166} &:= \frac{6+36}{11+66} \\ \frac{636}{11766} &:= \frac{6+36}{11+766} \\ \frac{636}{117766} &:= \frac{6+36}{11+7766} \\ \frac{636}{1177766} &:= \frac{6+36}{11+77766}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 638**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{638}{1276} := \frac{6+38}{12+76} \\ \frac{638}{12876} := \frac{6+38}{12+876} \\ \frac{638}{128876} := \frac{6+38}{12+8876} \\ \frac{638}{1288876} := \frac{6+38}{12+88876} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \frac{638}{957} := \frac{6+38}{9+57} \\ \frac{638}{9657} := \frac{6+38}{9+657} \\ \frac{638}{96657} := \frac{6+38}{9+6657} \\ \frac{638}{966657} := \frac{6+38}{9+66657} \end{array}$$

● **Number 639**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{639}{781} := \frac{6 \times (3+9)}{7+81} \\ \frac{639}{7881} := \frac{6 \times (3+9)}{7+881} \\ \frac{639}{78881} := \frac{6 \times (3+9)}{7+8881} \\ \frac{639}{788881} := \frac{6 \times (3+9)}{7+88881} \end{array}$$

● **Number 640**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{640}{704} := \frac{6+4+0}{7+04} \\ \frac{640}{7104} := \frac{6+4+0}{7+104} \\ \frac{640}{71104} := \frac{6+4+0}{7+1104} \\ \frac{640}{711104} := \frac{6+4+0}{7+11104} \end{array}$$

● **Number 642**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{642}{1177} := \frac{6+42}{11+77} \\ \frac{642}{11877} := \frac{6+42}{11+877} \\ \frac{642}{118877} := \frac{6+42}{11+8877} \\ \frac{642}{1188877} := \frac{6+42}{11+88877} \end{array}$$

● **Number 644**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{644}{1012} &:= \frac{6+4+4}{10+12} \\ \frac{644}{10212} &:= \frac{6+4+4}{10+212} \\ \frac{644}{102212} &:= \frac{6+4+4}{10+2212} \\ \frac{644}{1022212} &:= \frac{6+4+4}{10+22212} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 645**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{645}{1419} &:= \frac{6+4+5}{14+19} \\ \frac{645}{14319} &:= \frac{6+4+5}{14+319} \\ \frac{645}{143319} &:= \frac{6+4+5}{14+3319} \\ \frac{645}{1433319} &:= \frac{6+4+5}{14+33319} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 663**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{663}{1683} &:= \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{16+83} \\ \frac{663}{16983} &:= \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{16+983} \\ \frac{663}{169983} &:= \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{16+9983} \\ \frac{663}{1699983} &:= \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{16+99983} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 664**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{664}{1826} &:= \frac{6+6+4}{18+26} \\ \frac{664}{18426} &:= \frac{6+6+4}{18+426} \\ \frac{664}{184426} &:= \frac{6+6+4}{18+4426} \\ \frac{664}{1844426} &:= \frac{6+6+4}{18+44426} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{664}{913} &:= \frac{6+6+4}{9+13} \\ \frac{664}{9213} &:= \frac{6+6+4}{9+213} \\ \frac{664}{92213} &:= \frac{6+6+4}{9+2213} \\ \frac{664}{922213} &:= \frac{6+6+4}{9+22213} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 666**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{666}{1221} := \frac{6+6+6}{12+21} \\ \frac{666}{12321} := \frac{6+6+6}{12+321} \\ \frac{666}{123321} := \frac{6+6+6}{12+3321} \\ \frac{666}{1233321} := \frac{6+6+6}{12+33321} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \frac{666}{814} := \frac{6+6+6}{8+14} \\ \frac{666}{8214} := \frac{6+6+6}{8+214} \\ \frac{666}{82214} := \frac{6+6+6}{8+2214} \\ \frac{666}{822214} := \frac{6+6+6}{8+22214} \end{array}$$

● **Number 668**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{668}{1837} := \frac{6+6+8}{18+37} \\ \frac{668}{18537} := \frac{6+6+8}{18+537} \\ \frac{668}{185537} := \frac{6+6+8}{18+5537} \\ \frac{668}{1855537} := \frac{6+6+8}{18+55537} \end{array}$$

● **Number 672**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{672}{1776} := \frac{6 \times 7^2}{1+776} \\ \frac{672}{17776} := \frac{6 \times 7^2}{1+7776} \\ \frac{672}{177776} := \frac{6 \times 7^2}{1+77776} \\ \frac{672}{1777776} := \frac{6 \times 7^2}{1+777776} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \frac{672}{792} := \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2}{7+92} \\ \frac{672}{7992} := \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2}{7+992} \\ \frac{672}{79992} := \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2}{7+9992} \\ \frac{672}{799992} := \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2}{7+99992} \end{array}$$

● **Number 682**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{682}{1023} := \frac{6+8 \times 2}{10+23} \\ \frac{682}{10323} := \frac{6+8 \times 2}{10+323} \\ \frac{682}{103323} := \frac{6+8 \times 2}{10+3323} \\ \frac{682}{1033323} := \frac{6+8 \times 2}{10+33323} \end{array}$$

● **Number 684**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{684}{1782} &:= \frac{6 + 8 \times 4}{17 + 82} \\ \frac{684}{17982} &:= \frac{6 + 8 \times 4}{17 + 982} \\ \frac{684}{179982} &:= \frac{6 + 8 \times 4}{17 + 9982} \\ \frac{684}{1799982} &:= \frac{6 + 8 \times 4}{17 + 99982} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 690**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{690}{1012} &:= \frac{6 + 9 + 0}{10 + 12} \\ \frac{690}{10212} &:= \frac{6 + 9 + 0}{10 + 212} \\ \frac{690}{102212} &:= \frac{6 + 9 + 0}{10 + 2212} \\ \frac{690}{1022212} &:= \frac{6 + 9 + 0}{10 + 22212} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{690}{1518} &:= \frac{6 + 9 + 0}{15 + 18} \\ \frac{690}{15318} &:= \frac{6 + 9 + 0}{15 + 318} \\ \frac{690}{153318} &:= \frac{6 + 9 + 0}{15 + 3318} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 695**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{695}{1529} &:= \frac{6 + 9 + 5}{15 + 29} \\ \frac{695}{15429} &:= \frac{6 + 9 + 5}{15 + 429} \\ \frac{695}{154429} &:= \frac{6 + 9 + 5}{15 + 4429} \\ \frac{695}{1544429} &:= \frac{6 + 9 + 5}{15 + 44429} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 707**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{707}{1111} &:= \frac{7 + 07}{11 + 11} \\ \frac{707}{11211} &:= \frac{7 + 07}{11 + 211} \\ \frac{707}{112211} &:= \frac{7 + 07}{11 + 2211} \\ \frac{707}{1122211} &:= \frac{7 + 07}{11 + 22211} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 712**

$$\frac{712}{979} := \frac{(7+1)^2}{9+79}$$

$$\frac{712}{9879} := \frac{(7+1)^2}{9+879}$$

$$\frac{712}{98879} := \frac{(7+1)^2}{9+8879}$$

$$\frac{712}{988879} := \frac{(7+1)^2}{9+88879}$$

● **Number 714**

$$\frac{714}{1122} := \frac{7+14}{11+22}$$

$$\frac{714}{11322} := \frac{7+14}{11+322}$$

$$\frac{714}{113322} := \frac{7+14}{11+3322}$$

$$\frac{714}{1133322} := \frac{7+14}{11+33322}$$

$$\frac{714}{1309} := \frac{7+1+4}{13+09}$$

$$\frac{714}{13209} := \frac{7+1+4}{13+209}$$

$$\frac{714}{132209} := \frac{7+1+4}{13+2209}$$

$$\frac{714}{1322209} := \frac{7+1+4}{13+22209}$$

● **Number 715**

$$\frac{715}{1573} := \frac{(7+1) \times 5}{15+73}$$

$$\frac{715}{15873} := \frac{(7+1) \times 5}{15+873}$$

$$\frac{715}{158873} := \frac{(7+1) \times 5}{15+8873}$$

$$\frac{715}{1588873} := \frac{(7+1) \times 5}{15+88873}$$

$$\frac{715}{1815} := \frac{7+1+5}{18+15}$$

$$\frac{715}{18315} := \frac{7+1+5}{18+315}$$

$$\frac{715}{183315} := \frac{7+1+5}{18+3315}$$

$$\frac{715}{1833315} := \frac{7+1+5}{18+33315}$$

● **Number 721**

$$\frac{721}{1133} := \frac{7+21}{11+33}$$

$$\frac{721}{11433} := \frac{7+21}{11+433}$$

$$\frac{721}{114433} := \frac{7+21}{11+4433}$$

$$\frac{721}{1144433} := \frac{7+21}{11+44433}$$

● **Number 726**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{726}{1452} &:= \frac{7+26}{14+52} \\ \frac{726}{14652} &:= \frac{7+26}{14+652} \\ \frac{726}{146652} &:= \frac{7+26}{14+6652} \\ \frac{726}{1466652} &:= \frac{7+26}{14+66652}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 728**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{728}{1144} &:= \frac{7+28}{11+44} \\ \frac{728}{11544} &:= \frac{7+28}{11+544} \\ \frac{728}{115544} &:= \frac{7+28}{11+5544} \\ \frac{728}{1155544} &:= \frac{7+28}{11+55544}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 729**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{729}{891} &:= \frac{72+9}{8+91} \\ \frac{729}{8991} &:= \frac{72+9}{8+991} \\ \frac{729}{89991} &:= \frac{72+9}{8+9991} \\ \frac{729}{899991} &:= \frac{72+9}{8+99991}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 730**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{730}{803} &:= \frac{7+3+0}{8+03} \\ \frac{730}{8103} &:= \frac{7+3+0}{8+103} \\ \frac{730}{81103} &:= \frac{7+3+0}{8+1103} \\ \frac{730}{811103} &:= \frac{7+3+0}{8+11103}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 731**

$$\frac{731}{1887} := \frac{7^3 + 1}{1 + 887}$$

$$\frac{731}{18887} := \frac{7^3 + 1}{1 + 8887}$$

$$\frac{731}{188887} := \frac{7^3 + 1}{1 + 88887}$$

$$\frac{731}{1888887} := \frac{7^3 + 1}{1 + 888887}$$

• **Number 735**

$$\frac{735}{1155} := \frac{7 + 35}{11 + 55}$$

$$\frac{735}{11655} := \frac{7 + 35}{11 + 655}$$

$$\frac{735}{116655} := \frac{7 + 35}{11 + 6655}$$

$$\frac{735}{1617} := \frac{7 + 3 + 5}{16 + 17}$$

$$\frac{735}{16317} := \frac{7 + 3 + 5}{16 + 317}$$

$$\frac{735}{163317} := \frac{7 + 3 + 5}{16 + 3317}$$

• **Number 736**

$$\frac{736}{1012} := \frac{7 + 3 + 6}{10 + 12}$$

$$\frac{736}{10212} := \frac{7 + 3 + 6}{10 + 212}$$

$$\frac{736}{102212} := \frac{7 + 3 + 6}{10 + 2212}$$

$$\frac{736}{1022212} := \frac{7 + 3 + 6}{10 + 22212}$$

• **Number 742**

$$\frac{742}{1166} := \frac{7 + 42}{11 + 66}$$

$$\frac{742}{11766} := \frac{7 + 42}{11 + 766}$$

$$\frac{742}{117766} := \frac{7 + 42}{11 + 7766}$$

• **Number 747**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{747}{1826} := \frac{7+4+7}{18+26} \\ \frac{747}{18426} := \frac{7+4+7}{18+426} \\ \frac{747}{184426} := \frac{7+4+7}{18+4426} \\ \frac{747}{1844426} := \frac{7+4+7}{18+44426} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \frac{747}{913} := \frac{7+4+7}{9+13} \\ \frac{747}{9213} := \frac{7+4+7}{9+213} \\ \frac{747}{92213} := \frac{7+4+7}{9+2213} \\ \frac{747}{922213} := \frac{7+4+7}{9+22213} \end{array}$$

• **Number 749**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{749}{1177} := \frac{7+49}{11+77} \\ \frac{749}{11877} := \frac{7+49}{11+877} \\ \frac{749}{118877} := \frac{7+49}{11+8877} \\ \frac{749}{1188877} := \frac{7+49}{11+88877} \end{array}$$

• **Number 752**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{752}{1034} := \frac{7+5^2}{10+34} \\ \frac{752}{10434} := \frac{7+5^2}{10+434} \\ \frac{752}{104434} := \frac{7+5^2}{10+4434} \\ \frac{752}{1044434} := \frac{7+5^2}{10+44434} \end{array}$$

• **Number 756**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{756}{1188} := \frac{7+56}{11+88} \\ \frac{756}{11988} := \frac{7+56}{11+988} \\ \frac{756}{119988} := \frac{7+56}{11+9988} \\ \frac{756}{1199988} := \frac{7+56}{11+99988} \end{array}$$

• **Number 768**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{768}{1776} &:= \frac{7 \times 6 \times 8}{1 + 776} \\ \frac{768}{17776} &:= \frac{7 \times 6 \times 8}{1 + 7776} \\ \frac{768}{177776} &:= \frac{7 \times 6 \times 8}{1 + 77776} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 770**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{770}{1155} &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 0}{1 + 15 + 5} \\ \frac{770}{12155} &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 0}{1 + 215 + 5} \\ \frac{770}{122155} &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 0}{1 + 2215 + 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{770}{1815} &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 0}{18 + 15} \\ \frac{770}{18315} &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 0}{18 + 315} \\ \frac{770}{183315} &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 0}{18 + 3315} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 774**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{774}{1419} &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 4}{14 + 19} \\ \frac{774}{14319} &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 4}{14 + 319} \\ \frac{774}{143319} &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 4}{14 + 3319} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 777**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{777}{1221} &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 7}{12 + 21} \\ \frac{777}{12321} &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 7}{12 + 321} \\ \frac{777}{123321} &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 7}{12 + 3321} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{777}{814} &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 7}{8 + 14} \\ \frac{777}{8214} &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 7}{8 + 214} \\ \frac{777}{82214} &:= \frac{7 + 7 + 7}{8 + 2214} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 782**

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{782}{1012} := \frac{7+8+2}{10+12} \\
 \frac{782}{10212} := \frac{7+8+2}{10+212} \\
 \frac{782}{102212} := \frac{7+8+2}{10+2212} \\
 \frac{782}{1022212} := \frac{7+8+2}{10+22212} \\
 \frac{782}{1122} := \frac{7+8 \times 2}{11+22} \\
 \frac{782}{11322} := \frac{7+8 \times 2}{11+322} \\
 \frac{782}{113322} := \frac{7+8 \times 2}{11+3322} \\
 \frac{782}{1133322} := \frac{7+8 \times 2}{11+33322}
 \end{array}$$

• **Number 785**

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{785}{1727} := \frac{7+8+5}{17+27} \\
 \frac{785}{17427} := \frac{7+8+5}{17+427} \\
 \frac{785}{174427} := \frac{7+8+5}{17+4427} \\
 \frac{785}{1744427} := \frac{7+8+5}{17+44427}
 \end{array}$$

• **Number 792**

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{792}{891} := \frac{7+9^2}{8+91} \\
 \frac{792}{8991} := \frac{7+9^2}{8+991} \\
 \frac{792}{89991} := \frac{7+9^2}{8+9991} \\
 \frac{792}{899991} := \frac{7+9^2}{8+99991}
 \end{array}$$

• **Number 805**

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{805}{1771} := \frac{8 \times 05}{17+71} \\
 \frac{805}{17871} := \frac{8 \times 05}{17+871} \\
 \frac{805}{178871} := \frac{8 \times 05}{17+8871} \\
 \frac{805}{1788871} := \frac{8 \times 05}{17+88871}
 \end{array}$$

• **Number 808**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{808}{1111} &:= \frac{8 + 08}{11 + 11} \\ \frac{808}{11211} &:= \frac{8 + 08}{11 + 211} \\ \frac{808}{112211} &:= \frac{8 + 08}{11 + 2211} \\ \frac{808}{1122211} &:= \frac{8 + 08}{11 + 22211} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 814**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{814}{1221} &:= \frac{8 + 14}{12 + 21} \\ \frac{814}{12321} &:= \frac{8 + 14}{12 + 321} \\ \frac{814}{123321} &:= \frac{8 + 14}{12 + 3321} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 816**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{816}{1122} &:= \frac{8 + 16}{11 + 22} \\ \frac{816}{11322} &:= \frac{8 + 16}{11 + 322} \\ \frac{816}{113322} &:= \frac{8 + 16}{11 + 3322} \\ \frac{816}{1133322} &:= \frac{8 + 16}{11 + 33322} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{816}{1683} &:= \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{16 + 83} \\ \frac{816}{16983} &:= \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{16 + 983} \\ \frac{816}{169983} &:= \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{16 + 9983} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 819**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{819}{1001} &:= \frac{8 + 1^9}{10 + 01} \\ \frac{819}{10101} &:= \frac{8 + 1^9}{10 + 101} \\ \frac{819}{101101} &:= \frac{8 + 1^9}{10 + 1101} \\ \frac{819}{1011101} &:= \frac{8 + 1^9}{10 + 11101} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 820**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{820}{1804} := \frac{8+2+0}{18+04} \\ \frac{820}{18204} := \frac{8+2+0}{18+204} \\ \frac{820}{182204} := \frac{8+2+0}{18+2204} \\ \frac{820}{1822204} := \frac{8+2+0}{18+22204} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{820}{902} := \frac{8+2+0}{9+02} \\ \frac{820}{9102} := \frac{8+2+0}{9+102} \\ \frac{820}{91102} := \frac{8+2+0}{9+1102} \\ \frac{820}{911102} := \frac{8+2+0}{9+11102} \end{array}$$

• **Number 822**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{822}{1507} := \frac{8+2 \times 2}{15+07} \\ \frac{822}{15207} := \frac{8+2 \times 2}{15+207} \\ \frac{822}{152207} := \frac{8+2 \times 2}{15+2207} \\ \frac{822}{1522207} := \frac{8+2 \times 2}{15+22207} \end{array}$$

• **Number 824**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{824}{1133} := \frac{8+24}{11+33} \\ \frac{824}{11433} := \frac{8+24}{11+433} \\ \frac{824}{114433} := \frac{8+24}{11+4433} \\ \frac{824}{1144433} := \frac{8+24}{11+44433} \end{array}$$

• **Number 825**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{825}{1815} := \frac{8+2+5}{18+15} \\ \frac{825}{18315} := \frac{8+2+5}{18+315} \\ \frac{825}{183315} := \frac{8+2+5}{18+3315} \\ \frac{825}{1833315} := \frac{8+2+5}{18+33315} \end{array}$$

• **Number 828**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{828}{1012} &:= \frac{8+2+8}{10+12} \\ \frac{828}{10212} &:= \frac{8+2+8}{10+212} \\ \frac{828}{102212} &:= \frac{8+2+8}{10+2212} \\ \frac{828}{1022212} &:= \frac{8+2+8}{10+22212} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 832**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{832}{1443} &:= \frac{8 \times 32}{1+443} \\ \frac{832}{14443} &:= \frac{8 \times 32}{1+4443} \\ \frac{832}{144443} &:= \frac{8 \times 32}{1+44443} \\ \frac{832}{1444443} &:= \frac{8 \times 32}{1+444443} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 833**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{833}{1617} &:= \frac{8+3 \times 3}{16+17} \\ \frac{833}{16317} &:= \frac{8+3 \times 3}{16+317} \\ \frac{833}{163317} &:= \frac{8+3 \times 3}{16+3317} \\ \frac{833}{1633317} &:= \frac{8+3 \times 3}{16+33317} \end{aligned}$$

• **Number 836**

$\begin{aligned} \frac{836}{1045} &:= \frac{8+36}{10+45} \\ \frac{836}{10545} &:= \frac{8+36}{10+545} \\ \frac{836}{105545} &:= \frac{8+36}{10+5545} \\ \frac{836}{1055545} &:= \frac{8+36}{10+55545} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} \frac{836}{1254} &:= \frac{8+36}{12+54} \\ \frac{836}{12654} &:= \frac{8+36}{12+654} \\ \frac{836}{126654} &:= \frac{8+36}{12+6654} \\ \frac{836}{1266654} &:= \frac{8+36}{12+66654} \end{aligned}$
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$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{836}{1463} := \frac{8+36}{14+63} \\
 \frac{836}{14763} := \frac{8+36}{14+763} \\
 \frac{836}{147763} := \frac{8+36}{14+7763} \\
 \frac{836}{1477763} := \frac{8+36}{14+77763} \\
 \frac{836}{1672} := \frac{8+36}{16+72} \\
 \frac{836}{16872} := \frac{8+36}{16+872} \\
 \frac{836}{168872} := \frac{8+36}{16+8872} \\
 \frac{836}{1688872} := \frac{8+36}{16+88872}
 \end{array}$$

● **Number 840**

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{840}{1155} := \frac{8+40}{11+55} \\
 \frac{840}{11655} := \frac{8+40}{11+655} \\
 \frac{840}{116655} := \frac{8+40}{11+6655} \\
 \frac{840}{1166655} := \frac{8+40}{11+66655}
 \end{array}$$

● **Number 848**

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{848}{1166} := \frac{8+48}{11+66} \\
 \frac{848}{11766} := \frac{8+48}{11+766} \\
 \frac{848}{117766} := \frac{8+48}{11+7766} \\
 \frac{848}{1177766} := \frac{8+48}{11+77766}
 \end{array}$$

● **Number 850**

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{850}{1887} := \frac{8 \times 50}{1+887} \\
 \frac{850}{18887} := \frac{8 \times 50}{1+8887} \\
 \frac{850}{188887} := \frac{8 \times 50}{1+88887} \\
 \frac{850}{1888887} := \frac{8 \times 50}{1+888887} \\
 \frac{850}{935} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 0}{9 + 35} \\
 \frac{850}{9435} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 0}{9 + 435} \\
 \frac{850}{94435} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 0}{9 + 4435} \\
 \frac{850}{944435} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 0}{9 + 44435}
 \end{array}$$

● **Number 852**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{852}{1562} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 2}{15 + 62} \\ \frac{852}{15762} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 2}{15 + 762} \\ \frac{852}{157762} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 2}{15 + 7762} \\ \frac{852}{1577762} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 2}{15 + 77762} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 855**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{855}{1045} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{10 + 45} \\ \frac{855}{10545} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{10 + 545} \\ \frac{855}{105545} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{10 + 5545} \\ \frac{855}{1055545} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{10 + 55545} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{855}{1254} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{12 + 54} \\ \frac{855}{12654} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{12 + 654} \\ \frac{855}{126654} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{12 + 6654} \\ \frac{855}{1266654} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{12 + 66654} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{855}{1463} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{14 + 63} \\ \frac{855}{14763} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{14 + 763} \\ \frac{855}{147763} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{14 + 7763} \\ \frac{855}{1477763} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{14 + 77763} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{855}{1672} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{16 + 72} \\ \frac{855}{16872} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{16 + 872} \\ \frac{855}{168872} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{16 + 8872} \\ \frac{855}{1688872} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{16 + 88872} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{855}{1881} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{18 + 81} \\ \frac{855}{18981} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{18 + 981} \\ \frac{855}{189981} &:= \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{18 + 9981} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 856**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{856}{1177} &:= \frac{8 + 56}{11 + 77} \\ \frac{856}{11877} &:= \frac{8 + 56}{11 + 877} \\ \frac{856}{118877} &:= \frac{8 + 56}{11 + 8877} \\ \frac{856}{1188877} &:= \frac{8 + 56}{11 + 88877} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 858**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{858}{1287} &:= \frac{8 + 58}{12 + 87} \\ \frac{858}{12987} &:= \frac{8 + 58}{12 + 987} \\ \frac{858}{129987} &:= \frac{8 + 58}{12 + 9987} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 864**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{864}{1188} &:= \frac{8 + 64}{11 + 88} \\ \frac{864}{11988} &:= \frac{8 + 64}{11 + 988} \\ \frac{864}{119988} &:= \frac{8 + 64}{11 + 9988} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 874**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{874}{1012} &:= \frac{8 + 7 + 4}{10 + 12} \\ \frac{874}{10212} &:= \frac{8 + 7 + 4}{10 + 212} \\ \frac{874}{102212} &:= \frac{8 + 7 + 4}{10 + 2212} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 880**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{880}{1155} &:= \frac{8 + 8 + 0}{1 + 15 + 5} \\ \frac{880}{12155} &:= \frac{8 + 8 + 0}{1 + 215 + 5} \\ \frac{880}{122155} &:= \frac{8 + 8 + 0}{1 + 2215 + 5} \end{aligned} \qquad \begin{aligned} \frac{880}{1815} &:= \frac{8 + 8 + 0}{18 + 15} \\ \frac{880}{18315} &:= \frac{8 + (8 + 0)}{18 + 315} \\ \frac{880}{183315} &:= \frac{8 + (8 + 0)}{18 + 3315} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 882**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{882}{1078} := \frac{8 + 8^2}{10 + 78} \\ \frac{882}{10878} := \frac{8 + 8^2}{10 + 878} \\ \frac{882}{108878} := \frac{8 + 8^2}{10 + 8878} \\ \frac{882}{1088878} := \frac{8 + 8^2}{10 + 88878} \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{l} \frac{882}{1617} := \frac{8 + 8 + 2}{16 + 17} \\ \frac{882}{16317} := \frac{8 + 8 + 2}{16 + 317} \\ \frac{882}{163317} := \frac{8 + 8 + 2}{16 + 3317} \\ \frac{882}{1633317} := \frac{8 + 8 + 2}{16 + 33317} \end{array}$$

● **Number 884**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{884}{1287} := \frac{8 \times 8 + 4}{12 + 87} \\ \frac{884}{12987} := \frac{8 \times 8 + 4}{12 + 987} \\ \frac{884}{129987} := \frac{8 \times 8 + 4}{12 + 9987} \\ \frac{884}{1299987} := \frac{8 \times 8 + 4}{12 + 99987} \end{array}$$

● **Number 888**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{888}{1221} := \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{12 + 21} \\ \frac{888}{12321} := \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{12 + 321} \\ \frac{888}{123321} := \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{12 + 3321} \\ \frac{888}{1233321} := \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{12 + 33321} \end{array}$$

● **Number 902**

$$\begin{array}{l} \frac{902}{1804} := \frac{9 + 02}{18 + 04} \\ \frac{902}{18204} := \frac{9 + 02}{18 + 204} \\ \frac{902}{182204} := \frac{9 + 02}{18 + 2204} \\ \frac{902}{1822204} := \frac{9 + 02}{18 + 22204} \end{array}$$

● **Number 909**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{909}{1111} &:= \frac{9 + 09}{11 + 11} \\ \frac{909}{11211} &:= \frac{9 + 09}{11 + 211} \\ \frac{909}{112211} &:= \frac{9 + 09}{11 + 2211} \\ \frac{909}{1122211} &:= \frac{9 + 09}{11 + 22211}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 910**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{910}{1001} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{10 + 01} \\ \frac{910}{10101} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{10 + 101} \\ \frac{910}{101101} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{10 + 1101} \\ \frac{910}{1011101} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 0}{10 + 11101}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 913**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{913}{1826} &:= \frac{9 + 13}{18 + 26} \\ \frac{913}{18426} &:= \frac{9 + 13}{18 + 426} \\ \frac{913}{184426} &:= \frac{9 + 13}{18 + 4426} \\ \frac{913}{1844426} &:= \frac{9 + 13}{18 + 44426}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 918**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{918}{1122} &:= \frac{9 + 18}{11 + 22} \\ \frac{918}{11322} &:= \frac{9 + 18}{11 + 322} \\ \frac{918}{113322} &:= \frac{9 + 18}{11 + 3322} \\ \frac{918}{1133322} &:= \frac{9 + 18}{11 + 33322}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 924**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{924}{1232} &:= \frac{9+24}{12+32} \\ \frac{924}{12432} &:= \frac{9+24}{12+432} \\ \frac{924}{124432} &:= \frac{9+24}{12+4432} \\ \frac{924}{1244432} &:= \frac{9+24}{12+44432}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 927**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{927}{1133} &:= \frac{9+27}{11+33} \\ \frac{927}{11433} &:= \frac{9+27}{11+433} \\ \frac{927}{114433} &:= \frac{9+27}{11+4433} \\ \frac{927}{1144433} &:= \frac{9+27}{11+44433}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 930**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{930}{1705} &:= \frac{9+3+0}{17+05} \\ \frac{930}{17205} &:= \frac{9+3+0}{17+205} \\ \frac{930}{172205} &:= \frac{9+3+0}{17+2205} \\ \frac{930}{1722205} &:= \frac{9+3+0}{17+22205}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 935**

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{935}{1815} &:= \frac{9+3+5}{18+15} \\ \frac{935}{18315} &:= \frac{9+3+5}{18+315} \\ \frac{935}{183315} &:= \frac{9+3+5}{18+3315} \\ \frac{935}{1833315} &:= \frac{9+3+5}{18+33315}\end{aligned}$$

• **Number 936**

$$\frac{936}{1287} := \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{12+87}$$

$$\frac{936}{12987} := \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{12+987}$$

$$\frac{936}{129987} := \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{12+9987}$$

$$\frac{936}{1299987} := \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{12+99987}$$

● **Number 945**

$$\frac{945}{1155} := \frac{9+45}{11+55}$$

$$\frac{945}{11655} := \frac{9+45}{11+655}$$

$$\frac{945}{116655} := \frac{9+45}{11+6655}$$

$$\frac{945}{1166655} := \frac{9+45}{11+66655}$$

● **Number 952**

$$\frac{952}{1122} := \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{11+22}$$

$$\frac{952}{11322} := \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{11+322}$$

$$\frac{952}{113322} := \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{11+3322}$$

$$\frac{952}{1133322} := \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{11+33322}$$

$$\frac{952}{1232} := \frac{9+5^2}{12+32}$$

$$\frac{952}{12432} := \frac{9+5^2}{12+432}$$

$$\frac{952}{124432} := \frac{9+5^2}{12+4432}$$

$$\frac{952}{1244432} := \frac{9+5^2}{12+44432}$$

$$\frac{952}{1309} := \frac{9+5+2}{13+09}$$

$$\frac{952}{13209} := \frac{9+5+2}{13+209}$$

$$\frac{952}{132209} := \frac{9+5+2}{13+2209}$$

$$\frac{952}{1322209} := \frac{9+5+2}{13+22209}$$

● **Number 957**

$$\frac{957}{1276} := \frac{9+57}{12+76}$$

$$\frac{957}{12876} := \frac{9+57}{12+876}$$

$$\frac{957}{128876} := \frac{9+57}{12+8876}$$

$$\frac{957}{1288876} := \frac{9+57}{12+88876}$$

● **Number 963**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{963}{1177} &:= \frac{9 + 63}{11 + 77} \\ \frac{963}{11877} &:= \frac{9 + 63}{11 + 877} \\ \frac{963}{118877} &:= \frac{9 + 63}{11 + 8877} \\ \frac{963}{1188877} &:= \frac{9 + 63}{11 + 88877} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 966**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{966}{1012} &:= \frac{9 + 6 + 6}{10 + 12} \\ \frac{966}{10212} &:= \frac{9 + 6 + 6}{10 + 212} \\ \frac{966}{102212} &:= \frac{9 + 6 + 6}{10 + 2212} \\ \frac{966}{1022212} &:= \frac{9 + 6 + 6}{10 + 22212} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{966}{1242} &:= \frac{9 + 6 + 6}{1 + 24 + 2} \\ \frac{966}{12742} &:= \frac{9 + 6 + 6}{1 + 274 + 2} \\ \frac{966}{127742} &:= \frac{9 + 6 + 6}{1 + 2774 + 2} \\ \frac{966}{1277742} &:= \frac{9 + 6 + 6}{1 + 27774 + 2} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 972**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{972}{1188} &:= \frac{9 + 72}{11 + 88} \\ \frac{972}{11988} &:= \frac{9 + 72}{11 + 988} \\ \frac{972}{119988} &:= \frac{9 + 72}{11 + 9988} \\ \frac{972}{1199988} &:= \frac{9 + 72}{11 + 99988} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 990**

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{990}{1155} &:= \frac{9 + 9 + 0}{1 + 15 + 5} \\ \frac{990}{12155} &:= \frac{9 + 9 + 0}{1 + 215 + 5} \\ \frac{990}{122155} &:= \frac{9 + 9 + 0}{1 + 2215 + 5} \\ \frac{990}{1222155} &:= \frac{9 + 9 + 0}{1 + 22215 + 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{990}{1815} &:= \frac{9 + 9 + 0}{18 + 15} \\ \frac{990}{18315} &:= \frac{9 + 9 + 0}{18 + 315} \\ \frac{990}{183315} &:= \frac{9 + 9 + 0}{18 + 3315} \\ \frac{990}{1833315} &:= \frac{9 + 9 + 0}{18 + 33315} \end{aligned}$$

● **Number 996**

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \frac{996}{1826} := \frac{9+9+6}{18+26} \\
 \frac{996}{18426} := \frac{9+9+6}{18+426} \\
 \frac{996}{184426} := \frac{9+9+6}{18+4426} \\
 \frac{996}{1844426} := \frac{9+9+6}{18+44426} \\
 \frac{999}{1221} := \frac{9+9+9}{12+21} \\
 \frac{999}{12321} := \frac{9+9+9}{12+321} \\
 \frac{999}{123321} := \frac{9+9+9}{12+3321} \\
 \frac{999}{1233321} := \frac{9+9+9}{12+33321}
 \end{array}$$

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